

**The Securitisation of Human Rights in Counterterrorism Operations in
Nigeria: A Case Study of Boko Haram in Northeastern Nigeria**

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ABSTRACT

Nigeria has experienced several ethno-religious, political, separatist and sectarian conflicts since its independence in 1960. The most recent and deadly is the Boko Haram insurgency in north-eastern Nigeria, which has claimed thousands of lives, cost billions worth of properties and devastating economic and humanitarian crises. In response to this conflict, the Nigerian government resorted to a strictly militaristic approach that has attracted widespread allegations of wanton human rights violations locally and internationally. Extrajudicial killings, torture, unlawful arrest and detention of suspects, and sexual abuses are the most common violations widely linked to the counterinsurgency operations in northeastern Nigeria. The Boko Haram insurgency marked a turning point in Nigeria's struggle against militant groups, and the phenomenon is yet to be fully understood. The dynamic nature of the conflict poses an even greater challenge to the government's old-fashioned military response. Although a plethora of anecdotal reports exist on human rights violations, most are based on secondary data from NGOs like Amnesty International and Human Rights Watch. Empirical research on the topic is scarce, ahistorical and fixated on already-known issues.

Against this backdrop, this study examines the interplay between human rights and security and how the demand for security and the need for human rights protection in armed conflict could be achieved. Specifically, the research investigates the nature and extent of these alleged violations by the Nigerian military and their impact on the civilian population within the context of International Relations and Regime. Thus, using a case study design and a qualitative research methodology, primary data on the encounters between the Nigerian military and civilians in the conflict was collected and evidence of these violations was documented and analysed. The coercive counterterrorism approach is ineffective and exacerbates and escalates the conflict. Thus, alternative human rights-compliant counterterrorism approaches such as intelligence gathering, dialogue and community policing are identified. The decolonisation of terrorism research from its current Westernised state to a more diverse, multi-dimensional, and transnational field is also proposed to promote ideas advanced by African-based scholars such as myself in dealing with terrorism in Africa, i.e., an African solution, by African scholars, for Africa's terrorism challenges.

Keywords: Counterterrorism, Human Rights, Security, Conflict, Northeastern, Boko Haram, Nigerian Military

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Dedication

I dedicate this research project to my late and beloved mother, teacher and best friend, Mrs Hafsat Joseph, who gave me a professorial title even before I began my doctoral studies. Undoubtedly, you would have been very proud of my academic achievements.

Declaration

I hereby declare that this is original research and has not been submitted or published elsewhere either partly or in full.

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Signature_____

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Contents

CHAPTER ONE (1)	13
1.0 Introduction	13
1.1 Study Background	16
1.2 The conflict setting	17
1.3 Problem Statement	19
1.4 Research Aim and Objectives	20
1.4 Research Questions	20
1.5 Theoretical underpinnings	20
1.6 Significance of the Study	23
1.7 Thesis structure	24
Conclusion	24
CHAPTER TWO (2)	26
UNDERPINNING LITERATURE AND THEORY	26
2.0 Introduction	26
2.1 Human rights or security, which comes first?	28
2.1.1 Human rights and security: the liberal theorists' perspectives	30
2.1.2 The realist theorists' perspectives	35
2.1.3 Classical realism and morality	37
2.1.4 Neorealism and morality	40
2.2 Human rights and security: finding a balance	42
2.2.1 Critics of balancing	46
2.3 The communitarian perspective	48
2.4 The diplomatic approach	50
Conclusion	52
CHAPTER THREE (3)	53
INTERNATIONAL AND DOMESTIC CT-TERRORISM FRAMEWORKS	53
3.2 The Four Pillars of the UN Global Counterterrorism Strategy	55
3.2.1 Measures to address the conditions conducive to the spread of terrorism	55
3.2.2 Measures to prevent and combat terrorism	55
3.2.3 Measures to build States' capacity to prevent and combat terrorism and strengthen the role of the United Nations system	56

3.2.4 Measures to ensure respect for human rights for all and the rule of law as the fundamental factor for countering terrorism.....	58
3.3 United Nations Office to the African Union (UNOAU) Counterterrorism Framework.....	59
3.4 Human rights challenges	60
3.5 Nigeria Counterterrorism Strategy in Context.....	62
3.5.2 The establishment of NACTEST and other associated Acts.....	62
3.5.3 Objectives of NACTEST	64
3.5.4 Forestall	64
3.5.5 Secure.....	64
3.5.6 Identify.....	65
3.5.7 Prepare.....	66
3.5.8 Implement.....	67
3.6 Torture and Counterterrorism	68
3.6.1 Introduction.....	68
3.6.2 The moral justifications and counter-justifications for the use of torture.....	69
3.6.3 Torture, the lesser evil?: a pre-requisite for defeating terror?	71
3.6.4 Torture, a necessary evil?.....	74
3.6.5 Torture, an incentive to speak, but not necessarily the truth	77
Conclusion	79
CHAPTER FOUR (4)	80
RESEARCH METHODOLOGY	80
4.0 Introduction.....	80
4.1 Research Question	81
4.1.1 Defining a research question.....	81
4.1.2 Research aim	82
4.2 Methodological underpinnings	82
4.3 Research design: Explanatory case study	83
4.4 Interpretive research	85
4.5 Epistemology	86
4.6 Positionality	87
4.7 Data collection	89
4.7.1 The Interview Setting	92
4.7.2 Sampling technique.....	93

4.6.3 Purposeful sampling	94
4.7.4 Population of the study	95
4.8 Data analysis and interpretation	97
4.9 Ethical considerations (Ethics approval reference number: 13294)	98
4.10 Limitations of the study	100
Conclusion	101
CHAPTER FIVE (5).....	103
A MILITARISTIC APPROACH TO COUNTERTERRORISM.....	103
5.0 Introduction.....	103
5.1 Indiscriminate, unlawful arrest and detention of suspects.....	104
5.2 Random, sporadic, and illegal arrests of civilians.....	106
5.3 Violations of privacy, rape, and extortion.	109
5.3.3 Sexual abuse	112
5.4 Evidence and prevalence of human rights violation	116
5.4.1 Extrajudicial killings	117
5.4.2 Torture and interrogation of suspects.....	120
5.5 When it is an issue of life and death, torture is inevitable.....	126
5.5.1 Torture: a waning technique.....	129
5.3.1 Data mining and security surveillance	131
Conclusion	135
CHAPTER SIX (6).....	136
A HUMAN RIGHTS APPROACH TO COUNTERTERRORISM IN NIGERIA.....	136
6.0 Introduction.....	136
6.1 Military force and counterterrorism: a strategic failure.....	136
6.2 The state vs human rights	138
6.3 Human rights in armed conflict.....	142
6.4 Human rights and security: Two different sides of a coin?	143
6.5 Compliance and the issue of balancing	146
6.6 Contrasting opinions from the participants	149
6.7 Alternative counterterrorism strategies.....	152
6.7.1 Dialogue and community policing	152
6.7.2 Dialogues in Africa: a retrospect	154
6.7.3 Dialogues with Boko Haram: A historical review	155

6.8 Community policing	157
6.8.1 The concept of community policing in the US and Africa: A comparison	158
6.9 Conclusion	160
CHAPTER SEVEN	162
DISCUSSION OF FINDINGS	162
EVIDENCE OF HUMAN RIGHTS VIOLATIONS IN THE BOKO HARAM COUNTERTERRORISM CAMPAIGN	162
7.0 Introduction	162
7.1.1 Indiscriminate and unlawful arrest and detention of suspects	162
7.1.2 Violations of privacy and rape	163
7.1.3 Torture and interrogation of suspects	165
7.1.4 Effectiveness of torture	166
7.2 Military force and counterterrorism	167
7.3 Alternative Counterterrorism Strategies	168
7.3.1 Dialogue	168
7.3.2 Dialogue and the future of counterterrorism in Nigeria	171
7.3.2 Community Policing	173
7.3.3 Deterrence as the solution	175
Conclusion	177
CHAPTER EIGHT (8)	178
The Securitisation of Counterterrorism Operations in Nigeria	178
8.0 Introduction	178
8.1 The rationalisation of securitisation in counterterrorism	179
8.1.2 National security	179
8.1.3 Global counterterrorism efforts	180
8.1.4 Collateral damage	180
8.1.5 National unity	180
8.1.6 Complexity of guerrilla warfare	181
8.1.7 Ignorance of the Law	181
CHAPTER NINE (9)	183
CONCLUSION	183
Recommendations and suggestions for further study	186
Appendix	192

Bibliography..... 199

List of Acronyms

ACF	Arewa Consultative Forum
AGF	Attorney General of the Federation
AI	Amnesty International
AMIB	African Union Mission in Burundi
APC	All Progressive Congress
ATCSA	Anti-Terrorism Crime and Security Act
AU	African Union
BBC	British Broadcasting Cooperation
CAN	Christian Association of Nigerian
CAQDAS	Computer Assisted Qualitative Data Analysis
CCTV	Closed-Circuit Television
CDVR	Commission Dialogue Vérité et Reconciliation
CIA	Central Intelligence Agency
CPC	Community Policing and Security Committees
CSOs	Civil Society Organisations
CVE	Counter Violence Extremism strategy
DSS	Department for State Security
DDR	Demobilisation, Disassociation, Reintegration, and Reconciliation
EU	European Union
ECHR	European Charter for Human Rights
ECOMOG	Economic Community of West African States Monitoring Group
FBI	Federal Bureau of Investigation
FCT	Federal Capital Territory
FININT	Financial Intelligence
GDPR	European General Data Protection Regulation
GEOINT	Geospatial Intelligence
GOC	General Officer Commanding

GWOT	Global War on Terror
HUMIT	Human Intelligence
HRW	Human Rights Watch
IAC	International Armed Conflict
ICRC	International Committee of the Red Cross
IDM	Investigative Data Mining
IED	Improvised Explosive Device
IHRC	Icelandic Human Rights Centre
IHL	International Human Rights Law
IHRL	International Humanitarian Law
IMINT	Image Intelligence
IOM	Organization for Migration
IPOB	Indigenous People of Biafra
IRA	Irish Revolutionary Army
IRIN	Integrated Regional Information Networks
ISWAP	Islamic State of West Africa Province
ISIS	Islamic State
JTF	Joint Task Force
MASSOB	Movement for the Actualisation of the Sovereign State of Biafra
MENA	Middle East and North Africa
MJTF	Multinational Joint Task Force
MLPA	Money Laundering Prohibition Act
NATO	North Atlantic Treaty Organisations
NACTEST	Nigerian National Counterterrorism Strategy
NEMA	National Emergency Agency
NEF	Northern Elders Forum
NGOs	Non-Governmental Organisations
NHRC	National Human Rights Commission

NIAC	Non-international Armed Conflict
NIJ	National Institute of Justice
NRC	Norwegian Refugee Council
NYPD	New York Police Department
OAU	Organisation of African Unity
OHCHR	Office of the High Commissioner for Human Rights
OSC	Operation Safe Corridor
OSINT	Open-Source Intelligence
PAGAD	People Against Gangsterism and Drugs
PNP	Professional Night Patrol
PTA	Prevention of Terrorism Act
SIGMIT	Signal Intelligence
TPIMS	Terrorism Prevention and Investigation Measures
UDHR	Universal Declaration of Human Rights Law
UK	United Kingdom
UN	United Nations
UNOHCHR	United Nations Office of the High Commissioner for Human Rights
UNOAU	United Nations Office of African Union
US	United States
USA	United States of America
USAID	United States Agency for International Development
WEIRD	Western, Educated, Industrialized, Rich, and Democratic
WMD	Weapons of Mass Destruction

CHAPTER ONE (1)

1.0 Introduction

An age of something implies the persistent occurrence of that thing in such a unique way distinct from other times we have lived, or the ones experienced by our culture. But terrorism is an ambiguous term, and its meaning is divergent. As such, once we accept that the killing and hurting of civilians to advance a political agenda constitute its defining elements, it suddenly becomes clear that, in the conventional sense, there is no such thing as the age of terrorism. In fact, such instances of violence are exiguous and very rare in North America and in Western European societies. The ‘war on terror’ is no different. Even before the 9/11 attacks, the warrior metaphor was already a popular acronym, especially in the 1990s when the ‘war on drugs’ and ‘war on crime’ existed (Gearty, 2007). The current war on terror, however, is unique as it is constructed as an existential threat. The 9/11 trauma, among other terrorist events, could be attributed to promoting the war on terror language in these new (often aggressive) forms. The most pressing concern with the war on terror is how it engendered a level of hostility unprecedented in a democratic dispensation to safeguarding civil liberties and how to counter this hostility (Gearty, 2007).

Chalk (1998) contends that since terrorism became a prominent issue in domestic and international politics in the late 1960s, liberal governments have been grappling with tackling the phenomena in a way that adheres to democratic tenets and conform with their legitimacy. Given that the security of citizens is one of the central pillars of contemporary liberal democratic government, and given the significant danger terrorism presents, there is a general demand that such governments should squarely deal with the threat. Nonetheless, the response to terrorism in a liberal state should not contradict the liberal democratic values and traditions, especially individual freedom and civil liberty, lest it risks losing its legitimacy and exacerbating the situation (Chalk, 1998).

Furthermore, the realisation of security and the defence of human rights are, in fact, not contradictory. Yet, the two terms, security and human rights, since 9/11, are in the shared

imagination, now viewed as almost irreconcilable opposition (Goold, 2007). Consequently, Goold also notes that most security and human rights debates are confronted by the implicit political call for balancing this dichotomy. Instigated by the urgency or imagined uniqueness of our times, safeguarding freedom through security without violating human rights has become the most pressing concern for government officials, legal practitioners, and academics. In addition, the problem of ensuring security and safeguarding democratic freedoms is not simply due to the perceived threats occasioned by 9/11 but an issue that liberal democracies have historically faced. This challenge triggers democratic politics and the pressure that stimulates its philosophical modifications. At the centre of any sovereignty is the security of the nation and the citizen, and the ability to effectively do so forms the basis upon which the capability of a modern state is determined. Hence, from both the Lockean and Kantian viewpoints, the attainment of security through liberal principles of human rights is what differentiates democratic and authoritarian states and the yardstick by which they are judged (Goold, 2007).

Equally, Sulowski (2017) notes that after the 9/11 attacks, it became increasingly recognised that internal and external security are intertwined and interconnected. These new threats experienced on 9/11 created serious problems for democratic states in North America and Europe. Soon thereafter, security experts in the US realised that the methods previously applied to combat terrorism were no longer applicable. Therefore, a new response to a new kind of threat was considered necessary, as President Bush stated: a new pattern of thinking on the right to war is required in dealing with the new form of a terrorist threat. As such, there was a consensus among Western states to implement counterterrorism measures, including efforts to modify domestic state security laws and collaboration with other states to combat terrorism. However, Sulowski further asserts that this led to increased state power, which contradicts the liberal tradition built on the rule of law and respect for human rights. Hence, a conflict between security and the provisions of human rights and the challenge of balancing these two inseparable values arises. Thus, an international legal system was set up to protect against and combat terrorism, comprising rules within the UN, the European Union and the Council of Europe, which are unique because they are designed to conform to human rights provisions, including those of the terrorists (Sulowski, 2017).

However, this global effort to prevent and combat terrorism in what was later known as the ‘Global War on Terror’ (GWOT), spearheaded by the US in the aftermath of 9/11, became controversial due to its human rights implications. According to Versteeg (2009), although the new legislation and counterterrorism measures aimed at improving domestic security, for the most, they resulted in unprecedented and wanton human rights violations. National security interests in most Western democracies became more paramount to civil liberty and human rights obligations. This trade-off triggered serious debate among scholars, security experts, academics, and human rights activists across the globe on the conditions and circumstances (if ever) within which trading human rights for security is justified (Versteeg, 2009). Most liberal democracies, including Nigeria, have ratified the nine “core” treaties on human rights as enshrined in the Universal Declaration of Human Rights (UDHR) and the International Humanitarian and Human Rights Law (IHL/IHRL) and other similar EU/UN Conventions and treaties. Despite this, much research suggests a derogation from these laws, especially amongst liberal states, in their collective counterterrorism efforts since the 9/11 attacks.

Therefore, using the Boko Haram insurgency as a case study, this research will examine the widespread allegations of human rights violations against the Nigerian army in Borno state in northeastern Nigeria. The interplay between human rights and security and how to balance the need for security and the demand for individual rights in armed conflict will be analysed. Additionally, this study will examine the issue of compliance with international standards and how that can be secured in such conflicts. Given their leadership role in the GWOT, the US and the UK are mentioned throughout the study. However, this is for reference purposes only and to give a broader perspective for a better understanding of most of the contentious issues on counterterrorism. Also, the US counterterrorism legislation has influenced the framing and drafting of counterterrorism laws globally, including in Nigeria, coupled with the dominance of Western scholars and, by extension, Western literature in terrorism studies. Therefore, in some instances, comparative analyses are made implicitly or explicitly to draw lessons from history, support or argue against a particular issue, or provide historical evidence, as the case may be.

1.1 Study Background

Human rights infringement is more likely and widespread during armed or violent conflicts (OHCHR, 2023). Nigeria has been ravaged by violent conflicts (including insurgency, terrorism, farmer-herdsmen conflict, and militancy.) since the return to democratic governance in 1999. Many insurgent groups perpetrating violent acts hold particular grudges against the Federal government. For instance, the Movement for the Actualization of the Sovereign State of Biafra (MASSOB) and the Indigenous People of Biafra (IPOB) are fighting for a perceived injustice against their geo-political zone(s). While the Niger Delta Avengers demand more resource control, and some groups revolt against democratic values, which are felt to have failed.

So far, the Boko Haram terrorist group has been the deadliest and is recognised by the international community as one of the most dangerous terrorist movements in Africa and the world (Global Terrorism Index, 2014). According to Human Rights Watch, the group's activities, especially in northeastern Nigeria, are said to have claimed over 20 thousand lives, the destruction of properties worth billions of Naira, the displacement of approximately 2.1 million people in the north-east and the resultant humanitarian crisis. Also, the group also engage in kidnapping, robbery, rape and the abduction of women and children (Human Rights Watch, 2018).

Furthermore, the group mainly targeted government security agencies, especially police and military personnel and formations. The insurgents have attacked and killed police officers at police outposts, checkpoints, and public offices and killed civilians in churches earlier in the conflict and mosques in the later part of the conflict. In addition, Boko Haram has also claimed responsibility for several bombings of security facilities, including army bases and barracks, using locally made IED devices and suicide bombings.

In response to the atrocities perpetrated by Boko Haram, the Nigerian government adopted several measures to confront and end the group's activities, with military force at the forefront of its counterterrorism strategies. As a result, the military was deployed in different parts of the Northeast, launching offensives on terrorist camps and hideouts. Also, government security spending (particularly on military hardware) such as fighter jets and other warheads has increased since the start of the insurgency. Other measures taken include the transfer of the

defence headquarters and all the security chiefs from the Federal Capital Territory Abuja to Maiduguri, the Borno State's capital, where the activities of the group were most prevalent. In addition, a Military Joint Task Force (JTF) was also created, consisting of all the security agencies in the country, and later, the Multi-national Military Joint Task Force (MJTF), comprising Nigeria, Niger, Cameroon, and Chad.

However, in its attempt to stifle the group and restore peace and order to the Northeast, the tactics used by the military have come under some scrutiny and criticism by both the media (local and international) and Non-Governmental Organisations (NGOs) such as Amnesty International and Human Rights Watch and other Civil Society Organisations (CSOs). The military has been accused of heavy-handedness in its approach, resulting in serious human rights violations of not only the militants but, critically too, the civilian population. Specific examples of these abuses include extrajudicial killings, torture, unlawful arrest/detentions and other crimes against civilians (Chika, 2015; cited in Human Rights Watch, 2018). A case in point was the public execution of Mohammed Yusuf, Boko Haram's founder, and some of his followers in 2009 by the Nigerian Military (Ngwodo, 2015).

In fact, many commentators have attributed the spike in the group's activities to these killings, which angered local communities, increased anti-government sentiments and made it easy for the group to recruit (HRW, 2012). For example, according to a local report, in one of the attacks by the Nigerian Air Force in Rann in Borno State, an estimated 234 civilians were killed (HRW, 2018). The military blamed false intelligence for the attack, claiming that it was intended for Boko Haram.

1.2 The conflict setting

Nigeria is in West Africa and shares borders with Cameroon, Niger, Chad, and the Benin Republic. The country has a rich cultural heritage and diverse ethnic, tribal, and religious groups. Even though there are over 250 ethnic groups and hundreds of languages, only the three tribes of Igbo, Hausa-Fulani and Yoruba make up the majority in the country. However, the official language in the country remains English. Agriculture has been the country's major source of revenue pre-independence and in the early 60s, but petroleum has taken over this position ever

since it was discovered. Christianity and Islam are the two most popular religions, while the remaining population practices the traditional religion, with the Northern part of the country being predominantly Muslim while Christians constitute the majority in the South, especially in the South-East and South-South region (Udo et al., 2022).

Borno, the origin and epicentre of the Boko Haram conflict, is a predominantly Muslim and agrarian state in Northeastern Nigeria. The state is ranked 6th out of Nigeria's 36 states in population, with over 5 million people and a land area of 70,898 km² (27,374 sq. mi). It shares borders with Cameroon, Niger, and Chad, with Kanuri being the major ethnic group.

From its independence in 1960 down to the civil war between 1970 and 1973 under the military junta and the subsequent return to democratic rule in 1999, Nigeria has faced several ethnoreligious, communal, and political insurrections, but none, not even the civil war has caused the level of devastation, violence, and destruction of lives and properties as the Boko Haram insurgency in northern Nigeria. This was described as the most dangerous and deadliest terrorist group in Africa in the 2014 Global Terrorism Index report (Global Terrorism Index, 2014).

However, Boko Haram did not emerge from a vacuum. It was occasioned by decades of bad governance, high-level and institutionalised corruption, endemic poverty, unemployment, and the negligence of the political elite to the yearnings and sufferings of the poor masses. As such, Shekau, the group's founder, preached against Western education, which he viewed as anti-Islam and incompatible with his people's culture, traditions, and values. He also condemned the Western system of government where corruption, injustice, and oppression of the poor thrived and advocated for establishing an Islamic state governed by Sharia law, which he believed was the solution to all the problems Nigeria is facing. This ideology gained Shekau a strong followership base, which Akali (2020) attributed to his charisma and enticing recruitment strategies, such as small business empowerment and the provision of food and shelter for hungry street boys (Akali, 2019). With this strategy, Shekau became a powerful figure to many of his followers, predominantly unemployed youths, first in Borno and later in the rest of the northeastern states of Nigeria.

It is imperative to note that even though its teachings were considered extreme by the government, the public, and even some sects of Islamic scholars, Boko Haram was largely a non-

violent and non-armed group until the public extrajudicial killing of the founder Shekau, alongside several of his members by the Nigerian military in 2009 in Maiduguri the Borno state capital. It was this government action that triggered serious outrage from his followers and sympathy from some of the residents in Maiduguri City and the surrounding states of Yobe, Adamawa, and Bauchi states. These widespread allegations of human rights violations occasioned by the over-reliance on the military force inspired this research.

1.3 Problem Statement

Whereas there are several research on the intersections between counter-terrorism and human rights, with scholars highlighting how counter-terrorism measures have indeed led to the violation of civil liberties and individual rights (Mbah and Nwangwu, 2014; Okoli and Iortyer, 2014; Lawal, 2015; Walker, 2016; Olugbenga and Ayooluwa, 2017; Ogoloma and Sampson, 2015; Onuoha, 2019; Ibekwe, 2018; Suleiman and Osakwe, 2020; Abdulazeez and Musa, 2021; Akinola, 2022; Ogbonnaya, 2023), there remains a gap in our understanding of how military forces and other counterterrorism security agencies perceive the need to protect human rights during their operations.

Additionally, many of the existing studies are based on secondary data from organisations such as Amnesty International. This underscores the need to fill this gap by generating primary data on real encounters between civilians and the military by engaging the victims of these abuses, government security forces, legislators, and government/non-government human rights institutions to get a clearer, broader, and an all-encompassing picture of the problem. Similarly, it is pertinent to examine incidents of human rights violations, document evidence from victims of abuse, and ascertain responsibility for violations. Furthermore, research is needed on the patterns of human rights violations in the Northeast to identify the role of state actors involved. In summary, the Boko Haram insurgency marked a turning point in Nigeria's struggle against militant groups, and the phenomenon is yet to be fully understood. Moreover, this changing nature of the conflict (as evidenced by the insurgency) and the government's old-fashioned response through force have resulted in human rights violations. Thus, the central focus of this study is the interplay between violent conflicts and human rights abuse in Nigeria's Northeast.

1.4 Research Aim and Objectives

Understanding the nature and extent of allegations of human rights violations by the Nigerian military in the Boko Haram conflict and how/why state actors rationalise the securitisation of human rights in Nigeria is the core of this study's primary aim. The research will also examine how the need for security and the demands of human rights can be balanced in armed conflict. The study has the following specific objectives:

1. To examine how state actors rationalise the securitisation of human rights in Nigeria and why.
2. To investigate the nature and extent of human rights violations by the Nigerian security forces in the Boko Haram insurgency in northeastern Nigeria.
3. To examine the Boko Haram conflict and its impact on human rights within the context of international relations and law
4. To analyse how to balance the need for security and individual rights demand.

1.4 Research Questions

1. How and why do state actors securitise human rights in Nigeria?
2. What is the nature and extent of human rights violations in the Boko Haram conflict (insurgency)?
3. How has the Boko Haram conflict impacted human rights within the context of international relations and law?
4. How can security and the demand for individual rights be balanced?

1.5 Theoretical underpinnings

The discourse on human rights in international relations has been centred mainly on the following broad perspectives. The realist perspective focuses on the relative power and conflicts of interest in a world characterised by anarchy. Thus, ample consideration is given to national interest and state sovereignty. It is, hence, largely state-oriented. When conceived thus, realism has often been viewed as opposed to or incompatible with human rights, particularly its

normative positions and elements of moral obligations. Such scepticism of international law is amply expressed in the literature (Morgenthau 1940; Krasner 2002). They argue against a single 'moral code' and insist that the actions of states cannot be judged from a moral perspective (Morgenthau 1979; Kennan 1985). It is further pointed out that States would be unwilling to accuse each other of human rights violations since they too could be accused of the same, which can also undermine their sovereignty (Krasner 1993, 164).

Furthermore, realists contend that normative values and international regimes, as expressed in human rights, cannot account for state actions given that they do not have any power by themselves. Thus, an international regime matters in so far as it reflects the pre-existing 'distribution of power in the world' (Mearsheimer 1994/95: 7), and norms get subsumed 'in the material structure of the international system' (Mearsheimer 1995, 91).

The second perspective is the institutionalist/liberal perspective, and rather than state-centred, it is more focused on inter-dependence, international organisations and regimes. It, therefore, largely focused on rules and procedures. Primarily grounded in the liberal approach of international relations and international law, this approach argues that rather than relative power (as argued by realists), it is instead the level of convergence on national preferences that is the most important influence on international cooperation (Burley, 1993; Moravcsik, 1992). Thus, within this theoretical framework, "effective international regimes are likely to emerge only where they have deep roots in the functional demands of groups in domestic and transnational society, as represented by the domestic political institutions that mediate between society and the state" (Moravcsik, 1995).

Securitisation theory has also gained prominence among scholars in the academic discourse on international relations and security (Waever, 1995; Huysmans, 1998; Williams, 2003; Balzacq, 2005; Stritzel, 2007; McDonald, 2008; Salter, 2008; Balzacq, 2011; Hansen, 2012). Within this school of thought, securitisation is viewed as a more radical form of politicisation. One of the proponents of this theory (Waever, 1988, 1995b, 1995c) contends that something becomes an international security issue when it is ascribed more importance than other issues and requires absolute priority. To attain this level of importance, the issue must meet this criterion: it should be presented as an existential threat, i.e., it supersedes the normal political logic of assessing issues against each other; it must be important that any other issue is irrelevant, which if not

tackled immediately, it will be too late. Once this criterion is established, the actor has earned the right to deal with the issue through extraordinary means beyond the existing rules, including limiting rights that are otherwise inviolable (Waever, 1988, 1995b, 1995c).

Therefore, according to this school of thought, security is a referential practice, and it is in this practice the issue qualifies as such – not simply because of a real existential threat but because the issue is presented in this manner. However, presenting an issue as an existential threat to a referent object alone does not create securitisation; it becomes securitised only if and when the audience, i.e., the public, accepts it. Securitisation is also attained not only by breaking the rules or mainly based on existential threats but also when the breaking of rules is legitimised based on these threats. Securitisation is, thus, successfully achieved when it has these three components: existential threats, emergency action and effects of interunit relations in which the breaking of rules becomes legitimised. The rhetorical constructs that make securitisation distinct are survival and priority of action based on the urgency of the situation and the swift attention it requires (Buzan et al. 1998). Terrorism presents distinctive challenges to the liberal democratic state. Specifically, terrorists question state legitimacy; consequently, democratic States must cautiously devise counter-terrorist strategies in a manner that does not undermine their values in the process. The 9/11 attacks on the US significantly underlined tension in the liberal perception and understanding of international order. As a result, substantive norms emerged that seek to justify the use of force against repressive states that violated human rights and failing states that either support terrorist organisations or are unable to control them. “The consequence of this shift towards substantive liberal norms in international society is to place significant power in the hands of those states and alliances which have the capacity to act militarily” (Mearsheimer, 1995).

When dealing with terrorism as a threat to liberal democracy, it is a common assumption that it is the terrorists who pose the greatest threat to the underlying principles and freedoms that are enshrined in this form of political life. Nevertheless, several examples show that states pose a greater threat to political and civil rights and, hence, the democratic liberal way of life by failing to limit, define or control its response to terrorism. This research work, therefore, adopts the institutionalist/liberal perspective. At the theoretical level, this perspective, unlike the realist, gives serious consideration to international terrorism and the threats it poses. To realists, there is

a divide between domestic and international and as such, terrorism does not materially affect the international system. For liberals, however, terrorism is considered an ideological challenge to the core values it espouses, including toleration, civility and progress.

Furthermore, much of the discussion has centred on international terrorism. When it comes to domestic terrorism, national security appears to trump all other considerations. There is as yet no clear understanding of the moral limits of state responses to domestic terrorism. Within this context, this research hopes to contribute to the literature by first expanding the discussion to domestic terrorism and the state's obligations to human rights integral to liberal democracy, even while safeguarding national security. One of the core questions this research will address is balancing the need for security and the demand for individual rights.

1.6 Significance of the Study

When it comes to domestic terrorism, national security appears to trump all other considerations. There is as yet no clear understanding of the moral limits of state responses to domestic terrorism. Within this context, this research hopes to contribute to the literature by first expanding the discussion to domestic terrorism and the state's obligations to human rights integral to liberal democracy, even while safeguarding national security. This is equally novel in that it seeks to go beyond a mere examination of the literature and laws to examine instead the complex relationship between human rights and violent conflicts and how human rights treaty obligations should apply in practice in armed conflicts such as domestic terrorism and insurgency in the context of international relations and regimes.

Furthermore, this study also critiques existing unconventional and often ineffective counterterrorism approaches, and identifies better alternatives that reflect the local realities of northeastern Nigeria. The most significant aspect of this research is that it will help better understand how and why state actors rationalise the securitisation of human rights for national security interests, especially on domestic and international terrorism-related threats. Thus, the insights from the Boko Haram case study will contribute to the wider debate in the field of security and terrorism studies, one that recognises the inherent link between security and human rights and the other that opposes this notion.

1.7 Thesis structure

This research is structured and presented across seven different chapters. The first and preceding chapter provides a brief and comprehensive historical background of the study both broadly within a global and Nigerian context, a geographic and demographic overview of the conflict setting, the existing gap in the literature on terrorism research in Nigeria, the research aims and objectives, and how important this research is in terrorism studies. The second chapter reviews broad and relevant literature on some contentious debates on security and human rights from both the realist and liberal perspectives within the context of international relations and regimes. Additionally, the third chapter analyses the international and domestic counterterrorism legal frameworks, consisting of the UN global counterterrorism strategy, the African Union (AU) counterterrorism framework, and Nigeria's national counterterrorism strategy. The fourth chapter presents a detailed discussion of the study's entire research framework, approaches, and philosophical lens applicable to the overarching research aim, question, and justifications for adopting them. Furthermore, the next two chapters are both data analysis chapters. The first data analysis chapter (fifth chapter) focuses on the militaristic approach to counterterrorism and the controversial issues associated with it to determine its effectiveness or lack of, both globally and domestically in the Boko Haram case; the second data analysis chapter (sixth chapter)

centres on the human rights approach to counterterrorism to elicit an understanding of the effectiveness of this approach compared to the coercive use of military force. The seventh chapter discusses the main research findings, while chapter eight examines how state actors rationalised the securitisation of human rights in armed conflict, which also serves as the study's main contribution. The thesis ends in chapter nine, which includes the conclusion, recommendations and suggestion for further research.

Conclusion

This chapter began with a philosophical outlook on the framing of the “war on terror” metaphor and how it evolved as a concept and later became a dominant phrase in both domestic and international discourse in terrorism and counterterrorism literature. The research topic was then

introduced, and a brief historical account of the different insurgencies and insurrections in Nigeria in general, and more specifically, a background to the Boko Haram conflict with its varying social, religious, and political ideologies and motivations and government interventions were presented. The chapter then highlighted the existing methodological and knowledge gap in counterterrorism literature on Boko Haram in Nigeria and outlined the overall research aim and question, including the specific questions and objectives of the study. The chapter concluded with an introduction of the two theoretical schools of thought around which the research will be framed, followed by an overview of the thesis structure.

CHAPTER TWO (2)

UNDERPINNING LITERATURE AND THEORY

2.0 Introduction

The concepts of 'security' and 'liberty' are not only contentious but also ambiguous. The first covers a spectrum of the core issues of human freedom at one end and a much shallow statement regarding the need for uncontrolled movement at the other. Just like security, the concept of liberty also has corresponding levels of ambiguity. Liberty has been conceptualised within the context of the individual and their relationship to others or the individual's link to society. At other times, it is viewed as freedom from all authority. Whereas other times, it is viewed as the active involvement in the affairs of government. Furthermore, there has been a debate on whether liberty, in its very nature, is analogous to civil liberties (Gearty, 2010). Lawyers in the pre-rights era in the sixteenth century understood civil liberties as being mainly the law regulating police powers, and it is perceived the same way even in practice. However, when considered within the context of 'national security', it has been argued that 'threats to national security generally prompt incursions on civil liberties' (Faber, 2008: 1).

Gearty (2010) notes that the field of counterterrorism studies emerged from the perception of security as protection from attack. However, a focus has shifted to 'human security', which emphasises people rather than places. The focus here goes beyond immediate attacks on liberties to issues of systemic failures in the public domain that make people less safe (Gearty, 2010).

The 9/11 attacks on the USA represented a watershed moment in international relations and changed the dynamics of terrorism and counterterrorism. It also changed the way in which national security is understood. In devising strategies to deal with emerging threats, democratic states in North America and Europe faced a serious dilemma of balancing increased state power and civil liberties, ingrained in the liberal tradition built on the rule of law and the respect for human rights (Sulowski, 2017). Therefore, it became increasingly clear that in the present globalised and unilateral world, both internal and external security are intertwined and interconnected. As such, the US's policy recognised that some of the methods previously applied to combat terrorism, like military force, were no longer applicable. Given the ever-evolving

nature of threats, it became necessary to devise new strategies for tackling them. More importantly, as stated by President Bush, a new pattern of thinking on the right to war was required in dealing with emerging threats (Sulowski, 2017). Furthermore, there was a consensus among Western states on the need to put in place new, robust, and all-encompassing counter-terrorism measures. This necessarily entails making changes to internal laws regarding state security and greater collaboration between states to combat terrorism. Thus, an international legal system was developed to protect against and combat terrorism. It consists of laws within the United Nations (UN), the European Union (EU), and the Council of Europe. These laws are unique because they are designed to conform to the provisions to protect human rights, including those of the so-called terrorists (Sulowski, 2017).

This chapter will review relevant literature on terrorism and counterterrorism and major themes within this field. Specifically, the intersection between human rights and security in the context of armed conflict and from an international law perspective will be examined. By so doing, this chapter intends to discuss some contentious issues and arguments on the trade-offs between human rights and security advanced by both the liberal and realist schools of thought in the field of international relations (IR). Thus, as Bruce (1994) advanced, the literature review in this chapter provides the basis for conducting the research (Bruce, 1994). Hence, the review of the extant literature is expected to identify gaps to be filled by this study (Nunan, 1992; Rudestam, 2001).

Traditional or narrative, systematic, meta-analysis and meta-synthesis are the four main types of literature review. This study adopts the traditional literature review approach due to its inherent advantage of analysing and summarising a body of literature on a particular subject matter. It also presents a comprehensive background of the studies undertaken in this area and helps to identify a given topic of interest to discover new research streams and gaps or discrepancies (Coughlan, 2007).

In line with the chosen literature review method, the materials reviewed here are mainly from peer-reviewed academic journals and textbooks. These sources are best suited for academic research projects and provide robust, credible, and verifiable data and information by some of the best scholars and authors in the field. Where necessary, this core set of data sources would be supplemented by sources in grey literature, such as newspaper articles, internet publications, and

reports from government and non-governmental organisations. Nonetheless, information from such sources is utilised to the extent that they provide relevant and credible information.

In a nutshell, this chapter examines the relationship between human rights and security and how the latter impacts the former. Specifically, the research explores literature and research on counter-terrorism measures of states in defence of national security and how they encroach on or violate human rights. Finally, a critique of how to balance human rights provisions and the demand for security, as well as the moral debate for and against torture in response to terrorism and terrorist threats, will be extensively discussed.

2.1 Human rights or security, which comes first?

There are divergent and contrasting opinions among scholars, policymakers, and security agencies on whether or not security should be given the utmost precedence over human rights or vice-versa. While there are many scholars in the current counter-terrorism discourse that advocate and promote compliance with the provisions of human rights at all costs and in every situation (Ackerman, 2004; Te'son, 2005), others argue that there are times when the demands of protecting national security take precedence over any other consideration, including civil liberties as entrenched in liberal and democratic principles (Elshtain, 2004: 87; Ignatieff 2004; Shue 2004: 55; Dershowitz, 2002).

The complex interconnectedness of security and human rights remains a very contested issue both globally and domestically. In Nigeria's context, certain historical, socio-political, and economic factors have shaped the understanding of this complex relationship between these values, especially among state actors. From a historical perspective, the approach to security has been greatly influenced by colonial and post-colonial experiences. Aghedo and Osumah (2015) observe that the framing of security in colonial times was largely focused on maintaining order and not the human rights of the local population. This colonial security legacy, characterised by militarisation and authoritarian rule, continued after Nigeria's independence, coupled with the long successive military rule that followed, during which the military security institutions put state control above any other human rights obligations (Aghedo and Osumah, 2015). These

authoritarian security features of the past still manifest in most Nigerian security institutions, especially the Nigerian military.

Furthermore, the pro-security characteristic of the Nigerian military was further reinforced during and after the 1967-70 Civil War, which saw the advancement of national unity and sovereignty that was bent on maintaining state might over human rights. As such, when faced with security challenges like the Boko Haram insurgency, the security forces easily perceive such events as threats to national security and survival and extraordinary measures that violate individual freedoms often find legitimacy on this basis (Chukwuma, 2020).

Another factor that shapes state actors' perception of security and human rights is Nigeria's religious and ethnic heterogeneity. Specifically, the deep-seated ethno-religious tensions in northern Nigeria, the stronghold of Boko Haram and other non-state armed groups, influence state actors' view of security. Extreme and heavy-handed tactics have often been justified even in local ethno-religious conflicts in the past, and Boko Haram is viewed as a much bigger threat to Nigeria's survival that must be tackled by any means necessary, even if it tramples human rights and civil liberty. The Nigerian military's aggressive response to Boko Haram is a reflection of a broader conviction among other security institutions that when dealing with terrorists it will be counterproductive if human rights protection is prioritised over security (Chukwuma, 2020; Oyewole, 2020)

In addition, economic factors such as endemic poverty, unemployment and hunger not only constitute the main drivers of the conflict and impact how security is viewed by security actors but also trigger the grievances that fuel terrorism. While these factors highlight the need for a human rights-based approach to security that prioritises addressing the root causes of terrorism, short-term and militaristic approaches that seek to suppress immediate threats instead of long-term solutions appear to be more appealing to security agencies. Worst still, the exploitation of security challenges for personal gains and enrichment among security forces, especially in the Boko Haram conflict, has continued to push security and state actors to sabotage security efforts and disregard human rights obligations (HRW, 2019; Amnesty International, 2020).

However, one must beware that from the very moment human rights got institutionalised, they are subjected to the constraining effects of international law, where states are still the main gatekeepers. As long as international law remains the law states agree upon (apart from the interpretation, over which they do not have full control), it will be, by definition, limited in terms of emancipatory potential for the powerless and right holders at large. This is what Stammers (2009) refers to as the ‘paradox of institutionalisation’ or what Koskenniemi calls the ‘colonisation of political culture by a technocratic language’ (1999: 99). In this section, the core arguments and justifications postulated by realist and liberal theorists would be examined in depth.

2.1.1 Human rights and security: the liberal theorists' perspectives

Meiser (2018) posits that liberalism is founded on the moral argument that the government’s utmost objective is safeguarding an individual’s right to life, liberty and property. Consequently, liberals attach serious importance to individual welfare as the foundation of a just political system. At the core of liberalism is the emphasis on creating institutions that safeguard individual liberty by putting checks and balances on political power. For instance, liberalists argue that the absence of a clear separation of powers and procedures for checking excesses means that dictatorships cannot safeguard the life and liberty of citizens (Meiser, 2018). Furthermore, liberal principles support international cooperation, human rights, democracy and the rule of law. Nonetheless, international norms are usually challenged due to widespread differences in values globally. However, there are consequences for violating liberal principles, which can be direct and immediate (Meiser, 2018).

Ideologically, liberalism is founded on the conviction of a Western tradition, which maintains that the individual has rights that must be respected by the government. Central to this thinking is the idea that individual persons possess basic rights such as freedom of speech, fair hearing, and political equality entrenched in a political constitution. In contrast to realists who justify the advancement of national interest built on Hobbes’ anarchic state of nature in ‘Leviathan’, and Machiavelli’s (1515) criticism of moral tradition in his work ‘The Prince’, liberals, however, build on John Locke’s (1660) work ‘Essays on the Law of Nature’, and the ‘Metaphysics of

Morals' by Immanuel Kant, (1797) which advocates for equal moral worth for all persons, and in which the infringement of rights in one part of the globe is felt in the rest of the world.

Both realism and liberalism have long traditions in IR. Displeased with the 'world as it is', liberal theorists consistently focused on the 'world as it ought to be'. Plato, Aristotle, and Cicero all belong to the school of political idealism with a shared conviction that there exist some universal moral standards upon which political life could depend. For instance, Cicero advanced the concept of natural moral law that was applied to both national and global politics. This idea was further developed by early Christian scholars, including St. Augustine and St. Thomas Aquinas. This is more pronounced in the latter's ideas regarding righteousness in war (Korab-Karpowicz, 2018).

Nagengast (2015) contends that in liberal philosophy, an individual comes first before the community, and the individual is independent and free from the oppression that may emanate under the guise of 'community interests. Due to the emphasis on individual rights, liberalism has little regard for the submission to the community's interests of the individual. From the liberal viewpoint, therefore, all individuals have the right to challenge the decisions of the government, and they should be able to exercise these democratic rights (Nagengast, 2015).

According to Mcloughlin (2016: 311), human rights gained recognition largely because it centres on a "moral discourse and set of ethical standards" that surpasses politics and provides a simple utopia that alleviates suffering without trying to drastically change the world. Authoritarianism is characterised by human rights infringements, and thus, the protection of human rights serves as a remedy to such evils (Mcloughlin, 2016). What really defines modern and Western democracy today is the fact that its symbolic framework is embedded in the liberal practice founded on the rule of law, the respect of the rights of the individual, the defence against repressive state meddling, and the protection of human rights (Mouffe, 2000 cited in Carson, 2017).

Likewise, to Weatherley (1999), regardless of the time the idea of rights or human rights was conceived, the substantial level of Western scholarly attention it has attracted provides for an easy way of identifying a widely 'Western liberal' concept of rights, largely since it is founded on an existing tradition of liberal thinking. The liberal philosophy upon which the human rights concept was born sees the individual basically as an independent being, living according to his protected personal interests (Weatherley, 1999). When it comes to defining human rights, and

especially from the perspective of the role of the state in safeguarding human rights, the shift towards the pursuit of liberal values of governance has been substantial (Nagengast, 2015). He further links the focus on human rights, especially in advancing the change from communalism to liberalism.

However, international law, which is also the major legal framework for the international community, is the consistent driver of a political agenda that is, for the most part, liberal (Schick, 2006). He further asserts that the moral image of international law is human rights, which are also integrally liberal and, without doubt, the most widely recognised lexis of morality in the international community (Schick, 2006).

Advocates of human rights maintain that the nexus between security and human rights is essential and that this link will only be strengthened by realising that human rights define human security. The achievement of security is dependent on the protection of human rights. Thus, human rights are the bedrock on which individual, national, and international development rests. Thus, development entails reverence for human rights, which, in turn, limits conflicts. As such, peace-making must be built on the pillars of human rights. More so, peacekeeping and peacebuilding should accommodate human rights provisions as well as its strategies. Also, on the issue of counterterrorism, Ramcharan (2004) advises that the repression of terrorism must not be tackled with more repression as this has proved to be ineffective. Hence, respect for human rights is the measure of human security.

Howard-Hassmann (2012) further argues that human security considerations and agendas have the potential to inadvertently undermine international human rights law. However, she also stresses that when human security simply rephrases human rights provisions without identifying the threats, it only complements human rights at best, and at worst, it could undermine them. Therefore, it is essential to note that protection, fulfilment of, and respect for human rights are not policy choices on the relationship between international human rights law and the debate on human security. By ratifying the obligation of international humanitarian law, states have no right to place one or set of rights above another; neither are they allowed to use real or perceived security threats as a basis to decide which rights to respect no matter the threat be it traditional state security such as military or other forms of threats (Howard-Hassmann, 2012).

Additionally, Roth (2015) states that the violation of human rights is not just wrong but also unwise and counterproductive. According to him, the violation of human rights is a critical factor responsible for provoking most of today's crises. Human rights require restrictions that can feel antithetical to a "do what it takes" attitude that often succeeds in times of serious security challenges. Nevertheless, over the years, violations of human rights depict how ill-advised that response can be. Human rights violations are often responsible for igniting further security challenges, and when these violations persist, prevailing challenges could be intensified. Roth (2015) also added that human rights are more than just arbitrary restraints on governments. They are the reflection of fundamental values, generally accepted and deeply held, enforcing limits on the power of governments and vital safeguards for human dignity and freedom. Betraying those values never turns out well. For instance, the extrajudicial killings of terrorist suspects without trial in Nigeria and elsewhere in Africa, or policies targeted at minority religions often lead to more radicalisation, as in the case of Boko Haram in Nigeria, Al-Shabaab in Sudan, al-Qaeda in the US, and ISIS in the UK. Addressing security challenges requires not just the containment of some dangerous elements but also the moral principles that strengthen the social and political order. The immediate success of undermining those principal values and the essential wisdom they represent is not worth the long-term consequences that must be inevitably paid (Roth, 2015).

This position is further maintained by Hicks (2005), who argues that the international war against terrorism has heightened extreme pro-independence and factional sentiment in many countries. It is also being used as a pretext by governments to curb the protection of human rights, especially of minority communities. The often-prolonged tensions between states and their oppositions, specifically in circumstances involving violent separatist or pro-independence groups, have worsened with emphasis on the use of military force on previous challenges reframed as terrorist threats. To Hicks (2005), the notion that human rights and security are adversative or negatively related is in contrast with the rationale that gave rise to the Universal Declaration of Human Rights (UDHR) and is extremely detrimental to the work of human rights advocates. Accordingly, he suggests that respect for civil liberties, democracy, and the rule of law is a crucial remedy to the conditions that promote terrorism. On the contrary, the encroachment of fundamental human rights in counter-terrorism measures can eventually be

counter-productive and obscure the difference between those who comply with the rule of law and those who disregard it (Hicks, 2005).

In the current discourse of security and human rights in counterterrorism, Te'son (2005) asks:

“How should democracies react to security threats? How can governments respond to intensified forms of violence, such as terrorism, internal insurrection, or external aggression, and at the same time remain true to the rule of law, civil rights, and democratic values? Commentators and courts in some democracies, while divided on vital issues, seem unwilling to agree on the view that some amendment to our liberties is justified to face these threats. But when, if ever, is such a limitation defensible? And is a limitation of human rights not self-defeating – are governments which curtail liberty not destroying democracy under the pretext of protecting it?” (Te'son, 2005: 57).

Moreover, Te'son (2005) argues that restrictions on liberty are justified only if they are done to preserve liberty itself rather than other values, such as security. One important corollary is that well-tailored counterterrorism is a fight for human rights and not the other way around. He also asserts that orthodox thinking poses the problem as a dilemma: democratic governments must choose between two competing values, liberty and order. According to Te'son (2005), the more freedom civil society enjoys, the closer it is to anarchy because it makes society vulnerable to victimisation by others. Equally, if the desire of civil society is the limitation of destructive behaviour, it risks losing the very freedoms that justify its existence in the first place. Human rights and security are not opposing values.

On the contrary, security measures are not justified by any other values, such as order or stability, rather than freedom itself. In addition, security measures are justifiable only by the very moral standards that legitimise the state in the first place, i.e., the obligation to preserve and safeguard the liberal constitution, be it based on human dignity, human rights, natural rights, or any such liberal principles of justice. For Te'son, whatever that balance may be, it should be justified if it is in the interest of freedom itself, not security. He concludes that the tussle against terrorism is not one that is in tension with human rights. It is a tussle, possibly the most significant one of our times, for human rights (Te'son, 2005).

For Ackerman (2004), 9/11 is an illustration of many similar attacks that will characterise the twenty-first century. He, therefore, calls for new and urgent constitutional concepts to address the protection of human rights. In the absence of that, politicians will only create new restrictive and suppressive laws that do not necessarily guarantee national security. Ackerman (2004) also states that although he respects the absolutist defence of traditional freedom, which holds that no matter the magnitude of an event or the enormity of an ensuing panic, strict protection of rights must always be adhered to notwithstanding, he does not share this view. If respect for human rights requires governmental paralysis, serious politicians will not hold back before sacrificing rights to the war on terrorism. By crushing civil liberties aside as impracticable, politicians will even gain more popularity and support. He then suggests that human rights advocates must provide a tough doctrine that allows temporary emergency measures in order to avoid a continuous circle of repression. Additionally, he warns that politicians must not be allowed to take advantage of the temporary panic to impose long-term restrictions on liberty. This underscores the need to take careful precautions, mainly owing to the fact that emergency measures have, in the past, continued beyond the specified time (Ackerman, 2004).

Parker (2012) further suggests that many states seem to intuitively use hard power when faced with a terrorist threat. However, he stresses that existing literature on terrorism indicates that the use of force can also aggravate the problem. Terrorist groups keenly seek to take advantage of the dynamics that promote radicalisation and violent extremism, and most of the time, states appear to fall into their traps. Terrorist groups globally have been successful in employing asymmetrical warfare, which is usually aimed at turning an enemy's strength into a weakness. According to Parker (2012), international human rights principles can assist states in moderating their counter-terrorism responses to avoid turning themselves into their own worst enemy, thereby building legitimacy and eventually creating more productive counter-terrorism strategies. Right is might when it comes to the fight against terrorism, Parker further noted (Parker, 2012).

2.1.2 The realist theorists' perspectives

Realism is commonly opposed to idealism or liberalism, both of which emphasise international norms, interdependency amongst states, and international collaboration (Korab-Karpowicz, 2018). The accumulation of power and the gratification of national interest among states in an

an anarchic world is at the core of realism, as propounded by Hobbes (1660). To realist theorists, the underpinning factor of states' relations in international politics is the quest and struggle for power, which is contrary to the liberal principles where human beings are perceived to be both rational and moral agents possessing the ability to discern right from wrong and make moral choices (Hobbes, 1660).

Korab-Karpowicz (2018) further posits that realists are, by and large, sceptical about the importance of morality to international politics. They typically argue that morality has no place in international relations; the demands for morality and requirements of positive political action contradict; customary morality is not the same as that of the state; and that morality, if used at all, is simply to rationalise the state's action. He also states that realism emphasises the restraints human beings place on politics, whom they perceive as selfish, and the absence of international sovereignty. According to him, these factors combined create a conflict-based model of relations among states in the international system, whereby states are the major players and power and security are considered the major issues, in which morality has little role to play.

The realists theorists world, according to Hanson (2008:63), 'is one where rules are regularly broken, and agreements last only as long as they benefit the contracting parties.' He further notes that realist theorists' scepticism towards human rights is, for the most part, due to the condition of international anarchy, the pursuit of the national interest, and the ethical rejection of the liberal supposition of a universal morality upon which the existing human rights regime is built. This idea of having one international moral code that will guide states' actions, both domestic and international, is unattainable from a realist viewpoint (Hanson, 2008). For realist theorist, the state has unitary features, as politics and ethics do not belong to the same realms (Casla, 2018). What determines whether an act is wrong or right is the outcome and not the act itself, and understood as such, realism is often viewed as barely attuned to a real moral obligation to normative values as provided in the human rights regime (Casla, 2018).

Realism, according to Donnelly (2000), stresses the restraints on politics imposed by human nature and the absenteeism of international government. These make international cooperation mostly a realm of power and interest. In addition, nature, realists claim, is at its core selfish and, therefore, unchangeably disposed towards immorality (Donnelly, 2000).

2.1.3 Classical realism and morality

Classical realism emerged as a theory of international relations after World War II (WWII) and is based on the idea that international politics is a product of human nature. The theory finds its roots in the works of early thinkers such as Niccolò Machiavelli, Thomas Hobbes, and Thucydides (Sørensen, 2007).

In his book 'The Tragic Vision of Politics' published in 2003, Lebow discusses the realist tradition at length, with a focus on the works of key realist thinkers such as Thucydides, Clausewitz, and Morgenthau. Classical realists tend to envisage states abstractly, as basically rational, purposeful, and motivated, but refuse to view them as "hyper-rationalist robots". Classical realists theorist believe that state behaviour is fashioned by the lessons of times past (right or wrong), ideas (accurate or not), and ideology (good or bad) and that fear, susceptibility, and hubris, usually in the context of substantial uncertainty impacts the choices they make (Kirshner, 2010).

Further, classical realism is more far-reaching than neorealism. It is also different from neo-classical realism (Steven et al., 2009). Classical realists theorist have a habit of overlooking the static distribution of power and focusing more on the 'dynamics of power relations over time' (Kirshner, 2010: 56). Classical realists like E. H Carr, view politics as the clash of interests in which power is the determinant factor of results, and in the long run, through military power. Many wars were fought not for specific goals but to create military supremacy (Carr, 1946). Furthermore, classical realist theorists such as Thucydides, Morgenthau, and Gilpin put great emphasis on their perception of humans as political actors. 'Man is a political animal by nature,' holds, 'born to seek power' (Morgenthau, 1946: 168). More than just security, then, this perspective emphasises that men covet what other men have and, worse still, that they have a desire for power as an end in itself (Gilpin, 1986).

The classic debate between liberalists and realists can be found in the 'Melian Dialogue' in Thucydides' history (Korab-Karpowicz, 2018). This debate centres on whether international relations can be established on a moral order built on the principle of justice or if, ultimately, it is at odds with national interest and power. Many of the assumptions regarding state actors, egoism, security, and anarchy that underpin the realist philosophy can be traced to Thucydides.

Additionally, human beings are seen as integrally egoistic and self-centred to a point where self-interest overwhelms moral values (Korab-Karpowicz, 2018).

Reinhold Niebuhr (1963) contends that morality was developed in ideas that are beyond the state and was connected to absolutist notions of right and wrong. Although he acknowledged that human nature, imperfect as it is, meant a universal type of morality was unattainable. Niebuhr viewed Judaeo-Christian morals as a means to moderate the quest for national interests based on the adage ‘do unto others as you would have done to yourself.’ Though he believed personally that the uppermost expression of morality for sane beings was ‘mutual love’, he recognised that this level of mutuality was impossible in an international setting consisting of states with uneven material abilities (Neibhur, 1963).

Morality is linked to the expansion of the national interest that comprises an appreciation for the interests of other nations. A consideration of common interests in foreign policy mirrored the definite conception of morality in state decision-making, but the requirement of self-interest and the bounds of human rationality stop morality from being universally realised (Neibhur, 1963).

Korab-Karpowicz (2018) further states that classical realists do not dispute the possibility of moral judgment in international relations. Rather, they are sceptical of moralism, i.e., a vague moral debate that disregards political realities. They give the highest importance to successful political action based on prudence, i.e., the capability to discern the appropriateness of certain actions from other possible alternatives based on their potential political repercussions.

At a time when the relations among states were considered virtuous, and ethical standards were dominant in political literature, Machiavelli (1975) developed an ideology that challenged this well-established moral tradition. Machiavellianism disregards the significance of morality in politics and asserts that all means, whether moral or immoral, to attain some political ends are justified. He further argues that the Western political thought at the time was unrealistic, and by separating politics from ethics, His work gained widespread prominence among notable thinkers such as Hegel, who shared in the idea that ‘the highest duty of the state is to maintain itself’ (Hegel, 1817:129). On his part, Hobbes (1660) argues that human beings are neither moral nor social but individualistic and, for this reason, are predisposed to a perpetual and relentless desire for power after power, which ceases only in death’ (Leviathan XI 2). Hobbes’ theory of

international relations suggests that sovereign states, like independent individuals, are natural enemies, unsocial and selfish, with no moral limitation on their behaviour (Hobbes, 1660).

Hobbes' work was further developed by other classical realists such as Morgenthau (1946, 1954), Mearsheimer (1994), and Carr (1946). For instance, Morgenthau (1946) postulates that all great powers in the past have enunciated universal claims: it should not be a surprise if such actions were beneficial to the dominant power. 'Realism maintains that universal moral principle cannot be applied to states' actions' (Morgenthau, 1954: 9). The appeals for compliance to the universal moral law, Carr (1946) contends, are mere strategies for concealing the pursuit of other selfish goals (Carr, 1946).

Following these early thinkers, others have argued that the appeals to conform to the universal moral law are merely ways of concealing the quest for narrow selfish interests (Mearsheimer, 1994). He further adds that normative values and international laws lack power in themselves. The Universal Declaration of Human Rights is incapable of accounting for state action, and it is thus undeserving of much consideration. International law is relevant only when it projects the prior distribution of power in the world and incorporates norms 'in the material structure of the international system' (Mearsheimer, 1995).

Furthermore, Carr (2001) describes liberalism's claim to moral universalism and its idea of the accord of interests as 'utopianism'. In his work *The Twenty Years' Crisis*, first published in 1939, he argues that 'morality can only be relative, not universal.' In addition, he used the concept of relativity of thought to say that standards used in measuring policies are the outcomes of circumstances and interests. The interests of a given party, he asserts, often determine what it considers moral. As such, values such as peace or justice, usually regarded and promoted by liberalists as universal, are actually not (Carr, 2001). Politicians, for instance, he observes, often use the rhetoric of justice to conceal the interests of their countries or to justify acts of aggression. Thus, he insists that this act of discrediting a potential enemy on the premise of morality or morally justifying one's own position proves that moral ideas are derived from real policies (Carr, 2001).

2.1.4 Neorealism and morality

Neorealism is an ideological departure from Hans Morgenthau's writing on classical realism. Classical realism originally explained the machinations of international politics as being based on human nature and, therefore, subject to the ego and emotion of world leaders (Morgenthau, 1948). Neo-realist thinkers such as John Mearsheimer and Kenneth Waltz, instead, argue that structural restraints rather than strategy, egoism, or motivation are what will govern behaviour in international relations. In his book *The Tragedy of Great Power Politics*, Mearsheimer (2001) made a clear distinction between his philosophy of offensive neorealism and Morgenthau's classical realism.

The idea of power and state behaviour in classical realist philosophy is viewed differently by Kenneth Waltz (1979). In contrast, classical realists such as Morgenthau view power as both a means and an end and rational state behaviour as the main course of action that would accumulate the most power. On the contrary, neorealists assert that security is the major interest of every state, hence the emphasis on power distribution. Methodological rigour and scientific self-conception are among the factors that separate neorealism from classical realism (Stefano, 1998).

Neorealism, or structural realism as referred to by some scholars, is a theory of international relations in which power is viewed as the most significant factor in the relations among states at the international level. Waltz is credited for being the pioneer of this theory in his 1979 book *Theory of International Politics* (Scott, 2004). 'Alongside neoliberalism, neorealism is one of the two most influential contemporary approaches to international relations; the two perspectives have dominated international relations theory for the last three decades' (Robert, 1994: 313). The prominent proponents of neorealism include John Mearsheimer, Stephen Walt, Kenneth Waltz, Richard K. Betts, Robert Gilpin, Robert W. Tucker, Joseph Grieco, Robert Jervis, Christopher Layne, and Jack Snyder.

Contemporary realist theorists cling to Hobbes' argument that treaties that are not imposed by force 'are just words', which implies that the diplomacy of human rights is largely posturing. The realists' understanding of human rights is that they are simply part of the terminology of contemporary international society. After all, the principles upon which the human rights regime

is built were never publicly questioned by any state leader. Hanson (2008) added that realists argue that in desperate times, human rights are least on the priority list of national policy goals. Thus, from the realist standpoint, it makes no sense for states to promote human rights if doing so does not advance national interest (Hanson, 2008).

From the realist theorist perspective and as Posner (2005) notes, because human rights regimes cost liberal governments nothing, they keep drafting, signing, and ratifying them to project a good image of themselves to the international community. Similarly, Landman (2006) contends that states allow the emergence and improvement of human rights simply for short-term benefits and to advance international legitimacy while depending on weak and non-binding legal obligations (Posner, 2005; Landman, 2006).

Classical realist theorists view of international law regarding the state's morality from Hobbes' time to present-day neorealism continues to influence the current debate on security and human rights. After the 9/11 attack, the debate between realists and liberals on the issue of absolute compliance with international norms, as provided in the international humanitarian regimes, has heightened. Liberals largely adopt an absolutist position, which maintains that states should always comply with human rights provisions in all circumstances. This position poses serious challenges even to liberal governments who are confronted with the evolving threat of modern terrorism. For instance, Schmitt (2007) contends that the liberal proposition, which suggests that morality is not an issue to be debated and its applicability is always a superior universal moral code and, in all places, is simply political rhetoric (Schmitt, 2007).

Others have argued that human rights regimes have fallen short of their expectations. Posner (2014) argues that there is hardly any evidence to indicate that they have enhanced the well-being of the people. This, according to him, is because human rights have never been universal as they are often desired to be, and the idea that they could be imposed under the provisions of international law was misleading from the onset. He further claims that what constitutes a major challenge to human rights law is its ambiguity. This vagueness, which affords governments the opportunity to justify virtually anything they do, is not due to careless drafting of the laws but rather the deliberate decision to put too much weight on the treaties with obligations that are ill-defined. This huge number of poorly defined rights inevitably provides states with immense discretion. This problem occurs mainly at the international level but not at the state level, where

trusted institutions are vested with the responsibility of interpreting and defining ambiguous sets of rights and making compromises between different rights. In essence, therefore, the international humanitarian regime fails due to the difficulty of reducing the ideals of 'good governance' to a group of well-defined rules that are interpretable and enforceable by trusted institutions (Posner, 2014).

For Koskeniemi (2005), international law and International Humanitarian Law (IHL), to be specific, are double-edged swords that serve two opposite purposes at the same time. He claims that, on the one hand, international law depends on states' will, which has the virtue of authenticity. However, when it becomes too attached to the state's real practice and comes short of creating new obligations for states, it becomes 'apologetic' of established power, giving justification for it. Furthermore, attempts to derive the meaning of human rights from international law have become a practice of 'hegemonic contestation', in which international players, consisting of state officials, international NGOs, and propagandists, amongst others, regularly challenge one another by imposing laws and principles upon which they give meanings that advance their interests against those of their enemies (Koskeniemi, 2005; 2004).

Similarly, Schick (2006) contends that human rights law is inherently not consistent because they are derived from two different languages of liberalism (social and cosmopolitan), which are based on differing perceptions of the international system. As such, human rights law promotes a division between theory and practice. Conversely, the systematisation of rules has received too much attention instead of enforcement. The common assumption that human rights will be enforced once they become codified deviates from the political circumstances that make enforcement possible. Schick also argues that the lack of coherence in the current debate on international human rights law constitutes one of its key problems (Schick, 2006).

2.2 Human rights and security: finding a balance

The debate between liberalists and realists regarding human rights and security in counter-terrorism studies, as highlighted above, continues to rage. On the one hand, liberalists insist that a line must be drawn between security and human rights and that there can be no justification whatsoever that permits states to trample civil liberties in the name of security. On the other

hand, realists argue that states can use whatever means necessary to prevent an imminent terrorist attack, even if it means limiting some civil liberties. To realists, it is justifiable to limit human rights so long as this is done to protect life. In contrast to these two extreme positions, some argue that human rights and security are relatively connected. As such, they strive to find a balance instead. Proponents of this position argue that both human rights and security complement each other in counterterrorism. Thus, it is impossible to have security without the protection of human rights. This position is summed by Lazarus and Goold (2007) thus:

“The attainment of security and the protection of human rights are not necessarily antithetical, either as a matter of fact or principle. Nevertheless, since 9/11, the words ‘security’ and ‘human rights’ have, in the collective imagination, now come to connote an almost insuperable opposition. Anyone who engages in the debate over security and human rights is almost immediately confronted by this dichotomy, tacit in the political call for a ‘new balance’ and explicit in newspaper editorials calling for the retreat from human rights. Prompted by the urgency or supposed ‘exceptionalism’ of our times, politicians, judges, and intellectuals are all addressing the central dilemma of this dichotomy: how are we to protect freedom (through security) without denying its essence (by violating human rights)? For liberals, the search for a new language of reconciliation between security and human rights has arguably become one of their most urgent intellectual challenges” (Goold, 2007: 1).

In their work, *Security and Human Rights: The Search for a Language of Reconciliation*, Lazarus and Goold (2007) note that what makes liberal democracies unique from totalitarian governments is that the achievement of security through the practice of democratic independence is justified absolutely by the pursuit of liberty, which itself is impossible to be achieved in situations of insecurity. Human rights as positive dictions of the components of liberty are the measure by which liberal democracies are judged. Constitutions, parliaments, and courts act to safeguard them and to check the executive’s abuse of authority. Security as the pre-requisite for liberty, and human rights as the components of liberty are, therefore, integral parts of the wider liberal democratic project. In view of the above, Goold (2007) points out that:

“We must find ways of reconciling security with liberty since the success of one helps the other. The choice between security and liberty is a false choice. Our history has shown us

that insecurity threatens liberty. Yet if our liberties are curtailed, we lose the values that we are struggling to defend” (Lazarus and Goold, 2007: 2).

The quest for a balance between human rights and security in counterterrorism continues to prove difficult for states, policymakers, and human rights advocates. According to Goold (2007), for the better part of the last fifty years, US foreign policymakers have largely perceived human rights advancement and safeguarding national security as a conundrum. This is because the two have been exclusively treated by each administration: either human rights are promoted at the peril of national security or vice versa. Although US policymakers have sometimes demonstrated concerns for human rights, these have largely stood in conflict with national security. For instance, in 2002, President Bush stated that the US is committed to the protection of human rights. Yet, in the same document, he forcefully maintained that defending the US from its adversaries was the major priority of the federal government. Thus, human rights are subordinated to national security. Contrary to this position, those who seek a balance insist that a more effective US foreign policy is one that recognises human rights and national security as all-encompassing goals.

The middle-point position had earlier been advanced by Burke-white (2004). He asserts that, since the emergence of the human rights campaign in the mid-twentieth century, their advancement has been adjudged to be in competition with or even inimical to national security. Support for human rights has long been seen as a luxury to be considered only when the government has the spare diplomatic capacity and when national security is not threatened. Consequently, national security has generally truncated human rights in much of US policy. However, Burke-White (2004) argues that human rights and national security should be complementary rather than being considered antithetical. Accordingly, he developed three hypotheses to show the correlation between domestic human rights abuses and the aggression between states after the Cold War era. First, he argues that states that systematically limit human rights internally have a high possibility of engaging in transnational aggression. Second, states who have good human rights records are not likely to engage in international aggression. Third, states that respect human rights may likely engage in international intervention in accordance with international law to protect the human rights of citizens in states with records of human rights violations. He further claims that if his hypotheses are correct, it implies that a foreign policy that strongly promotes human rights globally can enhance both national and international

security by reducing the number of states that may possibly engage in international aggression (Burke-White, 2004).

The approach to liberty that easily puts the needs of the state at the expense of individual liberty has largely been influenced by Hobbes's idea of liberty (Gearthy, 2010). This idea has equally influenced or shaped democratic polity not just in the UK and the US but globally. This idea is more concerned with national security and gives little regard to the demands of either human security or the required political liberty for its attainment. Gearthy (2010) proposes that liberty and security must be reconciled from the viewpoint of human rights. This should be a broader approach to security and a fresh dedication to criminal law as the best way to balance security with total respect for individual liberty. An effective criminal law system that is perfect and consistent with human rights provisions will aid in designing the laws to address certain serious obstacles to security.

The need to reconcile human rights and security within the context of counterterrorism is further argued for by Wilson (2005). This should go beyond the question of expediency to include the use of a rationalist calculus by counter-terrorism experts to determine the most efficient government policy in fighting terrorism. While it is important and necessary to design effective measures to tackle security threats, it is equally necessary that these measures promote respect for human rights globally. Wilson (2005) also argues that what makes human rights crucial is not because they are absolute but because they signify the type of democratic values required in wartime. A human rights agenda, if sought after, would result in a substantial deviation from the popular 'war on terror' model as it is currently conceived. Thus, for democracies to fight terrorism without losing their moral values, they must repeatedly review the threshold between unrestrained individual rights on the one hand and needless governmental coercion on the other. At a time of apparently unending war, the politics of human rights help create reasonable checks and balances on the conduct of the executive branch and the architecture of its military command (Wilson, 2005).

According to Freeman (2005), regardless of how much novelty is attached to the modern terrorist challenge, a two-dimensional analysis is required to respond to it adequately. The first dimension is provided by the classical political theory of human rights, which attempts to find a just balance between order, rights, and threats. The second dimension is provided by a perception of

worldwide justice. He contends that both the first and second dimensions are required because the perception of human rights assumes a global scope, and the dialectic of terrorism and counterterrorism has a global impact. He observes that, to some degree, this is acknowledged in principle by Western policymakers even though it has yet to affect their practices (Freeman, 2005). He also supports the idea of finding a balance between security and human rights. However, he is also sceptical about the circumstances appropriate to trade human rights for security and the consequences of such decisions, especially States' tendencies to exploit and abuse such situations. More so, he sees human rights as a global issue that requires a global justice system that will serve as an umbrella watchdog for all states (Freeman, 2005).

2.2.1 Critics of balancing

There is yet another school of thought that argues against the balancing of human rights and security. For instance, Bronitt (2008) notes that, for the most part, the post-9/11 debate has centred on either expanding state power to fight terrorism or striking a balance between security and liberty. For instance, this 'balancing approach', in which security is reconciled with the protection of basic human rights, has been very instrumental in counter-terrorism law reform in Australia. However, in his critique of this approach, Bronitt (2008) claims that despite the intuitive appeal of balancing, there is a widespread rejection of its usage as a guide for counter-terrorism law reform. This, according to him, is because balancing advances consequentialism based on the notion that 'the end justifies the means and the idea of 'calculus' through which individual interests are exchanged for community gains. Additionally, he contends that the rationale of such utilitarian approaches is responsible for the proposition by some US and Australian scholars that the regulation of torture through judicial oversight may be justified to prevent an impending terrorist attack. Such precautionary actions are justified in situations of either self-defence or necessity. Contrary to this, he argues that where self-defence is concerned, the defensive action is unlikely to be targeted at the culprits of terrorism but 'easy targets' such as the family members of the suspected terrorist or his associates (Bronitt, 2008).

Similarly, Luban (2005) posits that in times of danger, states are confronted with the difficulty of choosing between national security and civil liberties. States are confronted with dangerous threats posed by merciless international terrorists with proven capability and determination for

mass murder and with the potential of laying hands on weapons of mass destruction. Faced with these threats, undue worry about human rights and civil liberties appears legalistic and, in his view, erroneous. He states that the trade-offs are unavoidable, and the key question is where to draw the line, i.e., how much civil liberties should be traded for security and how many human rights are to be respected? Luban's argument is that the purported trade-off between security and rights is, in fact, a cheap one so long as it is an exchange of one's rights for another's security. The question of trade-off becomes real only when properly framed in the legitimate form, i.e., how many of your rights can you afford to exchange for security? In a nutshell, for Luban (2005), there is no justification for exchanging one individual's right for another under the auspices of security. Although he acknowledges that the trade-off between security and human rights is inevitable, it is, however, unjustifiable unless there is a clear definition of the limits to which these rights can be curtailed and the circumstances in which they are deemed necessary. Rights are themselves forms of security, particularly against abuses of the state's powers (Luban, 2005).

According to Freeman (2005), it is challenging to 'strike a balance' between human rights and security in 'an age of terrorism' given that it requires multifaceted and tentative judgements and information that are difficult to come by. He, however, asserts that a more rational decision can be made by policymakers if all the variables are understood. Given that there is a human right to security, what is being balanced are, in fact, different sets of human rights that are not entirely well-matched. Universal rights to certain freedoms and protections expose us, or others, to danger, which may threaten human rights. Therefore, it is imperative to examine which human rights are at stake under the threat of terrorism and which risks ought to be taken. This requires understanding the risk of the threat of terrorism and factors that make citizens vulnerable to manipulation by governments that control this information (Freeman, 2005).

The idea of balancing security and human rights, argued by Ashworth and Zedner (2007), is not only lacking a clear definition but also militates against any structured considerations of the values of rights. It also subjects itself to the political rhetoric of more security and the infraction of rights. There is a risk that political debates of balancing and proportionality can obscure actual conflicts between the advancement of human rights and the quest for security. They further suggest that rhetorical demands for realignment of the criminal justice system to the advantage of

more security and public protection presupposes not only that such a practice is attainable but also that once balanced, the correlation between rights and security will be a firm one. For them, a more effective measure is to create a clear order of rights and then establish new ways of thinking as well as a dialogue that recognises that some rights are more in tune with the claims of security than others. His approach directly challenges those who question the idea that rights trump security and the view that balancing rights and security is just an issue of rearranging certain political priorities (Ashworth and Zedner, 2007).

Roth (2015) also shares the view that it is not easy to reconcile security interests with respect for fundamental human rights. While the pursuit of a language of reconciliation or recognising security as a right may assist in bringing both sides of the debate closer, the likelihood of addressing the tensions associated with it is proving rather unattainable. Hence, he thus states that the trade-offs between security and human rights are a major and re-emerging problem that will remain a central challenge for the liberal democratic project even in non-conflict times or after threats of impending terrorist attack have receded. However, for progress to be made, new ways are needed to address the conflict between human liberties and security and reduce the negative impacts that an absolutist commitment to either security or liberties may result in (Roth, 2015).

2.3 The communitarian perspective

On the other hand, Turner adopts a communitarian approach to justify the UK's anti-terrorism measure, specifically, the Terrorism Prevention and Investigation Measures (TPIMS) Act 2011. In what he calls communitarianism's critique of liberalism as a natural theoretical basis for the UK's counter-terrorism measures, he pointed out that TPIMs are anti-liberty and, therefore, are not compatible with liberalist ideas about individual and state, such as 'liberty principles' by John Rawl and Lock's ideals of 'natural rights. TPIMs Act 2011 was re-introduced in the Counterterrorism and Security Act 2015 as a result of the growing terror threat by ISIL. It was previously abolished due to human rights concerns on issues of indefinite detention in the control orders Clause of the Act. Nonetheless, the revised TPIMs, which reintroduces the 'relocation' of terrorist suspects and annexation from their families and associates, is a violation of Article 8(1) of the European Convention on Human Rights (ECHR) and increases their marginalisation as

well as their tendencies to reengage in terrorism. Also, the TPIMs are civil orders just like the old control orders and, thus, deny crime suspects the procedural rights given to them as provided in Articles 6(2) and 6(3) of the ECHR. Therefore, it is still open to debate whether the UK's present balance between the rights of terrorism suspects and its competing efforts to sustain security contravenes too much on the fundamental freedoms of individuals serving TPIMs. Thus, according to Turner, the central argument of communitarianism is that there are common formulations of public good against leaving it to be determined by each individual; the state cannot remain neutral on the issue. Hence, Turner asserts that the UK's counter-terrorism measures can be justified based on the provisions of Article 2(1) of the ECHR, which states that it is the state's fundamental duty to protect life (Turner, 2016).

Another proponent of communitarianism was the Israeli-American sociologist Amitai Etzioni. He also posited that communitarianism seeks to rebuild community and that there is a need to strengthen the bonds that bring people together to help them prevail over the isolation and alienation of liberalism. Furthermore, he asserts that all kinds of terrorists, whether those who use Weapons of Mass Destruction (WMDs), suicide bombs, or mere fanatics, cannot be prevented effectively by the common criminal justice system. He further criticises the suggestion by some scholars that terrorism suspects should be treated like other criminals, assumed innocent until proven guilty, given a fair hearing in ordinary courts, afforded several layers of appeals if found guilty, and incarcerated and freed upon completion of their terms. He also contends that such a procedure gives terrorists more rights than they are entitled to and undeservedly puts the security of innocent citizens at significant risk. His justification on why terrorists cannot be treated in like manner as common criminals is that they need to be prevented and not deterred: 'You cannot punish people who commit suicide after the act'. According to Etzioni, though security and liberty are important, neither should be prioritised over the other. Their relative importance changes over time and is dependent on the situation. The safer the nation feels, the more the willingness of judges to give priority to a liberty interest. The greater the threat to national security, the stronger the measures to repress those threats, even at the cost of liberty. According to him, the 'fluid approach' is simply 'common sense' (Turner, 2016).

2.4 The diplomatic approach

Pesto (2010) suggests that a diplomatic approach is the best solution to the fight against terrorism. He asserts that diplomacy is a powerful tool that every country possesses in the fight against conventional forms of terrorism that have spread beyond state borders. As a global problem, terrorism has exposed the whole planet to the dangers posed by the activities of terrorist groups and organisations. A robust and tactically applied diplomacy is the fundamental factor that can fuse all counter-terrorism measures in a dense and related whole. Pesto further opines that political and diplomatic counter-terrorism measures can help in resolving intractable conflicts, and this can be achieved through both public engagement and secret diplomacy. These methods, according to him, deter terrorist organisations from partaking in mass movements that are perceived to be causing both political and social change. Promoting change without using violence entails that accustomed characteristics of traditional movements are reinforced while the effect of terrorist organisations is abridged. Consequently, a momentary or provisional pardon can be granted to members of some terrorist organisations that are considered liberal movements in their home countries, and in addition, further de-legitimization of more violent terrorist groups and the use of diplomatic pressure can be employed on countries and other sympathisers of terrorist organisations. Diplomatic pressures such as withdrawal of diplomatic corps from countries who support terrorists either morally or financially or termination of a diplomatic tie with those countries, according to Pesto, will play a key role in counter-terrorist activities as a whole, be it in agreements, negotiations, or even mediation processes directed at finding peaceful counter-terrorism solutions (Pesto, 2010).

Perl, in his work *Enhancing Diplomatic Effectiveness: A common-sense Risk Management Approach to Counterterrorism* (2009), suggests that there is a need to refocus attention and resources on diplomacy and individual-to-individual diplomatic process instead of the conventional military might. He argues that a broadened diplomatic effort is pivotal for coordinated intelligence and harmonised action against terrorism and its causes. Also, through enhanced multi-personal diplomacy, nations will work as a team with a shared vision in the multi-faceted war on terror. Hence, expanded diplomacy is a common-sense approach to fostering both present and future counter-terrorism campaigns at different levels. This approach

is indeed well thought out and presents a better alternative to the use of military force and other anti-terrorism legislations and laws, which, more often than not, threatens not only the fundamental human rights of individuals but their existence, which it seeks to protect and preserve (Perl, 2009).

From all the arguments and counterarguments above, human rights and security remain the focal point in counterterrorism. Their applicability, however, has remained controversial and contentious since the 9/11 attack. This is because both human rights and security are the pillars upon which all democratic societies are built. While human rights seek to protect freedom, human dignity, and the moral principles that hold democratic and civilised societies together (which differentiates democratic societies from dictatorships) and from violations from excessive use of force by the state apparatus on the one hand, security on the other hand, seeks to safeguard states and individuals from both internal and external threats such as terrorism which seeks to destroy the very life that human rights aim to protect. This debate is one which will continue for a very long time because of its delicate nature and sensitivity to human life. I, however, for the purpose of this study, agree with the liberalist approach to counter-terrorism. This is not only because studies have shown that violations of human rights such as extra-judicial killings of terrorist suspects, indiscriminate attacks on the civilian population, torture, and indefinite detentions of terrorist suspects in counter-terrorism have proven counter-productive not only in the US, the UK, and Nigeria as well but also because many research shows a strong linkage between these violations with radicalisation, public sympathy for terrorist, damaging public trust and confidence in security authorities and bitterness toward governments. This is true, especially in the Boko Haram case in Nigeria, and for this reason, the quest for balancing security and human rights should not only be advocated and debated, but democratic governments, especially Nigeria, must continually develop measures and mechanisms to achieve it. Goldstone (2005) perfectly puts it this way:

“The tragic and previously unimaginable events of 9/11 have changed the United States and indeed the world in ways that are still emerging and difficult to comprehend. Leaders in many countries are struggling to find appropriate policies to deal with the new reality that this level of terrorism presents. This is not a new problem and has been a challenge in many countries for many years. Governments combating terrorism in democracies have an additional burden. They are required to balance efficient law enforcement with respect for the civil liberties of their citizens. There is a consensus that all lawful means

must be used to prevent such terrible crimes. The problem relates to the legitimacy, and sometimes the lawfulness, of those means. In particular, to what extent can civil liberties be curtailed and normal legal processes circumvented? I do not share the pessimism of some human rights activists who suggest that the age of human rights has come and gone. Too much momentum has been gathered during the past sixty years to allow the recognition and implementation of human rights to be derailed. At the same time, there is danger in complacency, and the setbacks to the human rights movement since 9/11 must be acknowledged and recognised as a challenge” (Goldstone, 2005: 157).

Conclusion

This chapter carried out a traditional narrative approach to literature review, which aids in analysing and summarising the body of literature on the topic being studied to identify new research streams and gaps or discover discrepancies. The sources from which the literature was drawn mainly consisted of peer-reviewed academic journals, grey data sources such as media reports, reports from relevant NGOs, e.g., Amnesty International, and textbooks and their suitability for academic research such as this were highlighted. Given that this study seeks to examine human rights violations by states in conflict situations (and in the case of this study, domestic terrorism), the literature review mainly focuses on the moral arguments of states concerning international law, human rights, and national security in the liberal and realist or Constitutionalist theories of IR within the context of counterterrorism discourse especially, within liberal and democratic states. Among the major themes reviewed in the literature are the moral arguments on human rights and security from the Liberalist and Realist perspectives. Here, arguments from prominent authors in the Liberal and Realist school of thought on the intersection between human rights and security in both international and domestic settings were extensively dissected. Lastly, a discussion on the various circumstances within which the trade-offs between human rights and security in armed conflict occur and how this could be reconciled and balanced within the context of international Relations and International law was critiqued accordingly.

CHAPTER THREE (3)

INTERNATIONAL AND DOMESTIC CT-TERRORISM FRAMEWORKS

3.0 Introduction

After a comprehensive review of the theoretical and conceptual discourse on the different perspectives of liberal and realist schools of thought in the security and human rights debate in the preceding chapter, this chapter will examine the international and domestic counterterrorism strategies. Specifically, the focus shall be on the UN Global Counterterrorism Strategies, under which the various mechanisms for strengthening international and regional approaches to counterterrorism will be analysed. Furthermore, an examination of the four broad and comprehensive pillars of the UN counterterrorism strategy for the prevention of all acts that promote, encourage and sponsor all forms of terrorism and violent extremism among member states was presented. Also, the chapter pinpoint some of the UN treaties, conventions, and sister agencies, including the United Nations Office of African Union (UNOAU), that collaborate with member states in the implementation of the UN Security Council's resolutions in combating international and regional terrorism. In addition, the drawbacks of these counterterrorism frameworks in the protection of human rights and freedoms were also identified and analysed. Moreover, the Nigerian counterterrorism strategy, its main objectives and the various Acts for implementing the counterterrorism efforts were elaborately outlined. In conclusion, a moral discourse on torture in the security and human rights contexts within the international law framework and its effectiveness in global counterterrorism efforts were also presented.

3.1 The UN Global Counterterrorism Strategy

The UN universal counterterrorism framework is a distinct global mechanism for enhancing domestic, regional, and international approaches to counterterrorism. The universal strategic and operational measures for countering terrorism were assented to by all UN Member States through a consensus in 2006. The strategy re-emphasises the member states' sole obligation to

implement the UN Global Counterterrorism Strategy and inhibit and curtail terrorism and violent extremist ideologies related to terrorism. A blunt message was sent that all forms of terrorism and its ramifications are not condonable and that member states are committed to taking actionable measures to prevent and fight terrorism both independently and collectively. Those practical measures consist of several broad efforts, including enhancing member states' capability to combat terrorist threats and better coordination of the UN system's counterterrorism structure and operations (UN, 2006).

By embracing the strategy, the commitment of member states during the September 2005 summit was actualised and further strengthened on the different elements advocated by the Secretary-General in May 2006. The counterterrorism strategy is reviewed every two years to keep it up to date and align it with the counterterrorism agendas of Member States. The fifth review of the UN Global Counterterrorism Strategy took place in 2016, which marks the policy's 10th anniversary. The Secretary General's report on the strategy's implementation ten years after it was launched was assessed in the 2016 UN General Assembly when the Secretary General's Action Plan for the prevention of violent extremism (A/70/674-A/70/675) was adopted by a consensus after further consideration by the General Assembly (UN, 2006).

3.1.2 The plan of action

To help implement the global strategy, a plan of action with four specific pillars was developed by the UN General Assembly to combat terrorism threats globally. The action plan is basically the member states' resolution to persistently, unapologetically and firmly condemn all forms of terrorism regardless of who is involved, where it is committed, and for whatever reason, given the grave dangers it poses to internal security and stability. The action plan highlights some specific objectives such as the instant involvement in the established anti-terrorism international agreements and protocols, their implementation and a commitment to the framing of a comprehensive convention on international terrorism; the execution of all resolutions on efforts to eradicate international terrorism, including safeguarding human rights and freedoms while fighting terrorism; the implementation of resolutions associated with international terrorism by the Security Council and full cooperation with the Security Council's relevant counterterrorism bodies in discharging their duties and providing the needed assistance of Member States in

implementing the resolutions; ensure strict compliance with international law obligations, especially human rights, refugee and humanitarian law including the UN charter and other in the global efforts to prevent and fight terrorism (UN, 2006).

3.2 The Four Pillars of the UN Global Counterterrorism Strategy

3.2.1 Measures to address the conditions conducive to the spread of terrorism

This pillar focuses on dealing with favourable factors for promoting terrorism, such as persistent conflicts, the inhumane treatment of victims of terrorism in its entirety, absence of the rule of law and human rights violations, religious and ethnic discrimination, political segregation, socio-economic injustice and intolerance to any justifications for acts of terrorism. In addition, this pillar also aims to continually cement and take full advantage of UN capacities around peacekeeping and peacebuilding, conflict prevention, reconciliation, dialogue and rule of law to help peacefully prevent and resolve enduring conflicts. Using the different programmes and projects of the UN, this pillar also advances the promotion of tolerance and unity among states, cultures and religions and prohibits any acts of religious or cultural slander.

Also, through the instrumentality of the UN Educational, Scientific and Cultural Organisation (UNESCO), inter and intra-faith dialogue among civilisations will be encouraged, and appropriate and necessary measures will be taken to prevent the incitement of terrorism according to members state's obligations under international law. In addition, the pillar re-emphasised a commitment and resolve to ensure prompt and complete actualisation of the UN Millenium Development Goals universal prosperity for all. Other areas this pillar will address include creating practical mechanisms for assisting victims of terrorism and promoting international cooperation to advance civil society participation in the global counterterrorism campaign.

3.2.2 Measures to prevent and combat terrorism

Under this pillar, the member states resolved to distance themselves from organising, promoting, sponsoring, funding or harbouring terrorist activities and to apply the required actionable

measures to guard their individual territories from being used by terrorists to perpetrate violent acts against their citizenry or other countries. Also, full cooperation to combat terrorism in line with international legal frameworks among states will be sought after to deal with, extradite and prosecute anyone that supports, promotes, collaborates, funds, plans, participates, or attempts to partake in perpetrating terrorism or accommodates terrorists.

In addition, adequate judicial support, extradition arrangements, and cooperation between security bodies, including the exchange of timely and credible intelligence to deter and fight terrorism, will be strengthened, intensified, and encouraged by Member States. Furthermore, greater coordination and collaboration among states in fighting crimes, especially international organised crime associated with terrorism such as drug dealing, illegal arms trade, particularly light weapons and drone defence technology, the trading and smuggling of dangerous atomic, biological and radiological materials, are also advanced under this pillar.

Other objectives of this pillar include strengthening counterterrorism systems or centres at regional and sub-regional levels through support from the UN Counterterrorism Committee, the UN Office of Drugs and Crime and the International Criminal Police Organization. Additionally, the implementation of a broad international standard in line with the recommendations of the Financial Action Task Force on Money Laundering and Terrorist Financing and the development of a unified database on biological attacks is encouraged among Member States. Moreover, the pillar also emphasised the coordination of regional and global efforts to combat the utilisation of the internet to promote terrorism in any form online and to create international and regional bilateral efforts and appropriate cooperation to enhance border and customs controls for monitoring and preventing terrorist movement.

3.2.3 Measures to build States' capacity to prevent and combat terrorism and strengthen the role of the United Nations system

The third pillar concerns capacity-building for Member States, which constitutes one of the fundamental elements of the UN global counterterrorism campaign and strengthening coordination within the UN structures to foster international counterterrorism cooperation. Also, capacity-building in the maritime, port, and civil aviation sectors and the optimal use of existing

regional and international organisations' frameworks for stimulating their contributions to international efforts in these areas are also advocated under this pillar. Another objective of this pillar is to create measures to enhance proper and regular information dissemination on the cooperation and technical support among Member States and all relevant international agencies and organisations and to help states implement relevant UN counterterrorism resolutions.

Furthermore, the pillar encourages the UN Counterterrorism Committee and the Executive head to enhance the consistency and effectiveness of technical support on counterterrorism by entrenching its dialogue mechanisms with states and partner organisations and agencies at regional and international levels. Additionally, a close consultation between the UN Counterterrorism Committee and its executive and the UN Office on Drugs and Crime among Member States is advanced to enhance technical support to states to help implement international conventions and procedures linked to the relevant UN Counterterrorism resolutions. An aspect of this third UN Global Counterterrorism Strategy promotes cooperation between the International Monetary Fund, the International Police Organization, and the UN Office on Drugs and Crime with Member States to foster full compliance with international standards to curtail money laundering funding of terrorist acts.

Also, the pillar advocates efforts between the International Atomic Energy Agency and the Organisation for the Prohibition of Chemical Weapons within their separate mandates in assisting states in building their ability to stop terrorists from acquiring nuclear and other deadly material by safeguarding similar facilities and swift response to attacks with those weapons. Another aspect of the pillar concerns providing support for regional and international reforms and transformation in border management mechanisms and institutions of member states and the strengthening of cooperation among the International Maritime Organisation, the World Customs and the International Civil Aviation Organisations working with states to help discover transport security needs and provide support in these areas also forms part of this pillar's objectives.

3.2.4 Measures to ensure respect for human rights for all and the rule of law as the fundamental factor for countering terrorism

Central to this UN Global Counterterrorism pillar is ensuring member states commitment to human rights protection and the rule of law applicable to all global strategy's components and the recognition that safeguarding human rights and counterterrorism efforts are not adversative but in agreement and emphasising the importance of protecting terrorism victims' right. Also, this pillar reiterates commitment to the 2005 UN General Assembly resolution 60/158, which serves as the core framework for human rights protection and fundamental freedom in counterterrorism efforts. Member states are also encouraged to operate within the international law framework, especially human rights, refugee and humanitarian law and to make a concerted effort to advance and sustain an efficient domestic rule of law and criminal justice-based approach to counterterrorism to prosecute terrorist collaborators, sponsors and sympathisers in accordance with human rights laws and civil liberty provisions.

In addition, the Global Counterterrorism Strategy shall, through this pillar, provide the needed support for the development and maintenance of effective criminal justice institutions and encourage member states to seek assistance provided by the United Nations Office on Drugs and Crime. This pillar will also support and contribute to the Human Rights Council's evolving and dynamic program on promoting human rights protection in the global counterterrorism campaign and support the strengthening of the Office of the UN High Commissioner for Human Rights' operational capacity, especially on expanding field operations and activeness. Additionally, the OHCHR, under this pillar, is encouraged to take the lead in examining human rights law issues in the fight against terrorism by proposing state's human rights obligations and assisting them in creating awareness of international human rights law among domestic law enforcement agencies whenever the states so desires. Also, the Special Rapporteur on human rights protection and individual freedoms is mandated to communicate and visit member states and collaborate with the UN and other regional organisations to support states' human rights efforts and provide comprehensive guidance in this area.

3.3 United Nations Office to the African Union (UNOAU) Counterterrorism Framework

The African Union (AU) has since 1999 developed a counterterrorism framework during its Convention on the Prevention and Combatting of Terrorism and the 2004 Protocol, which assigned coordinating and harmonising mandate to the AU PSC on all aspects of continental and international counterterrorism efforts. The AU also created the African Centre for the Study and Research on Terrorism (ACSRT) in Algiers for the centralisation of information and terrorism research and the establishment of capacity-building programs for countering terrorism. The ACSRT will also facilitate the collaboration and cooperation between Member States and continental structures. In addition, a Special Representative for Counterterrorism was appointed in 2010 to solidify AU counterterrorism programs, including the African Model Law on Counterterrorism adopted in 2011 by the AU Assembly for the integration of terrorism legislation among Member States (UNOAU, 2015).

Furthermore, to strengthen the AU regional counterterrorism efforts further, several bodies were created and embraced by the State-level Peace and Security Council (PSC) Heads in 2014 in Nairobi, Kenya, with several objectives outlined for the AU Commission and Member States. The AU Commission was mandated by the PSC to set up a Counterterrorism Fund and organise a yearly AU forum to manage counterterrorism efforts. Also, joint sub-regional specialised counterterrorism units were created by the PSC in accordance with the AU Non-Aggression and Common Defence Pact within the African Standby Force framework as well as the African Capacity for Immediate Response to Crises (ACIRC) before the ASF became active. Other AU-led initiatives, such as the Sahel Fusion Liaison Unit (UFL) and the Committee of Intelligence and Security Services of Africa (CISSA), were supported by the PSC to improve legislation, exchange of intelligence, operational competence and management. Additionally, to improve police cooperation between member states to address transnational crime, the PSC also endorsed the AU Assembly's creation of the African Mechanism for Police Cooperation (AFRIPOL) and encouraged the investigation of terrorist funding and the enhancement of AU sanctions law (UNOAU, 2015).

Generally, UNOAU works with the AU in implementing PSC's decisions to promote coordination with the appropriate UN bodies, including managing counterterrorism funds, developing ideas to curtail the promotion of radicalisation and violent extremism and organising public sessions on counterterrorism annually to facilitate efforts. UNOAU also works with the sanction committee of the UN Security Council to assist the AU PSC in implementing its sub-committee on terrorism and sanctions and assists the AU in advancing its sub-regional arrangements of the Nouakchott and Djibouti processes (UNOAU, 2015).

3.4 Human rights challenges

The UN Global Counterterrorism Strategy is a program created to be the front-runner in influencing member states' approaches and measures to counterterrorism and has since markedly developed in the 9/11 aftermath. Despite its noble intentions, however, striking evidence shows a widespread derogation of human rights protection, women's and children's rights, and intimidation of human rights activists and civil society organisations by many member states in their counterterrorism operations. Worse still, a significant number of member states even changed or excluded parts of the original draft, which would have ensured better human rights protection and recognition of civil society organisations in the global counterterrorism campaign.

As a result, the proposed creation of an autonomous oversight mechanism for monitoring and assessing the UN counterterrorism strategy's impact on human rights, rule of law and governance have been greatly undermined. The amended draft is now challenging, and it is unclear whether there is even a need for an extensive internal evaluation mechanism proposed in the initial draft (HRW, 2021). Although the 7th review of the UN Global Counterterrorism Strategy UN General Assembly adopted in 2021 advances a new comprehensive, autonomous and neutral monitoring mechanism for the UN counterterrorism's impact on human rights, rule of law, humanitarian intervention and civic space, several human rights and gender equality reinforcing language were rejected by member states (HRW, 2021).

Furthermore, the ninth and the most recent review of the Global Counterterrorism Strategy in 2023 only highlights the role of the UN human rights mechanism and human rights treaty bodies like the UNOHCHR and the independent procedures of Human Rights Council in maintaining,

examining, and advising member states on human rights in combating terrorism. Though the General Assembly shows displeasure at the high level of derogation from international law and international human rights, refugee and humanitarian law in countering terrorism, there was still no mention of any concrete action plan to mitigate these violations or enforceable law to punish member states that violate them. Therefore, the absence of a strong policy or mechanism in the UN Global Counterterrorism Strategy for punishing or holding member states accountable for human rights violations, the UN's commitment to human rights and individual freedoms, especially for vulnerable groups in armed conflict and the fight against terrorism, remains highly questionable. As such, decisive measures to ensure member states' compliance with human rights protection in the global effort against terrorism are urgently needed.

Terrorism has spread significantly in Africa since the early 2000s. According to the Global Terrorism Index report, in 2022, almost half of the total terrorism-related deaths recorded globally were in Africa. Faced with this threat, counterterrorism efforts in the region remained solely military-driven, which has, in most cases, proven ineffective and counter-productive. This, on the one hand, is largely due to the incompatibility of the Western approaches to counterterrorism adopted by states faced with terrorism threats in the region and, on the other hand, the egregious consequences for human rights and individual freedom often linked to radicalisation and the bridge of public trust. Hence, the decolonisation of this Western-dominated counter-terrorism approach is advanced and extensively discussed at the end of this study (Global Terrorism Index, 2022).

Conversely, while there is a strong UN presence in Africa, as evidenced in its several extensive humanitarian programmes and interventions through its various bodies and agencies in some of the worst conflict-stricken countries, there is little or no commitment in most of these interventions to pressure or influence state's counterterrorism measures to ensure compliance with international human rights and humanitarian law in Africa. Despite acknowledging the high rate of violations of international and human rights law among member states and signatories to the UN Global Counterterrorism Strategy, checks or measures to decisively deal with violating states in the future are still lacking, with no sign in sight to create such measures, which is also true in the case of the UNOAU Counterterrorism framework.

3.5 Nigeria Counterterrorism Strategy in Context

The response of the Nigerian government to terrorism has been characterised by ad-hoc approaches in resolving issues that a particular terrorist act generates at a given point in time. This was captured by Umar (2013) when he opined that the Nigerian government's response to terrorism had been characterised by reactions to the symptoms of terrorism alone. The Nigerian government's initial methods of reaction to terrorism had its backing in Section 11 of the 1999 Constitution (Amy, 2014). This section of the Constitution states that the National Assembly shall make laws for public safety and public order for the federation (FGN, 1999). Hence, most steps taken against terrorism drew inspiration from the Constitution. Therefore, no law addressed terrorism directly.

The need to address terrorism from its root causes and develop the capability to react to its symptoms necessitated the making of laws and a strategy for counterterrorism. The recent and relevant laws are the Terrorism (Prevention) Act 2011 (TPA 2011), Money Laundering (Prohibition) Act 2011 (MLPA 2011), Money Laundering (Prohibition) (Amendment) Act 2012 (MLPA 2012) and Terrorism (Prevention) (Amendment) Act 2013, (TPA 2013), while the strategy is the NACTEST (Dasuki, 2013). This chapter will particularly explore the NACTEST to assess Nigeria's counter-terrorism policies. However, reference will continuously be made to TPA 2011, MLPA 2011, MLPA 2012 and TPA 2013 because none of these documents can be evaluated in isolation. Put differently, the NACTEST forms the core of the assessment, but legislation that relates to NACTEST will also be assessed. This is in a bid to offer a robust and comprehensive assessment of the response.

3.5.2 The establishment of NACTEST and other associated Acts

The Nigerian government promulgated the TPA 2011, TPA 2013, MLPA 2011 and MLPA 2012. These Acts were intended to provide a legal framework for the government's counter-terrorism measures. TPA 2011 was revised in 2012, leading to the enactment of TPA 2013 in February 2013 (United States Department of State, 2015a). The TPA 2011 and the TPA 2013 stipulate how terror suspects can be arrested and prosecuted, disrupting terrorism financing and taking

measures to check international terrorists' influence on terrorism in Nigeria (FGN, 2011a; FGN, 2013). That is, the Acts cover terrorist funding, terrorists' properties, prosecution and international cooperation in extraditing suspected terrorists (Umar, 2013). The Money Laundering Acts of 2011 and 2012 are designed to tackle terrorism financing, either from local or international sources, as well as stipulating how offenders are arrested and prosecuted through the regulatory institutions and the judiciary (FGN, 2011b; FGN, 2012). These laws are interpreted through the Federal High courts and implemented by agencies of government like the Office of the National Security Adviser (ONSA), Central Bank of Nigeria (CBN), EFCC, Nigerian Customs Service (NCS), Nigerian Fraud Intelligence Unit (NFIU), Prisons Service, and the Inspector General of Police, amongst others (FGN, 2011a; FGN, 2011b; FGN, 2012; FGN, 2013).

The TPA 2013 gave the ONSA authority to coordinate the security and enforcement agencies for the purpose of implementation (FGN, 2013). Although the Acts exist alongside the NACTEST, the purpose of making NACTEST the core document for assessment in this study is because the NACTEST operationalises what all the Acts seek to achieve. It also contains the roles of more agencies and bodies (beyond those stipulated by TPA 2013) responsible for its implementation in a single document, and their activities are coordinated by a single body (NACTEST, 2014). These include the Federal Ministry of Environment, the Federal Airports Authority of Nigeria, Civil Society Organisations (CSOs), and the National Intelligence Agency (NIA), amongst others (NACTEST, 2014). The ONSA coordinates the enforcement of all counter-terrorism activities (Amy, 2014: 26). The office of the Attorney General of the Federation ensures that all counter-terrorism implementation aligns with international best practices (Amy, 2014).

NACTEST is Nigeria's counter-terrorism strategy. It adopts a broader approach that addresses both the root causes and the most effective response to terrorist attacks (Barkindo and Byranns, 2016). In other words, 'NACTEST takes a comprehensive and holistic approach to counterterrorism' (Dasuki 2013: 9). Thus, NACTEST is a merger of hard and soft approaches. It is designed to identify the root causes of terrorism and proffer necessary measures to tackle such to de-radicalise extremists and prevent radicalisation (Ackerman, 2014). As a presidential directive signed on 30th April 2014 (Barkindo and Byranns, 2016), NACTEST is a framework that guides all the counter-terrorism measures of the Nigerian government, and it brings about

the synergy of all the agencies responsible for counterterrorism (Dasuki, 2013). The Counter-Terrorism Centre domiciled in ONSA, is charged with the implementation of the NACTEST (NACTEST, 2014).

3.5.3 Objectives of NACTEST

The NACTEST framework is pentagonal, consisting of five objectives, which are forestall, secure, identify, prepare, and implement (NACTEST, 2014). In order to have a comprehensive assessment of Nigeria's counter-terrorism policies, it is expedient to have some detailed insight into the objectives.

3.5.4 Forestall

The core of the forestall part of NACTEST is 'preventing terrorism in Nigeria by engaging the public through sustained enlightenment/sensitisation campaigns and deradicalisation programmes' (NACTEST, 2014: 16). This will be achieved through the promotion of good governance, prison deradicalisation, enhancing Small and Medium Scale Enterprises (SMEs) for job creation, media campaigns and utilising the education sector, monitoring activities of religious organisations and capacity building in all areas of the criminal justice system to deter terrorism (NACTEST, 2014).

3.5.5 Secure

The secure aspect has as its focal point 'ensuring the protection of life and property, public and key national infrastructure/services including Nigerian interests around the world' (NACTEST, 2014: 16). This aspect of the NACTEST is achieved through strengthening border security, protecting critical national infrastructure and training security forces to respond to threats of terrorism (NACTEST, 2014). The secure agenda is to equip security agencies to have the capacity to guard against terrorist menace.

One of the major factors accounting for Boko Haram's success is the unfettered movement of arms and people across the country's porous borders (Uduonwa, 2013). Individuals, businessmen, terrorist organisations and corrupt government officials have taken or taken advantage of the porous borders, corruption, weak institutions, weak laws and poverty to launder money from crime proceeds and to perpetrate crimes (United States Department of State, 2015b). Boko Haram has been alleged to use animals and women and disguise them as women to traffic small and light weapons for cross-border armed transportation (Onouha, 2013). Fulani herdsmen are nomads who move within the West African sub-region with their cattle and have been alleged to transport small arms and launder money through their livestock (Omitola, 2014). Security agents hardly subject them to search because they feel they are just animal herders, and the routes they take are so remote that they can hardly encounter security agents most of the time. However, the length of the borders, coupled with inadequate border patrol capacity, made border closures difficult to implement (Solomon, 2012).

3.5.6 Identify

The purpose of this objective of NACTEST is 'ensuring that all terrorist acts are properly investigated, and terrorists and their sponsors are brought to justice' (NACTEST, 2014: 16). Identification is achieved through proper investigation and prosecution, cooperation on intelligence gathering amongst security agencies, Subscriber Identification Module (SIM) card registration, monitoring of cyberspace and controlling terrorism financing (NACTEST, 2014). A look at the channels through which the identified objective will be achieved is expedient.

Section 2 Subsection 5a of the TPA 2013 grants security agencies the power to investigate to ascertain if anyone has been involved in terrorist activities (FGN, 2013). Suspects arrested and detained by the military had no access to their families or lawyers and were not even brought to court. These arrests were made without being preceded by a thorough investigation, and some of those arrested were killed in an extra-judicial manner (Amnesty International, 2016). The effective positioning of the criminal justice system was a key area in identifying. The criminal justice system was the structure on the ground that balanced the investigation and prosecution of criminal matters. An effective criminal justice system entails ensuring criminal justice practitioners exercise their authority in a fair and just way by being inclined to justice, law and

order in dealing with the citizenry (Otu and Aro, 2013). In May 2015, the administration of the Criminal Justice Act was passed into law. This Act regulated the activities of the judiciary in the administration of criminal justice (United States Department of State, 2016a). Its major provisions are that victims of crime be compensated, sentences are served outside prisons, and proceedings are recorded electronically (Amnesty International, 2015). The Act makes provisions for sentences to be served outside the prisons, and this allows parole, suspended sentences and community services (United States 114 Department of State for 2016b). In essence, the Act prohibits the maltreatment of detainees (United States Department of State 2016b).

The Anti-Torture Bill was also passed in 2015 but has not been signed into law (Amnesty International, 2016). It was passed to strengthen the criminal justice system and, explain what torture was, and prohibit it in any form (United States Department of State, 2016b). The state of prison facilities in Nigeria does not engender a vibrant criminal justice system. This assertion was well captured by Amnesty International (2016: 275), 'however, prisons remained overcrowded and court processes slow; frequent strikes by court employees, such as court clerks, overpay and the consequent closure of courts, lead to delays in trials and the supervision of pre-trial detention.'

3.5.7 Prepare

The thrust of the objective tagged 'prepare focussed on 'preparing the populace so that the consequences of terrorist incidents could be mitigated' (NACTEST, 2014: 16). The objective is envisaged to be achieved through the agencies' prowess in responding to direct damages caused through terrorist acts, identifying potential risks that Nigeria could face as a result of terrorism and assessing the effects thereof (NACTEST, 2014). A look at the steps the government has taken to achieve the prepared objectives will be relevant.

NACTEST outlines the need to locate a call centre that will operate for 24 hours daily to take anonymous calls on terrorism matters to be located within the ONSA (NACTEST, 2014). NEMA will ensure the establishment of Disaster Response Units in government establishments and ensure coordinated training and multi-agency cooperation among stakeholders (NACTEST,

118 2014). Consequently, NEMA has toll-free emergency hotlines. NEMA was the coordinating agency that cared for victims of terrorism (Amy, 2014). The emergency numbers on the website of the Nigerian Police Force have two phone numbers (each has 11 digits) through which 56 officers can be contacted. The flaw with these emergency numbers for the Police and NEMA is that they contain too many digits to remember in the case of an emergency.

Setting up IDP camps was a response to the effects of terrorism. NEMA was saddled with the responsibility of setting up and taking care of these camps (Campbell, 2014). As of April 2016, there were a total of 2,155,618 displaced persons in Nigeria, out of which 1.8 million were due to terrorism, and as of May 2016, a total of 186,473 Nigerian refugees were in neighbouring countries of Chad, Cameroon and Niger (UNHCR, 2016). The states affected are the six North Eastern states, while the IDP camps are in Adamawa, Borno and Gombe (Sidi, 2015). In partnership with relevant Non-Governmental Organisations (NGOs), NEMA provides humanitarian relief through food, medical services, sanitary supplies and educational services (Amy, 2014).

3.5.8 Implement

The core of the implement objective of NACTEST was 'devising a framework to effectively mobilise and sustain a coordinated cross-governmental population-centred effort' (NACTEST, 2014: 16). The office of the National Coordinator on Counterterrorism has been created to coordinate all agencies and participate in international cooperation in implementing NACTEST (NACTEST, 2014). The roles of agencies in the NACTEST, TPA 2011, TPA 2013, MLPA 2011 and MLPA 2013 include curbing terrorism financing, creating awareness, investigating, arresting, prosecuting, and conducting military operations. The CBN, EFCC, NFIU, and National Insurance Commission, are agencies which spearhead and liaise with other local and international agencies in checking terrorism financing and drug trafficking (FGN, 2011b; FGN, 2012). The Federal Radio Corporation of Nigeria, the National Orientation Agency and the National Broadcasting Commission, in conjunction with CSOs and other relevant agencies, all promote awareness of terrorism-related activities (NACTEST, 2014).

The defence headquarters coordinates the activities of other security agencies in the combat against terrorists (NACTEST, 2014). The DSS and NIA are in charge of intelligence for the government's security apparatus on the local and international scenes, respectively (Umar, 2013). The cooperation of the ONSA, NIA, DSS, Defence Intelligence Agency (DIA), police, military, other law enforcement agencies and stakeholders would foster intelligence gathering and investigation by identifying groups that promote terrorism (NACTEST, 2014). However, inter-agency distrust has made intelligence sharing among the security agencies charged with combating Boko Haram very low (Amy, 2014). Domestic information exchange has also taken place between NFIU and EFCC, DSS, NPF, NCS, NIA, NSCDC and 121 other agencies (NFIU, 2014). This cooperation was to check money laundering. The TPA 2011 and TPA 2013 stipulated cooperation with countries on the extradition of terrorists across countries (FGN, 2011b; FGN, 2013).

The NACTEST also emphasised cooperating with other countries and multilateral organisations (NACTEST, 2014). It is envisaged that the Ministry of Foreign Affairs would spearhead working relations with NIA and DIA for the implementation of NACTEST on foreign matters (NACTEST, 2014). A major suspect in the Nyanya Abuja bombing of April 2014, Sadiq Ogwuche, who fled to Sudan, was extradited to Nigeria by the Sudanese authorities (Sudan Tribune, 2014). This was evidence of international cooperation. The Nigerian government has solicited assistance from countries with technical prowess, experience, resources and personnel to combat terrorism (Uduonwa, 2013). Foreign governments and international organisations have also partnered with Nigeria in implementing NACTEST in the areas of training, financial aid and military involvement.

3.6 Torture and Counterterrorism

3.6.1 Introduction

Torture is a translation of the Latin word “tortura”, and it entails twisting or distortion. The word was a household phrase and was widely understood as a punishment given by ecclesiastical authority in medieval Latin. It was also popular in ancient Assyria and Achaemenid Persia and was legally and morally accepted not only in ancient societies but also in medieval and early

modern civilisations (Einolf, 2007; Jacob, 2017). Thus, torture is nothing new but a phenomenon that existed and evolved over time. It was used by states as an interrogation technique and came to be viewed as an effective means of information gathering and punishment for crime. However, not until after the horrors of WWII, torture enjoyed little to no restrictions in the international legal framework. While the despicable war crimes of WWII and other subsequent conflicts prompted several conventions that assigned an absolute ban and peremptory norm (*jus cogens*) status on torture for both signatory and non-signatory states to the International Human Rights Law, torture was widely associated with only dictatorship and non-democratic states until the 9/11 attack. However, much research suggests that since the 9/11 attacks, most democratic states like the US have created some exceptions for torture in the fight against terrorism, which ushered in an era of gross use of torture.

Therefore, given the absolute prohibition on torture and its prevalence in the GWOT campaign and most contemporary armed conflicts across the globe and some democratic states, particularly in the Boko Haram context, this section will examine and analyse the concept of torture in the security and human rights discourse in armed conflict. Specifically, a discussion on the moral justifications and counter-justifications for torture and why states often resort to this method of counterterrorism from both realist and liberalist standpoints.

3.6.2 The moral justifications and counter-justifications for the use of torture

The War on Terror campaign that followed 9/11 has reintroduced fresh philosophical and political debate in the US and the rest of the world regarding the justification for the use of torture. This debate is mainly restricted to the question of whether or not torture should be completely banned or if certain special circumstances may justify its use, for instance, to prevent a greater danger from befalling society (Evans, 2007).

Moral absolutism, an ideology strongly held by liberalists and, as extensively discussed in the previous section, suggests that torture is a condemnable practice and adversative to the principles of human rights and, as such, should be prohibited in totality. This absolutist position is also supported by Nye (2005), who states that individuals must ‘do things only when they are right’ rather than measuring the consequences of their actions (Nye, 2005).

The absolute and utter condemnation against torture is highlighted in all the international conventions: Article 5 of the 1948 Universal Declaration on Human Rights (UDHR) and Article 50 of the 1949 Fourth Geneva Convention. Others are Articles 4 and 7 of the 1966 International Covenant on Civil and Political Rights and Article 2 of the 1984 Convention against Torture and Other Cruel, Inhuman, or Degrading Treatment or Punishment. They all prohibit in strict and clear terms the use of torture or cruel, inhuman, and degrading punishment on any human being, whether civilians, enemy combatants, or terrorists, under any circumstances, either during war or with the threat of war and political instability (Evans, 2007).

However, despite these provisions, torture has been found to be prevalent. According to a study conducted by Hathaway (2004), countries that have internationally endorsed treaties prohibiting torture violate more than countries that did not ratify them. Forsythe (2006) also contends that though dictatorial and authoritarian governments appear to use torture more frequently, democratic governments, despite their commitments to the promotion of human rights, also condone torture, especially in situations where their security is threatened (Forsythe, 2006).

Thus, whereas there are scholars and security experts who hold on to the idea that in times of grave security threat, torture or inhumane treatment is necessary for the protection of lives, others call for its absolute ban, maintaining that there is no justification whatsoever for its use. Others, such as Žižek (2002), even disapprove of the discussion of torture as a legitimate topic. He states that ‘essays which do not advocate torture outright but simply introduce it as a legitimate topic of debate, are even more dangerous than an explicit endorsement of torture. ‘The mere introduction of torture as a legitimate topic allows us to entertain the idea while retaining a pure conscience’ (Žižek, 2002: 103-04). Therefore, the next section will make a critique of the moral justifications for and against torture in the current discourse on counterterrorism. This will help give a deeper understanding of the moral complexities associated with the ‘war on terror’ and its intersection with human rights provisions as stipulated in the international human rights regime.

3.6.3 Torture, the lesser evil’: a pre-requisite for defeating terror?

Since the 9/11 attack, the use of advanced and cruel torture techniques on terrorist suspects has dramatically increased and has been condoned (though not officially but rather, in practice) by the US and UK governments, respectively and for this reason, they have attracted widespread criticism globally. Though other countries also condone the use of torture, however, the US stands out among them. This is evident in institutions such as the Guantanamo Bay and Abu Ghraib prisons run by the US government, which have since become international symbols of the world’s most dangerous facilities for torture and other inhumane interrogations for criminals, especially terrorists. The main idea behind torture is the extraction of vital information from suspects for national security concerns. The question now arises: is torture ever justified in the war on terror or other crimes against humanity? There are contrasting views among scholars, security experts, and academics on this issue. Scholars such as (Dershowitz, 2002; Bagaric and Clarke, 2005; Parry, 2004; Ignatieff, 2004; and Levinson, 2004) have a shared view that the use of torture to prevent an imminent attack of potential mass casualty is permissible, whereas scholars like (Wisnewski, 2008; Parker, 2012; Brecher 2007; Langbein, 2004; and Posner, 2004) share contrasting opinions. In his renowned work ‘Why terrorism works’ Dershowitz asked these questions to establish his argument on torture:

‘If the use of torture is imminent, is it worse to close our eyes and tolerate it by low-level law enforcement officials without accountability, or instead bring it to the surface by requiring a warrant for it as a precondition to its infliction? The question is not whether some torture would or would not be used in the ticking bomb case—it surely would. The dilemma is whether it would be done openly, pursuant to a previously established legal procedure, or whether it would be done secretly, in violation of existing law. This is the important policy issue about which I have tried to begin a debate: how should a democracy make difficult choice-of-evil decisions in situations for which there is no good resolution?’ (Dershowitz, 2002).

To Dershowitz (2002), the use of torture in a ticking bomb scenario is necessary, especially when it is the only alternative to stop the bomb from killing a large civilian population. He further notes that torture is morally unacceptable if it lacks legal backing, but it is also inevitable. The unavailability of torture presents the need for some form of judicial oversight of the

practice, such as “torture warrants” for public accountability, which could minimise its use. From this point of view, it is logical to have a formalised, transparent and accountable system that is easier to manage than an illegal, underground, and ad hoc system of torture. Albeit not totally convinced that the use of judicial warrant as a precondition to non-lethal torture would reduce the level of physical cruelty applied to suspects of terrorism, Dershowitz (2002) believes that a double check, i.e. torture warrants are usually more protective than without them (Dershowitz, 2002).

Bagaric and Clarke (2005) also share a similar view in that they affirm that torture is very instrumental when it comes to extracting information. Once some criteria (such as proof that a terrorist suspect is withholding vital information that will help prevent an impending attack or torture appears to be the only alternative option to save mass civilian lives) are met, all kinds of torture may be employed even if this will lead to the death of the suspect they posit. In their opinion, torture is simply an act in which the rights of one individual are sacrificed for the greater good. Therefore, although torture varies in degree, they are actually the same as other conducts like sleep deprivation, disinformation that causes stress, and coercion, which are authorised in other situations (Clarke, 2005).

In addition, Shue (2004: 55) suggests that ‘to allow the destruction of much of a great city and many of its people would be almost as wicked as purposely destroying it’. However, he also posits that torture is the ultimate shortcut, and should it ever be legalised under any conditions, its abuse would highly increase. Similarly, Elshtain (2004) states that even though ‘the ban on torture must remain, ‘moderate physical pressure’ to save innocent lives might be needed. Thus, he argues for ‘coercion’ as against ‘torture’, which is not only demanded in certain extreme circumstances but is arguably the ‘least bad’ thing to do (Elshtain, 2004: 86). He further points out that ‘far greater moral guilt falls on a person in authority who permits the deaths of hundreds of innocents rather than choosing to ‘torture’ one guilty or complicit person’ (Elshtain, 2004: 87).

Ignatieff (2004), a renowned liberal scholar, argues that when democratic governments fight terrorism, they do so in the defence of their political life from violence. Thus, violence is a prerequisite for defeating terror, which may also require confidentiality, deception, force, and infringement of rights. It is, therefore, impossible for states to escape truncating the very values

they seek to preserve using these means. In situations where the only effective means to stopping terror or imminent danger requires the sacrifice of some civil liberty, states may overlook human rights in the interest of security. He describes this position as choosing the “lesser evil”. However, he cautions states not to take advantage of this narrative to deliberately violate civil liberty but to do so only when necessary and as a final resort. Necessity may require us to take action to defend democracy, which will contradict democracy’s fundamental obligations to dignity. While we are faced with this inevitability, the best means to lessen harm is to differentiate clearly in our minds between what necessity can justify and what the morality of dignity can justify. He cautions against getting carried away by justifications such as imminent danger, necessity and risk. (Ignatieff, 2004). Due to the moral complications of these measures, their application must be targeted to the barest minimum number of people and only when there exists no other alternative and should be kept under the careful examination of a free democratic system. Though Ignatieff does not support the legalisation of torture as Dershowitz proposes, he suggests other forms of interrogation, such as sleep deprivation that do not cause mental or physical harm and disinformation that causes stress (Ignatieff, 2004).

Additionally, Pham (2004) agrees with Ignatieff’s “lesser evil” proposition. He suggests that if the destiny of free societies is to be constantly tried in the forge of insistent, asymmetrical, non-reciprocal warfare, then Ignatieff’s suggestions are indeed sensible, even though his specific policy recommendations are challengeable. He states that a “lesser evil” approach to ethics allows the needed flexibility that the situations of the war on terror require, including, probably, among other tough options, lengthy preventive detention, brutal interrogation, defensive strikes, and targeted killings. Thorough scrutiny of the antagonistic procedure in democratic polities can prevent flexibility from becoming a norm. However, Pham (2004) adds that for this to effectively chart the realistic course between an absolutist human rights/civil liberties viewpoint that insists that violations of rights can never be justified and a similarly purist consequentialist position that assesses actions mainly on their usefulness, this process must be determined by honesty rather than deception, sincerity and not denial. Thus, in democratic societies, it is often desirable to decide controversial issues through open debate and due consideration instead of making them hurriedly, emotionally, and while under pressure. This is particularly true where the choice to be made is strategic, requiring a balance of liberty and security (Pham, 2004).

Furthermore, in a ticking bomb case, where there is an existential danger of imminent terrorist attack, Gur-Ayre (2004) contends that the use of interrogational force can be justified on the basis of self-defence, particularly where it is impossible to get information through other means. To him, the criminal law concept of self-defence can go beyond just validating to also limiting the practice of interrogation (Gur-Ayre, 2004).

Parry (2004) also contends that the evil of torture cannot be completely ruled out as a method of combating terrorism, irrespective of the provisions of international law. If torture happens to be the only hope for saving innocent lives in the face of imminent danger, the “necessity defence” should serve as justification for the interrogators’ conduct. Though he supports the use of torture, Parry also suggests that even if it is justified in certain cases, for instance, from the perspective of criminal law, it is also important to ask if it is wise to permit it (Parry, 2004).

3.6.4 Torture, a necessary evil?

Wisnewski (2008), in his work *Unwarranted Torture Warrants: A Critique of Dershowitz’s Proposal*, argues that establishing a process of judicial review as proposed by Dershowitz would make some cases of torture legal. For instance, those conducted after a warrant for said torture was acquired. The problem here is that even though torture is illegal, it is still being practised, indicating a lack of willingness to respect the law and contempt for the gravity of torture. In addition, he asserts that legalising some instances of torture will not make people obey the law concerning torture any more than an absolute legalisation of all torture would. Hence, it is alien to suggest that judiciary review would reduce the occurrence rate of torture; neither would it suddenly make those who do not presently uphold the rule of law start respecting it. Therefore, a torture warrant will make little difference. Rather, it may even result in its occurrence with more impunity (Wisnewski, 2008).

Dershowitz (2002) also claims that European courts issued torture warrants to force information out of suspects in the sixteenth century, which proved effective. This, he claims, is similar to his proposed torture warrants, which will not only help reduce the frequency of torture occurrences but can also serve as a means of saving lives. Wisnewski (2008) disagrees with this assertion, arguing that judges could not issue torture warrants because it was never a standard judicial

procedure in Europe. The only body to have issued torture warrants was the Privy Council, and it was only for a short period. This argument is also countered by Langbein (2004), who contends that England never had a system of judicial torture because the power to investigate under torture was never vested with ordinary law enforcement officials or courts. As such, there is hardly any evidence of such practice in the Anglo-American criminal procedure (Langbein, 2004; Wisniewski, 2008).

Levinson (2004) criticises Dershowitz's proposal and calls it the ultimate evil that transcends the pale for any state that considers itself civilised. He also criticises the moral perfectionism of liberalists who generally hold the notion that justice must prevail even if the heavens will fall (Levinson, 2004). Earlier, Thomson (1986) stated that if someone threatens to kill you with the exception that you torture someone else to death, you do not have the right, even to save yourself, to do so. The right to life is made up of not just the right not to be killed but also the right not to be unjustly killed (Thomson, 1986)

In his argument for limited and controlled use of torture, Brecher (2007) describes Dershowitz's proposal as more sophisticated than those who support the use of interrogational torture. Nonetheless, it is also the most influential and, therefore, most dangerous. He states that the idea of legalising torture is a thought too far, and the 'ticking time bomb' situation described by Dershowitz is merely an illusion. He also contends that heightened security and evacuation of threatened premises are better alternatives to dealing with such a situation (Brecher, 2007).

Likewise, McCain (2005) notes that while the 'necessity defence' for the use of torture, as illustrated in the 'ticking-time-bomb' scenario, provides justifications for the application of cruel, inhumane, and degrading methods to get intelligence that could prevent a terrorist attack, this does not serve as the basis to legalise its use. He stresses that providing a legal exception to this basic principle of human rights may pave the way for abuse even in non-extreme circumstances (McCain, 2005). This position is also shared by Langbein (2004), who warns that based on lessons from history when torture becomes legal, it might be exploited continuously by vested interests (Langbein, 2004).

The inevitability of the use of torture, as argued by Dershowitz (2002), is also countered by Schauer (2004), who argues that "resisting the inevitable is not to be desired because it will

prevent the inevitable but because it may be the best strategy for preventing what is less inevitable but more dangerous. What is ‘less inevitable but more dangerous is’, for example, the expanded use of interrogational torture to less-than-catastrophic cases” (Schauer, 2004: 229-235). Once state agents are authorised to use interrogational torture in one set of cases, it is difficult to preclude use beyond the limited subset of cases. Rather, such powers and authority are likely to expand far beyond their original intended use. He concludes that the more rooted the prohibition of torture as a norm is, the harder it is for the government to convince the public of the necessity of violating such a norm (Schauer, 2004).

Posner (2004) maintains that Dershowitz’s proposal of a ‘torture warrant’ as a check on the executive’s discretion is an exaggeration for the following reasons: firstly, there will be no effective screening because a warrant is issued in *ex parte* proceedings, which gives the applicant privilege to choose which judge to apply to. Secondly, the hearing may be biased because the judicial officers are likely to be chosen because they are sensitive to issues of national security. Thirdly, the whole process may be kept confidential due to security concerns, and as such, it does not promote honesty, administrative values, or transparency. Thus, Posner concludes that a warrant might “operate merely to whitewash questionable practices” (Posner, 2004: 296).

In a similar view, Brown (2007) argues that if a judge gives *ex-ante* approval to torture in a system where torture is allowed and the act is consequently carried out by the officials, all the parties involved are accomplices in violating one of the fundamental moral standards of international law. Though the idea of a torture warrant proposed by Dershowitz is presented as a solution, Brown (2007) argues that it creates even more problems than it solves.

“Torture mocks the law, using punishment to gather evidence to justify the punishment already inflicted, rather than using evidence already gathered to justify punishment. When torture becomes an official policy, the victims’ suffering and pain lose legal relevance, and they become further isolated just when they most need the law’s protections” (Brown, 2007: 2).

Legalising torture, even in extreme conditions, creates insuperable difficulties for the international system. For instance, ‘Is torture by a dictator also legitimate because it has been warranted by the government?’ (Brown, 2007:16). Furthermore, Hajjar (2019) argues that the right prohibiting torture is ‘exceptional’ from other rights human beings can claim due to the

lucidness of the situation in which it occurs and its universal nature. Its provisions not only outline clear restrictions on what states can do to people but also outline sanctions in cases of violation. In addition, advocacy for torture is the epitome of the frailty of reaction, and what is required is an aggressive attack on pro-torture postulations, thereby safeguarding human rights and humanitarian principles globally (Hajjar, 2019).

3.6.5 Torture, an incentive to speak, but not necessarily the truth

In response to Bagaric and Clarke (2005), Rumney (2006) argues that there is a problem regarding the effectiveness of the proposed coercive methods of torture. Any form of coercive interrogation that results in death, according to him, has obviously failed. There is evidence indicating that the use of coercive interrogation to extract information has largely been unproductive in the past. Rumney (2006) further argues that torture, even the ‘ticking bomb’ terrorist context for which the entire debate is situated, may prove less effective. In addition, if torture is often not effective, then its use based on other propositions is pointless. According to him, only a sadist would approve the legalisation of torture without considering if the outcome would be useful. Consequently, the question of efficacy is crucial to the entire discourse regarding the legalisation of torture and must be engaged with by both those who propose and oppose the idea. Therefore, even if torture works in getting reliable information, it is just one amongst several other ethical concerns that need to be properly scrutinised, particularly the possibility of using legal means to control it (Rumney, 2006).

Similarly, on the issue of effectiveness, Levinson (2004) also observes that there is no existing proof to indicate that torture is a reliable way of extracting information. Whereas the effectiveness of coercive interrogation is indeed surrounded by uncertainties, its reliability cannot be ascertained. What is required instead is the discourse on evidence in order to understand its efficacy (Levinson, 2004).

In addition, Langbein (2004) also observes that because torture tests endurance rather than veracity, innocent persons might yield to the pain and torment and confess things that they never did. Thus, ‘the agony of torture created an incentive to speak, but not necessarily to speak the truth’ (Langbein, 2004: 93-103). He adds that in the practice of coercive forms of torture, no

precautionary mechanism exists that could protect the innocent and guarantee the truth. These methods of coercive interrogation have largely proven to be unreliable ways of securing confession (Langbein, 2004).

In addition, Parker (2012) posits that whereas exponents of torture claim that it produces results that cannot be obtained using lawful means, the counterfactual is, of course, impossible to prove one way or another. While it is undeniable that some people are compelled to make confessions under duress, the historical record clearly indicates that, more often than not, many do not (Parker, 2012).

According to Bowden (2003), while on the one hand, torture has, on some occasions, compelled suspects to confess, on the other hand, the outcomes differ depending on the individual. He adds that while torture produces results in some cases, it is often ineffective (Bowden, 2003). Similarly, Carter (2004) suggests intelligence gathered through torture yielded some desired outcomes, for instance, the capture of the late Saddam Hussein in 2003. Nonetheless, he maintains that the bulk of the literature on torture shows that forceful interrogations have the tendency to produce fake information than useful ones (Carter, 2004). In addition, military officers who have engaged in coercive interrogation have largely refuted its usefulness in generating useful intelligence (Budiansky, 2005). He notes that many experienced interrogators have explained that torturing prisoners is not only unlawful, but it has also proven ineffective (Budiansky, 2005).

McCain (2005) also postulates that the cruel treatment of prisoners often results in bad intelligence. He warns that captured terrorists should not be tortured or treated cruelly because it undermines rather than helps the war on terror. Furthermore, he stated that in his experience, 'abuse of prisoners often produces bad intelligence because under torture a person will say anything he thinks his captors want to hear--whether it is true or false if he believes it will relieve his suffering' (McCain, 2005: 34).

So far, much of the discussion is centred on the interplay between security and human rights and the extant and relevant literature on states' moral obligations to the international conventions on International Relations and human rights in armed conflict from both realist and liberal viewpoints. While International Law and International Human Rights Law remain the main and most referenced legal instruments in the international terrorism and counterterrorism debate, it is

equally sacrosanct to examine existing domestic legal frameworks and how they apply to domestic conflicts such as insurgency. This is even more important given the domestic nature of the case under investigation and the level of the allegations of human rights abuses in the conflict. As such, an analysis of the domestic counterterrorism legal framework will help in the better understanding of the objectives of these laws and their application in preventing and or countering terrorism and terrorism-related activities in Nigeria. Thus, a detailed presentation and analysis of Nigeria's National Counterterrorism Strategy (NACTEST) and other terrorism prevention Acts will be the focus of the next section.

Conclusion

This chapter examined the international and domestic counterterrorism strategies with a focus on the UN Global Counterterrorism Strategies and its various mechanisms for strengthening international and regional approaches to counterterrorism, including the four major pillars for the prevention of all forms of terrorism and violent extremism among member states. Also, some of the UN treaties and conventions, the UNOAU counterterrorism efforts, and the UN Security Council's resolutions in combating international and regional terrorism were discussed. Consequently, the human rights challenges of the UN Global Counterterrorism Strategy and the Nigerian counterterrorism strategy, as well as their objectives, including the various acts for implementing the counterterrorism efforts, were elaborately outlined. Additionally, the moral discourse on torture from a security and human rights context within the international law framework and its effectiveness in global counterterrorism efforts were also presented. Specifically, the section made a critique of the moral debate on torture and its application in national security discourse from a liberal and realist viewpoint and its intersection with human rights provisions as enshrined in the international regime.

CHAPTER FOUR (4)

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

4.0 Introduction

Leedy and Ormrod (2001:14) state that research methodology is ‘the general approach the researcher takes in carrying out a research project’. Similarly, Howell (2013) defines research methodology as the overall research plan that explains how research is to be carried out, including the identification of the methods to be employed in it. The methods identified in a methodology describe how data will be collected and analysed (Howell, 2013). Thus, a methodology is the systematic, theoretical inquiry of the approaches used in a study. It includes the theoretical examination of several methods and principles linked with a branch of knowledge. It usually comprises concepts like paradigms, theoretical models, stages, and quantitative or qualitative methods (Irny, 2005). As such, research methodology is the philosophical blueprint of the research being undertaken as well as the bedrock on which the research is built (Brown, 2006). It has also been referred to as the framework designed in relation to a specific set of model assumptions used in conducting research (O’Leary, 2004).

This chapter details the research methodology for conducting the study. It outlines the research approach and design and the justification for its use. This chapter also explains the data collection and analysis procedures and the sampling technique. The study's objective and research design are also outlined, including justifications for the choice of the case study approach. In summary, this chapter provides the research framework encompassing the entire gamut of the research methods applicable to the overarching research question and in line with my epistemology.

4.1 Research Question

4.1.1 Defining a research question

A research question is a question that a research project sets out to answer (Mattick et al., 2018). Choosing a research question is an essential element of both quantitative and qualitative research. An investigation will require data collection and analysis, and the methodology for this will vary widely. Good research questions seek to improve knowledge on an important topic and are usually narrow and specific (Mattick et al., 2018). In addition, a research question provides a focus for investigation. It also clearly defines a significant area of interest (for the individual or a group) which requires investigation. A research question is the fundamental core of a research project, study, or review of a body of literature. It helps focus the study, determines the methodology, and guides all stages of inquiry, analysis, and reporting (Lewak, 2015).

Martiskova (2016) asserts that a research question is a focused, concise, and critical aspect of research that is arguable and relates to the theme of a given research. Furthermore, a research question is the foundation of any research that answers the basic query of the researcher; ‘what do I want to know about my topic?’ Moreover, it gives the writer a clear path for the entire structure of the literature review, data collection, data analysis, and conclusion (Martiskova, 2016). Also, qualitative research tries to determine the relationship between two or more variables but is more focused on individual experiences and events rather than on numbers, which is why its research questions start with ‘how’ and ‘why’ (Martiskova, 2016). Finally, the answer to a research question will help address a research problem (Booth et al., 1995).

4.1.2 Research aim

This study seeks to investigate the nature and extent of human rights violations by the Nigerian military in the Boko Haram conflict. The interplay between security and human rights in armed conflicts and how they can be balanced within the context of international relations/law is at the core of this study. The under-listed specific research questions will also be examined:

1. How are violent conflicts and human rights violations linked?
2. What is the nature and extent of human rights violations in the Boko Haram conflict?
3. How have Nigeria's counterterrorism measures impacted human rights within the context of international law?
4. How can the need for security and the demand for individual rights be balanced?

4.2 Methodological underpinnings

Terrorism studies are mainly criticised for largely relying on secondary data sources (Schmid and Jongman, 1998; Silke, 2001; Jackson, 2007; Gunning, 2007). Therefore, there is scepticism about the research rigour of the studies in this field, given the lack of adequate primary data sources that would generate new knowledge and areas of analysis (Smyth, 2007). This has been well captured by Silke (2004), who notes that the majority of the research on terrorism is predominantly based on secondary rather than primary data sources because of limitations on methodology and institutional bias, including state funding of research on terrorism that restrict reflexive research (Blakeley, 2007, 2010; Gunning, 2007; Peoples and William, 2014).

With particular reference to terrorism research in Nigeria, much research in this field is ahistorical and largely reliant on secondary data sources (Njoku, 2020; Uzorka, 2020; Omenma and Hendricks, 2018; Tella, 2017; Olaniyi, 2016; O. Omale, 2013; Solomon, 2012; Nte, 2011). This methodological gap and lack of "multidisciplinarity" in terrorism research create the dominance of a shared set of narratives, beliefs, and assumptions on terrorism and counterterrorism in the field that are continually often ill-supported by empirical research

(Jackson, 2007a; 2007b), which according to Silke (2004) is a cabal of virulent myths and incomplete truths advanced by even think tanks and experts.

The above-identified methodological drawbacks imply that rather than analytical, the majority of literature on terrorism studies is mainly imitative and descriptive (Jackson, 2005), and the Boko Haram conflict is a case in point. This underscores the need for empirical and reflexive research that will address the current gap in this field in Nigeria. Therefore, unlike most studies in this area in Nigeria, this research investigates the nature and extent of allegations of human rights in the Boko Haram conflict in Nigeria to provide the required meticulousness and in-depth analysis from a social constructivist viewpoint. This departure from the dominant secondary data-based research that is largely narrow and is merely a reiteration of existing and well-known knowledge allows for a more critical reflection of social reality.

4.3 Research design: Explanatory case study

This research is an explanatory case study and will be guided by the how and what questions to examine the within-case analysis of single cases in a study. According to Jack (2008), once the researcher has decided that a qualitative case study is best suited for answering the research question, what should follow next is deciding the type of case study to be utilised. The choice of a particular type of case study design will be dependent on the overall research purpose. Yin (2003) classifies case studies into three categories: explanatory, exploratory, or descriptive. He likewise distinguishes between single, holistic case studies and multiple-case studies. Hence, the study will utilise what Yin (2003) termed a “holistic single case study”. A holistic case is a case study with a single unit of analysis (Yin, 2009: 50-52). Case study qualitative research is one of the rigorous and thorough methods that “afford researchers opportunities to explore or describe a phenomenon in context using a variety of data sources” (Baxter and Jack, 2008: 544). It is also a strategy that offers insight into how something works in life over time (Brun, 2001). Also, a case study can detect patterns and help “in understanding the difference between the ideal and the real” (Brun, 2001: 117).

A case study design was chosen for this study because it offers the required platform to holistically study a particular problem of upholding, respecting, and preserving human rights

within the context of conflict with more clarity and focus. The qualitative case study enables the investigation of a phenomenon within its context through a range of data sources. On the contrary, a quantitative case study is mainly concerned with finding the relationship between variables, usually by testing a hypothesis. Hopkins (2008) contends that quantitative research designs are usually descriptive or experimental. Descriptive research seeks only to find the relationship between variables. Similarly, an experimental study seeks to establish interlinkage. Also, in a descriptive study, tens of hundreds or more samples are often required to accurately determine the relationship between variables (Hopkins, 2008). This is unnecessary in qualitative research, in which only fewer participants are required, and data collection usually stops at the saturation point where no new data are being generated. Urquhart (2013) postulates that saturation is the stage in coding when no new codes are being generated in the data. There is an increasing emergence of the same codes, but new codes are not forthcoming (Urquhart, 2013). Given (2016) also opines that saturation is the point when more data does not result in generating new themes (Given, 2016).

In addition, quantitative research is an investigation of an already known problem and commonly involves testing a theory, measurement based on numbers, and the use of statistical analyses. In a quantitative method, the objective is to establish whether the prognostic generalisation of a theory is true (Beck, 2010). This approach is not suited for a study such as this in which the topic in view requires the examination of the phenomenon from the perspective of the parties involved in this case, the Nigerian military and civilians. Testing of theories or hypotheses and statistical analyses alone cannot comprehensively and thoroughly facilitate an understanding of the sensitive and complex nature of the alleged human rights violation by the Nigerian Army in the Boko Haram conflict in Nigeria. This topic demands an in-depth investigation into the problem such that the views and opinions of the different subjects involved are captured respectively.

Thus, a qualitative approach allows the issue to be explored through a range of lenses, which enables the unravelling and understanding of the multi-facets of the phenomenon (Jack, 2008). A similar argument has been advanced by Mason (1996), who asserts that “qualitative researchers should not be satisfied with producing explanations which are idiosyncratic to the limited empirical parameters of their study; qualitative research should therefore produce explanations which can be generalised in some way, or which have a wider resonance” (Mason, 1996: 6).

Another advantage of the method is that it leads to findings that are not only unique but also easily generalisable (Yin, 2008). Therefore, by examining the Boko Haram conflict as a single case study, this research will be able to explain the intricate nature of the counter-terrorism operations of the Nigerian armed forces in the north-eastern region of the country, thus having an extensive application and usefulness, which will serve as a link in the sphere of academic studies in counterterrorism.

4.4 Interpretive research

Given the qualitative method adopted for this study, an interpretive, rather than a positivist method, would be used to analyse the cases, thus generating more comprehensive explanations of the cases with narratives rather than mere reductionist and statistical descriptions (Lincoln, 2008). Therefore, the research focuses on understanding the meaning of events from the standpoint of the victims of human rights violations rather than testing hypotheses and causative links between variables. In this context, the researcher aims to unravel how the counter-terrorism efforts of the various security forces, particularly the Nigerian military, affect or impact civil liberty and human rights in the Boko Haram conflict. By exploring the context within which human rights violations occur, the research will show multiple interlinking factors at play and offer a more complete and meaningful explanation (Yin, 2008).

The Boko Haram conflict has lasted for over a decade, and during this period, many allegations of human rights have been labelled against the Nigerian Army. Also, there is widespread criticism of the Nigerian government for not putting enough effort into bringing the perpetrators to justice, an allegation that the government has often denied. Therefore, to get to the root of a sensitive and complex problem such as this, an exploratory research approach is required so that the researcher can engage both parties involved to get the complete picture of the issue.

Furthermore, qualitative research is also best used for answering “specific, narrow questions to obtain measurable and observable data on variables” (Creswell, 2005: 47). Frankel (2000) also states that qualitative research methods are most appropriate when the research questions consist of complex issues that quantitative research methods are incapable of completely solving and the Boko Haram conflict in northeastern Nigeria is a typical example of this.

Another advantage of a qualitative approach and its variation of interpretive research instead of quantitative for this study is the empirical and exploratory nature of the topic. Unlike the quantitative method, where the social and cultural construction of variables that the qualitative approach attempts to correlate is often ignored (Silverman, 2000), qualitative research is mainly concerned with participants' views of their worlds and attempts to explain culturally significant phenomena (Ryan, 2006). Thus, a qualitative rather than quantitative approach is required if what is desired is getting comprehensive information on the alleged human rights violations in the Boko Haram conflict.

4.5 Epistemology

Whereas ontology is about how we understand the nature of social reality, epistemology centres on the means and methods to know this reality (Spencer, 2004). Epistemology is also a part of the philosophy of knowledge that is concerned with the nature, sources, and limits of knowledge. It is an inquiry into what knowledge is, how it is acquired, and how we know what we know (Patton, 1990). Different epistemologies have different conceptions of the nature of reality, produce different knowledge about it, and confer distinct roles to the researcher. Just as is the case with research on any social phenomena, research on terrorism and counter-terrorism results from how the researcher sees and approaches reality (Spalek et al., 2018).

The epistemology of this research is embedded in the constructivist philosophical outlook. Social constructivism is mainly interested in the individuals' viewpoints and the context in which those views are derived. Whereas social constructivism views terrorism as an objective reality, the drivers of terrorism and how it is understood is a social construction. (Turk, 2004; Spalek, 2008). Constructivism is founded based on the social construction of reality (Searle, 1995). What is more essential is undertaking reflexive research through critical thinking regarding the purpose and nature of my research, engaging where essential, critiquing and regularly re-assessing my presuppositions, and in addition, being cautious about the degree to which my opinions, actions, and decisions affect my research (Mason, 2002). In contrast, post-positivism is predicated on a deterministic idea in which causes determine effects or results. Therefore, the problems studied by post-positivists indicate the necessity to identify and evaluate the causes that impact results, e.g., experimental research. It is also reductionistic, given that the aim is to narrow the ideas into

a small, separate set to test, for instance, variables that contain hypotheses and research questions. The knowledge advanced through post-positivism is founded on cautious examination and measurement of the objective reality present 'out there' in the world. Thus, developing statistical procedures of observations and studying individual conduct is of utmost importance for a post-positivist (Creswell, 2014).

Creswell (2014) observes that social constructivists are of the view that individuals try to understand the world they live in. As such, they create subjective meanings of their experiences, i.e., meanings ascribed to particular objects or things. Such meanings are not only different but numerous; thus, the researcher is forced to seek multifaceted forms of views as opposed to reducing meanings into a few categories. The aim of the researcher is to depend on the opinions of the participants regarding the issue being researched. The question becomes far-reaching and general in such a way the participants can frame the meaning of a situation, normally formed through conversing with other individuals (Creswell, 2014). Hence, when used in this research, social constructivism as a perspective fosters close collaboration between the researcher and the participants, as it gives participants the opportunity to narrate their stories (Miller, 1999). In this way, the participants can define their opinions of reality, which then allows the researcher to have a better comprehension of the participants' actions (Lather, 1992; Robottom and Hart, 1993).

From a methodological point of view, therefore, to fully understand the nature of the alleged human rights violations by the Nigerian army in the Boko Haram conflict, the best approach to employ is qualitative research and its constructivist philosophical underpinnings. In addition, qualitative research affords a broader basis from which to generate "well-founded cross-contextual generalities" (Mason, 2002: 1). This study also requires a fluid, flexible research approach that "can move easily around a 'constellation' of potential informants and data types" (Visser, 2000: 16).

4.6 Positionality

Positionality in qualitative research is understood as the position a researcher takes in a particular research study (Savin-Baden & Major, 2013) and prompts the deliberate examination of the

researcher's identity to help the reader understand how their opinion influences or shapes the research topic and processes. Although positionality is an essential aspect of research, and researchers are encouraged to not only show awareness but also admit their position on the research topic, scholars like Creswell, Morse, and Hammersley opposed this research practice due to concerns around bias, ethics, objectivity, and validity of the research analysis and findings. This is especially true in that researchers can easily become selective in their focus on evidence that supports or aligns with their belief systems or opinions (Creswell, 2013; Morse, 1999; Hammersley, 2020). However, scholars like Lipscomb and Carr (2021), have countered this existing rationale and stressed the importance of positionality in social science research.

Arguing from a historical perspective, Lipscomb and Carr (2021) insist that historians cannot isolate themselves from their research and view history as a relatively subjective discipline. The scholars argue that the social, personal and cultural background of a researcher impacts how they approach and produce knowledge. Lipscomb and Carr insist that a research process can be enriched through positionality as it enables critical and ethical engagement with the research topic and highlights how ethical positionality helps researchers to be mindful of the power dynamics between them and their participants, especially in multi-cultural or marginalised situations. In his 1961 classical work "*What is History?*" E.H. Carr postulates that history cannot be entirely objective or factual because it is often a reflection of the historian's selection of sources and narratives and challenges the notion of an unbiased historian, emphasising that history is a dialogue of the researcher's past and present (Carr, 1961).

While Carr (2021) recognises the subjective nature of historical interpretation, on the contrary, Harding (1995) further argues that a researcher's social and political inclinations have a direct influence on how knowledge is produced. She criticises the proposition that all opinions are seemingly valid, arguing that marginalised perspectives offer a more critical and accurate understanding of social reality as they align more with power structures that are common in traditional research. On the one hand, Harding's position supports the ethical positionality of Lipscomb and Carr, on the other hand, she further advances the debate to the sphere of activism and proposes a more transformative approach to knowledge that strongly focuses on marginalised voices and experiences.

The concepts of positionality and reflexivity in research are closely interlinked. Reflexivity deals with identity and positionality issues by explicitly making the researcher's opinions known and identifying means to challenge them (Lazard & McAvoy, 2017). These two concepts are commonly linked to qualitative research, especially in critical theory methods in which researchers are required to show awareness of their position and how this, in turn, shapes how knowledge is acquired and interpreted (Kincheloe & McLaren, 2008). In my own case, my position in this research aligns with both Carr and Harding's concepts of positionality. First, due to my northern background, where the Boko Haram conflict originates and is prevalent, my direct experience of the conflict and its impact on the socio-political and religious landscape of the local community, including my family, has indeed shaped my perception and interpretation of the conflict. This fits well with Lipscomb and Carr's proposition that the researcher's social and cultural background inevitably influences their interpretation and production of knowledge. As a humanitarian, the guiding principles and ethics of my work abhor human rights abuses in whatever form or shape, regardless of who commits them. As such, my views and approach to examining the research topic inherently align with human rights principles and have the tendency to be implicitly or explicitly prejudicial towards any acts contrary to these values and principles. From this perspective, my positionality also aligns with Carr's radical argument on positionality that advances activism and the amplification of marginalised voices, which in the context of this research are victims of human rights violations. These two factors have, to an extent, influenced my views, understanding and interpretation of knowledge throughout the thesis.

Thus, reflecting on my doctoral journey over the past four years, my positionality and worldview have greatly transformed from a human rights-centred predisposition to a more academic point of view. Suffice it to say, therefore, that rather than personal opinion and experience, my overall approach to understanding and interpreting the interplay between security and human rights in the Boko Haram conflict is informed by critical analysis of the research problem that is factual and evidence-based. As such, I am now more an academic than a human rights activist.

4.7 Data collection

Apart from the secondary sources of data utilised in carrying out the overall research, the main primary data before this study was generated through in-depth interviews. The secondary data,

for the most part, consists of academic journal articles, textbooks, reports from highly reputable local and international NGOs in the field of security studies, and verifiable/reliable media reports.

In the context of this study, Human Rights Watch (HRW) and Amnesty International (AI) are the two major secondary data sources utilised. This is because they are the two organisations that publish most of the data on human rights issues in Africa, especially Nigeria. In fact, according to Leech (2013), in the past three decades, Human Rights Watch has been one of the front runners among NGOs in the world that advance human rights globally. However, there is growing criticism about the credibility of some of their reports in recent times. For instance, the HRW is criticised for being selective on certain human rights issues in their reports (Leech, 2013), subjective and biased (Rubin, 2020), unprofessionalism, poor research methodology, and concerns about the credibility and reliability of their reports (Ballesteros et al., 2007; Sheehan, 2021). In addition, the organisation is also accused of producing reports that are sometimes politically motivated and ideologically prejudiced (Ping, 2022).

All this criticism undermines the credibility of the reports published by these organisations and may be viewed as inappropriate for academic research such as this. However, it would be wrong to assume that reports from these organisations are always biased or not credible. On the contrary, much of their published data is cited in several academic articles, International NGOs such as the UN, and reputable media outlets. According to Osnos (2012), HRW is an indispensable source for tracking violence and human rights repression globally and has published several credible reports from across the globe over the years. Thus, to ensure credibility, most of the data and information from AI and HRW used in this study are cross-examined with other credible sources to the extent that the information is verifiable.

In terms of data collection, this study adopted a semi-structured type of interview. As a common practice in qualitative research, the interviews are generally open-ended questions that are few and intended to elicit views and opinions from the participants (Creswell, 2014). Bell (1999) notes that this method is flexible as modifications of the questions can be made where necessary as the interview is being conducted (Bell, 1999). Although there are several approaches to interviewing in social science research, this study will adopt what Fujii (2018) called 'the relational interview approach'. According to Fujii (2018), relational interviewing is a method of

collecting data through conversations between the researcher and the participant. Its philosophy is human-centred, and it is based on reflexivity. The justification for choosing this method of interview is predicated on its interpretive rather than positivist nature. The relational interview, unlike other social research tools such as surveys in which the researcher is restricted to an already drafted set of questions and is unable to re-create new questions even if an interviewee's response raises another question or set of questions that requires further interrogation, the relational interview allows the researcher to reformulate research questions as new evidence emerges in the course of the interview. Further justification for adopting this method of data collection, as Fujii (2018) rightly observed, is that its objective is not just the extraction of information from the participants through questioning but also understanding how they view the world by dialoguing with them. In a relational interview, interaction rather than interrogation is the process through which data is generated, and through this interaction, research-based knowledge is engendered (Fujii, 2018). The interviews will focus on a sequence of key questions and will be exploratory such that the participants are convenient to share their experiences and knowledge as the interview unfolds.

In the context of terrorism studies, which have drawn widespread criticism for largely depending on secondary data sources (Schmid and Jongman, 1998; Silke, 2001; Jackson, 2007; Gunning, 2007a), there is scepticism about the reliability and validity of research in this field given the scarcity of primary data sources needed to generate new knowledge and areas of analysis (Smyth, 2007). Therefore, the interview approach will help provide a historical perspective of the allegations of human rights violations in the Boko Haram conflict in north-east Nigeria by engaging with key state and non-state actors hence, providing comprehensive and reliable data that is required in terrorism and counterterrorism research such as this.

The interviews will be conducted face-to-face, but where this proves impossible, a telephone or online video interview shall be arranged. The 'general interview guide' method and the standardised open-ended interview propounded by Patton (2002) will serve as a guide for the interview process. Unlike structured interview, which is mostly organised around a set of already constructed questions that restrict participants' responses to yes or no answers, which in turn limits participants' ability to fully express their views (Berg, 2001), or an unstructured interview that slightly offers greater flexibility for both the interviewer and the interviewee (Holstein,

2001), the relational interview, just like a semi-structured opened-ended interview, provides for a more interactive and detailed discussion between the researcher and the interviewee and the exploration of participant's views and beliefs on a given issue that are sometimes personal and sensitive (Vaughn, 2019).

4.7.1 The Interview Setting

The interviews were conducted in two phases. The first phase involved a visit to IDP camps in the Boko Haram conflict-stricken north-eastern region of Nigeria. These camps are home to a large number of people displaced by the conflict and those who have first-hand experience of the conflict in most of its ramifications. Thus, participants in this study were drawn from these camps, which also served as venues for conducting some of the interviews. The IDP camps are in the northeastern Borno and Adamawa states, respectively. The second phase took place in Nigeria's Federal Capital Territory (FCT), where the headquarters of most security and intelligence agencies are located. Targeted participants will include leaders and policymakers such as legislators, top government security officials in the army, the police force, the Department for State Security (DSS), and heads of NGOs with operational stations in the study area. Each phase was planned to take a total of between four to six weeks. Furthermore, due to the sensitivity of the research to the various security agencies, it was anticipated that some agencies might be reluctant to grant interviews or even deny access to their personnel to be interviewed. In such a situation, potential gatekeepers were identified to assist in facilitating access to such agencies. A gatekeeper is someone who can allow or restrict the researcher's access to participants. An example of this is a top official in an organisation or an individual in a community who has the power to deny or permit the researcher access to conduct the research (Saunders, 2006). When planning to conduct research, it is a common practice to take into consideration the sensitive nature of the study, the susceptibility of the participants, and the use of gatekeepers to enter the research area (Wheeler, 2009).

Furthermore, for many years, fieldworkers have continually found it difficult to gain access to research sites. In some instances, it may be wrongly viewed as not being a problem in research studies (Sixsmith et al., 2003). Yet there is proof that shows that the gatekeeping procedure has impacted research studies negatively in different aspects (Rist, 1976). They comprise restricting

the conditions for meeting with participants, restricting access to data and to interviewees, limiting the breadth of analysis, and withholding privileges in terms of dissemination methods (Rist, 1976). However, to avoid these challenges in this study, the researcher identified close family contacts currently serving in the Nigerian Army, where gatekeepers were required due to the highly secretive and strict nature of the institution.

4.7.2 Sampling technique

Niehauss (2009) observes whether the methodology adopted is quantitative or qualitative; sampling techniques are envisioned to increase efficacy and validity. Even so, sampling must be in accordance with the goals and presumptions intrinsic to the use of either method. Qualitative approaches are, for the most part, meant to attain depth of understanding, whereas quantitative approaches are intended to achieve extensiveness of understanding (Patton, 2002). The common practice in qualitative research is to purposefully select participants or sites that will assist the researcher in the best possible way to investigate the problem and the research question. This does not essentially imply random sampling or selection of a large number of participants and sites, as typically found in quantitative research (Creswell, 2014).

Convenience, purposefulness, and theory are the three main sampling strategies in qualitative research. The least thorough strategy among them is convenience sampling, as it entails the utilisation of the easily available participants. This strategy is also cheap and less time-consuming, and the data is often poor due to a lack of academic credibility (Nikolopoulou, 2022). Another common sampling strategy in qualitative research is, to some extent, theoretically in nature. It involves the framing of interpretative theories from new data and applying a new sample to analyse and explain the theory. Although this strategy is mainly associated with grounded theory, in some ways, it can also be applied in most qualitative research where interpretation is required (SAGO, 2023). Furthermore, there is also a technique commonly known as purposeful sampling. In this strategy, a structure of the variables that will potentially affect the participant's opinion is developed, which is dependent on the researcher's knowledge of the topic, existing literature, and the study's findings. Compared to other sampling techniques, purposeful sampling is highly intellectual and can be ranked based on existing public attitudes if the researcher knows the subjects. This type of sampling may be beneficial for

examining a diverse range of participants, including outliers (deviant sample), participants with specific experiences (critical case sample), as is the case in this study, or participants with exceptional skills (key informant sample). Generally, there is a significant intersection between the three sampling strategies, as evidenced in the explanation above. The comparative balance is dependent on the research question selected, data analysis and interpretation style. Because qualitative research is a natural approach as it involves the study of people in real and not in artificial settings, the individual's characteristics and the temporal, spatial and study context should be considered (Marshall, 1996).

4.6.3 Purposeful sampling

Purposeful sampling in qualitative and mixed methods research consists of reiterative steps for choosing research participants instead of a prearranged sample. In grounded theory, for instance, Schutt (2006) contends that the sampling selection steps involve identifying topics, ideas, and indicators through observation and meditation. When using this technique, researchers choose participants based on their understanding or familiarity with experimental inquiry (Schutt, 2006). Also, purposeful sampling is not meant to give a representative sample but to enhance a given phenomenon. The selection process includes prioritising knowledgeable and experienced participants of the cultural settings of the phenomena being investigated, a consideration of the participant's willingness to talk and the ability to extensively discuss their views (Rubin, 1995).

Additionally, purposeful sampling, just like other similar non-probability sampling, produces information unique from that of probability sampling. Yet, drawing on differing views can create a crucial understanding of qualitative and mixed methods-driven research by highlighting the significance of the participant's positionality and the research in point. The different forms this sampling technique contributes to wider research objectives have been outlined by Teddlie and Yu (2007), which involves creating representativeness, highlighting special cases, and the gradual selection of cases according to their relevance to the research question. Furthermore, purposeful sampling enables the prolonged interaction between the researcher and participants and generates even richer data compared to random sampling (Shaw, 1999).

In comparison, purposeful sampling differs from other types of non-probability sampling, like availability and snowball sampling, and is not an easily available constituent of the population, nor is it easy to reach or find. Also, unlike quota sampling, the basis for selection in purposeful sampling is not dependent on the populations' demographics. Purposeful sampling is, however, mainly criticised for the inadequate explanation of the selection criteria by researchers who use it, which questions their research integrity and hinders them from taking full advantage of this knowledge during the analysis. Notwithstanding, for researchers who are conscious of their selection process, the purposeful sampling technique can provide a better understanding of multifaceted social processes that are often overlooked or disregarded in probability-sampling-based research (Robinson, 2014).

Therefore, a purposeful sampling technique will be employed in this research. This sampling technique is widely used in qualitative research to identify and select cases with robust information for the most effective use of inadequate resources (Patton, 2002). It also involves identifying and selecting individuals or groups specifically knowledgeable of or experienced with a phenomenon of interest (Clark, 2011). Therefore, given the foregoing, this sampling technique is best suited for this research because it would enable the identification and selection of participants directly involved in the conflict. These include security officials, community members affected by the conflict and legislators, human rights organisations, and individuals/groups who are familiar with and have comprehensive knowledge of the Boko Haram conflict.

4.7.4 Population of the study

Qualitative research usually has a smaller sample size compared to quantitative research due to its emphasis on getting a deeper understanding of an issue or problem, often focused on the “*how* and *why*” question of a particular social process, situation, or given social interactions (Creswell, 2014). Rather than the generalisation of the population and testing hypothesis, an in-depth interview is an inductive and nascent process. Therefore, in-depth interviews and grounded theory seek to create categories from the data and analyse connections between them, as well as address how participants' lived experiences can be comprehended (Charmaz, 1990).

Several discussions exist on the right sample size to use in qualitative research, and they mostly centre on the concept of saturation, whereby new or relevant data is no longer emerging in the data collection process (Mark, 2010), or when new theoretical understanding is no longer derived from the data nor shows the research's major theoretical themes (Charmaz, 1990). Data saturation is determined by many factors, and some are beyond the research's control, including the homogenous or heterogenous nature of the population, the selection condition, the research budget and the researcher's intellectual ability to know when the data has reached saturation (Charmaz, 1990). Although less emphasis is given to the number of interviews required by most experts in qualitative research, there is also no specific minimum recommended or generally acceptable number. Between five to fifty interviews are usually considered adequate in the majority of the academic literature on research methods, with much consideration given to the quality of the data, the study's scope, the research topic, and the overall research methodology used (Morse, 2000).

For this research, therefore, the intended total number of interviews to be conducted is twenty-five. This consisted of three retired military officers of the Nigerian Armed Forces, three serving DSS Personnel, and two serving officers of the Nigerian Police Force who had experience in the conflict. The choice of retired army officers is deliberate and is intended to reduce the level of bias given that serving officials may tend to withhold key information that is, however, vital to this research in order to preserve the reputation of their institutions or to protect their jobs. One of the major limitations of this strategy is that retired officers may not have access to current information on the activities and operations of the Nigerian army. They may also label false allegations against the institution in the form of retaliation if they hold any grudge against their former employer.

In addition, the Executive Director of the National Human Rights Commission (NHRC) and Nigeria's Country Director, Amnesty International (AI), were interviewed. The Chairman of the House Committee on Army of Nigeria's National Assembly, The Chairman of the House Committee on Human Rights, and two members of the committee were also interviewed. The other research participants include two state officials of the National Human Rights Commission Adamawa state chapter, an official of the National Emergency Management Agency (NEMA) in charge of the Malhoki IDP camp in Jimeta Adamawa state, and twenty IDPs. Ten were from the

Malhoki IDP camp in Jimeta, Adamawa state, and the other ten were from IDPs already integrated into the society.

4.8 Data analysis and interpretation

Data analysis is a crucial aspect of research and follows immediately after data collection. However, it can also be done simultaneously alongside data collection. The intent is to make sense of the text and or image data, as the case may be. It involves segmenting and setting apart the data as well as putting it back together (Creswell, 2014). The first step taken in the analysis of the data is the one advanced by Kane and Brun (2001), who suggest that the data collected should be initially reduced, structured, and organised in conformity with the extensive themes discussed in the review of the literature. Since the interviews were audio-recorded where ethically practicable, the data was transcribed and, in some cases, translated. A total of twelve audio-taped interviews (approximately eleven hours) were transcribed, while two other interviews were handwritten before data coding commenced. Coding refers to detecting and describing procedures whereby the researcher tags, splits, compiles, and organises data to expressively connect the coding to categories (Taylor, 2010). Therefore, key information gleaned from the interviews formed the basis for developing codes.

The data was analysed using a qualitative computer data analysis program called the QSR NVivo. Lester (2016) notes that Computer-assisted Qualitative Data Analysis Software (CAQDAS) is made of tools that can be used to transcribe, code, and interpret the text. Also, this computer software can be used in content analysis, grounded theory, and discourse analysis (Lester, 2016). QDA has recently been more widely used in qualitative research because hand coding is strenuous and often a long process, even for smaller data. Creswell (2014) confirmed this when he states that qualitative software programs have become the most preferred method for researchers in that they help them easily sort, organise, and look for information in text or image databases. Though the researcher must still read each line of the text and assign code just like hand coding, this method may prove faster and more effective than hand-coding (Creswell, 2014).

The first step taken in the NVivo analysis was the importation of the transcribed interview document, which was then explored and reviewed. After exploring, the data was then coded according to themes and saved in the form of nodes. For instance, I copied all references to the cruel treatment of suspects, such as beating, from the interviews and coded them as evidence of torture. I then further reviewed and organised all the references into sub-themes. For instance, I coded all references that support torture under “justifications for torture.” I even used a verbatim response from one of the participants, who stated that “when it comes to life and death, torture is inevitable”, to coin one of the sub-themes under torture. After each coding, a review was then carried out to identify relationships between codes, and where necessary, unrelated or irrelevant codes were uncoded and transferred to other nodes. This process was replicated throughout the coding process to identify word frequency and relevance and develop key themes and sub-themes. I also created an interview memo to help summarise key points and note contradictions or surprises on a particular issue. For instance, the memo helped me identify contrasting responses among IDP focus groups on the efficiency of the military approach to counterterrorism, which I later developed into a theme titled “contrasting opinions from the participants”.

Afterwards, all the themes were transferred to an MS Word document and thematically analysed. Braun and Clarke (2006) contend that thematic analysis is a technique used in qualitative data analyses that usually involves searching a set of data transversely to find, analyse, and record recurrent patterns (Clarke, 2006). A thematic analysis is chosen based on the exploratory nature of this research and the thematic pattern in which the literature review and the interview questions were constructed, respectively. As Joffe (2011) rightly points out, a thematic analysis is mainly suitable for a constructivist research approach because as a wide range of data is being analysed, it shows how a particular social construct develops. As such, a constructivist thematic analysis will aid in discovering more dormant, deeper themes in the data (Joffe, 2011).

4.9 Ethical considerations (Ethics approval reference number: 13294)

Ethics is an important aspect of research, and adherence to ethical standards is vital in contemporary social research. For example, Sultana (2007) contends that “in order to undertake ethical research, it is critical to pay attention to positionality, reflexivity, the production of

knowledge, and the power relations inherent in research processes” (Sultana, 2007: 382). Therefore, to conduct ethically compliant research, all participants were given an informed consent form defining the nature, aims, and processes of the study prior to the interview, which they will be required to sign or assent to. Informed consent, according to Biggs (2010), is a requirement for independent decision-making, while O’Neill (2002) observes that the social values widely associated with informed consent are autonomy and trust. The benefit of informed consent in research involving human subjects is that it promotes respect for the participants while allowing the researcher to engage with them, thereby enhancing the relationship between the researcher and the participants, which may reduce discontent and litigation (Schofield, 2014). According to Ursin (2009), two factors play a vital role in recruiting participants in a research study. First, the consent to participate must be informed completely and granted freely. Informed consent must be deemed essential to protect the individual from hurt and to ensure the basis of self-sufficiency as a right is protected by enabling participants to choose independently (Ursin, 2009).

For this research, the interviews were audio-recorded where possible. However, where participants disapproved of this method, notes were taken instead. The interviews were conducted in private, usually in the participant’s office or any venue where the participant feels secure and comfortable being interviewed, e.g., a café. For the IDPs, all interviews were conducted within the IDP camp in a designated office approved by the camp officials. Participants were notified of their right to decline to answer any question they felt uncomfortable with and to terminate the interview whenever they felt the need to.

Overall, the interviews were conducted pursuant to the guidelines provided by the Ethics Committee of the University of the West of Scotland. Ethics approval letter, consent and participant’s information forms, and screenshots of the code books can be found on pages 190-196). Participants were assured of the confidentiality of their details and that the use of all information given would be restricted only for this study. Confidentiality is a practice by which the privacy of a person is protected. It relates to the handling of information revealed by a person based on trust, and such information can only be disclosed to others with the permission of the informant (Institute, 2005). In addition, in research ethics, the fundamental principle relating to confidentiality involves a requirement that the researcher ensures that all information gathered

from or disclosed by individuals respects the dignity and independence of the participant and does not infringe on the individual or community's interest (Bos, 2020). Both the Helsinki Declaration, as amended in 2013, and the European General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR, 2018) ratified the right to confidentiality in research.

Therefore, to ensure privacy and confidentiality in this research, each participant was given a code name and anonymised. At the end of the interview, verbatim transcriptions and handwritten interpretations of the interview were sent to some participants, such as security personnel and legislatures, for review, and all were satisfied with the transcripts. This view is supported by Patton (2002), who asserts that qualitative methods are commonly used in evaluations since they tell the program's story by gathering and communicating the participants' stories (Patton, 2002).

4.10 Limitations of the study

As with any other research approach, qualitative research has limitations. One of the limitations of this approach is that it is time-consuming, as interviews usually last one hour or more and can take up to one to two months for the overall exercise to be completed. However, in the context of this study, the major limitation is the adoption of a single data collection approach, making it impossible for methodological triangulation. Methodological triangulation helps to mitigate researcher bias (Bekhet and Zauszniewski, 2012; Gorissen, van Bruggen, and Jochems, 2013; Horne and Horgan, 2012; Lloyd, 2011). Denzin (1989) observes that the ability to envisage data from a different viewpoint and study a phenomenon in multiple ways helps curtail the tendency to look at data from just a single perspective (Denzin, 1989). The use of triangulation in terms of multiple data sources enhances the reliability of results (Stavros and Westberg, 2009) and the saturation of data (Fusch and Ness, 2015). However, Atkinson and Hamersley (1983) warn that "one should not adopt a naively optimistic view that the aggregation of data from different sources will 'unproblematically' add up to a complete picture" (Atkinson, 1983: 199).

Furthermore, there was an issue of language barrier during the interview as most of the IDPs do not understand the English language. This made it difficult to ask some questions using the right and appropriate grammar originally drafted despite my good command of the local language. The implication of this is that in translating the questions to the respondents' language, the

questions are either taken out of context or the respondents find them difficult to comprehend. However, it is important to also note that the questions in point are few. Another limitation is the use of research assistants during the fieldwork. Research assistants are usually recruited by a senior researcher either in academic or non-academic settings to conduct desk-based research tasks such as literature review or interpreted bibliographies (Molony, 2007), or coordinate the collection of primary data in a large-scale research project (Grosh, 2000). In the context of this research, an official of the Nigeria Emergency Management Agency NEMA was recruited to help me navigate the local terrain due to security concerns as the IDP camps were situated within the conflict zone, and my business travel was yet to be approved (though there was no violence at the time of the data collection) and to assist in identifying suitable participants and conduct interviews. The NEMA official has good research experience and has helped other NGOs collect data from the IDP camps in the past, which made him suitable and qualified for the role. However, the five interviews conducted by the research assistant were not included in the final analysis due to some discrepancies and the fact that I later interviewed the same participants following the approval of my business travel.

Conclusion

This chapter discussed the study's research methodology in detail. Firstly, the research aim is to investigate the nature and extent of human rights violations by the Nigerian military in the Boko Haram conflict, the interplay between security and human rights in armed conflicts, and how these two inseparable values (human rights and security) could be balanced within the context of International Relations/Law was presented. Secondly, the specific research objectives and the methodological underpinnings both within the broader context of terrorism studies and terrorism research in Nigeria were also highlighted. Thirdly, the research design (explanatory, holistic case study) and justifications for its adoption in this study were explained. Fourthly, the data collection (in-depth and open-ended interviews), including the interview settings and stages and analysis (thematic) procedures, the sampling (purposeful) technique, and the study population, were further discussed. This was followed by the research ethical considerations in which all ethical requirements for data collection under the UWS ethical guidelines were elaborated. The chapter concluded by discussing the impact of COVID-19 on my research, mental health and

general well-being, including the study's limitations. In summary, this chapter provides the research framework encompassing the entire gamut of the research methods applicable to the overarching research question and in line with my epistemology.

CHAPTER FIVE (5)

A MILITARISTIC APPROACH TO COUNTERTERRORISM

5.0 Introduction

The concerns for human rights protection during conflict situations such as terrorism and insurgency have attracted serious debates in the pre-and post-9/11 attack (Yourow, 1996; O'Boyle, 1998; Gross and Aoláin 2001, Dershowitz, 2002; Ignattief, 2004; Ramcharan, 2004; Goold and Lazarus, 2007;). Military governments are often criticised for their disregard for human rights laws. However, some of the world's foremost democracies, such as the US and the UK, which often project themselves as symbols of liberal states built on and committed to an ideology that promotes individual rights and civil liberty, have also come under widespread scrutiny especially, in their 'war on terror' campaigns (Daalder and Lindsay, 2001; Burke-White, 2004; Denise 2004; Scot, 2004; Amnesty International, 2004; Goldstone, 2005; Kennedy-Pipe and Vickers, 2007; Ryan, 2008; Gearthy, 2010). Their response to these allegations is often denial, and Nigeria has also been found wanting in this regard in its counter-insurgency operations against Boko Haram. However, just like their counterparts, the Nigerian Government, especially the Nigerian military, also often turn a blind eye to these allegations (Amnesty International, 2020). Drawing from the data collected, this chapter aims to analyse and discuss the major themes of human rights abuses in the Boko Haram conflict. The analysis will be focused on the real-life experiences of the victims of human rights violations and the nature, prevalence, and extent of these violations. There are five major themes to be analysed in this chapter. The first three themes will cover the issues of illegal arrest and detention of suspects, privacy violations, extortion, and rape, and the evidence and prevalence of such alleged violations by the Nigerian Military. The last two themes in this chapter will critique the discourse on torture and the debate on the effectiveness and reliability of the method as an interrogation technique in counterterrorism.

5.1 Indiscriminate, unlawful arrest and detention of suspects

Unlawful arrest and detention of suspects are one of the most common forms of human rights violations in the war on terror campaigns. This usually occurs during counter-terrorism operations where security personnel arrest and detain individuals suspected to be terrorists for a long period, either based on intelligence or suspicion, without any concrete evidence or legal procedure. This type of act contravenes one of the provisions of international human rights law, which protects every person against arbitrary arrest. This is rightly put by Londras (2011) in her book *Detention in the War on Terror: Can Human Rights Fight Back?* Here, she opines that what is expected is not absolute liberty but rather that liberty can only be contravened within the provisions of international human rights law. To be precise, only in a restricted number of circumstances should individuals' rights be truncated (i.e., that the bases for detention are clear) and in a contested way (i.e., that the reason for detention is deliberated upon by a constitutionally recognised authority whose resolutions will be obeyed by the detaining body) (Londras, 2011).

Commenting on this issue, a senior legislator of the Nigerian House of Representatives also worried that:

“The number of people in detention today is so alarming, and most of those people are innocent. Why do you go and arrest the mother, the wife, and the father of a suspect and put them in detention? What have they done? If we have an intelligence system that is working, you don't need to do that. You can track anybody using modern-day intelligence-gathering technology such as voice recognition, phone tracking, et cetera, to trace and nab terrorists and criminals anywhere in the world” (Member A).

The guide to the case law of the European Court of Human Rights (ECHR) further validates Londras' postulations. According to Article 5 sections (1(a), (b), and (c), a person can only be detained after being convicted by a competent court for disobeying a legal order of a court or to secure the fulfilment of any requirement specified by law; on serious suspicion for committing an offence or when adjudged essential to deter the person from committing an offence or fleeing after doing so (ECHR, 2021).

However, after the 9/11 attack, many countries, especially the US and the UK, have been criticised by the international community and many other international human rights NGOs, such

as Human Rights Watch, for unlawfully arresting and detaining civilians on suspicion of engaging in terrorist activities for a prolonged period without any form of the legal backing (Gross, 2002; Roberts, 2007; Cassel, 2008; Hakimi, 2009). According to Londras (2011), despite taking distinctly different executive strategies in executing their anti-terrorism operations following the 9/11 attacks, both the US and the UK have sought legislation that presents a significant danger to the existing principles of the international human rights regime (Londras, 2011). One example of such legislation is Part 4 Section 23 1 (2) of the UK Anti-Terrorism Crime and Security Act 2001 (ATCSA), later renamed the Prevention of Terrorism Act (PTA) 2005 in March 2005, under which the Home Secretary was empowered to permit the detention of terrorist suspects whether temporarily or indefinitely. This contradicts the European Convention on Human Rights, as stated in the Human Rights Act 1998. Even though these laws are being reviewed almost annually by Parliament to ensure compliance with the provisions of the international human rights regime, the level of transparency in the implementation of such reviews and adherence by law enforcement agencies during counter-terrorism operations remains under serious public scrutiny and criticism.

Furthermore, Londras (2011) also suggests that the detention of suspects involved in acts of terrorism was at the core of the counter-terrorism policies of both the Bush and Blair administrations. In either case, there was a concerted effort not just to a counter-terrorist detention agenda but also to a very secretive detention system through which this detention is to be reviewed. Terrorist suspects were projected by both administrations to be dangerous to the extent that they could be detained and convicted without proper systems and procedures of review (Londras, 2011). The US's Guantanamo Bay and the UK's Frankland prisons, where hundreds of terrorist suspects are being detained for years without trial or conviction, are good examples of the US/UK Governments' disregard for the protection of the rights of persons against arbitrary arrest and detention as enshrined in the international human rights regime (ACLU, 2022; HRW, 2020; Borelli, 2005). According to Letta Tayler, an associate Crisis and Conflict director at Human Rights Watch, Guantanamo Bay is still among the lasting symbols of injustice and neglect of the rule of law and human rights masterminded by the US in retaliation to the 9/11 attacks (HRW, 2022).

Several instances of these forms of abuses also abound in the Boko Haram conflict, as evidenced in several media and NGO reports and research publications, including a plethora of outstanding court cases against the Nigerian military by the victims of this violation. Worst still, even IDP camps that are meant to be safe havens for civilians are not spared from these violations by the Nigerian military. For instance, one female IDP during an interview revealed that:

“Yes, I have seen it. For instance, when we fled from our villages to save our lives from Boko Haram attacks, we were expecting the soldiers to rescue us. Instead, we fled by ourselves, and it is not as if the soldiers went and rescued us from Boko Haram. But instead of helping us, they captured many men and imprisoned them. Separating them from their wives and children. This is inappropriate” (Respondent 1, female IDPs peer group).

Similar to the Guantanamo prison run by the US government, the Giwa barracks detention facility, which is situated in the heart of the conflict zone in north-eastern Nigeria, is the most popular terrorist detention facility in the country due to the cruel conditions detainees are subjected to. A 2016 Amnesty International report revealed at least 20,000 suspects were unlawfully arrested and detained by the Nigerian military since 2011. Most of the detainees were denied the right to see their families or legal representatives or tried and convicted in a court of law (Amnesty International, 2016). The report further added that around 7,000 suspects have died in military custody due to poor medical care, lack of feeding, inadequate water supply, and diseases due to poor sanitation. Another shocking revelation in the report indicates that the military slaughtered and shot 640 suspects they recaptured following a Boko Haram Jailbreak attack on Giwa barracks on the 14th of March 2014, and the government never made any effort to launch an investigation into the incident or prosecute the perpetrators (Amnesty International, 2016). Therefore, it is imperative to investigate this issue in that it is one of the forms of abuse under investigation in this study and forms part of the core research questions, which is to investigate the various forms and patterns of the alleged human rights violations by the Nigerian military in the Boko Haram conflict.

5.2 Random, sporadic, and illegal arrests of civilians

An in-depth investigation through interaction with some of the victims of this violation suggests that the random and sporadic arrests/detention of Boko Haram suspects without any evidence or

credible intelligence are prevalent in the Boko Haram counterterrorism efforts of the Nigerian military. When asked whether they have experienced this kind of abuse before, one respondent from the male peer group of IDPs in Malhoki camp in Yola explained that:

“We have seen it even here in this camp. We did not come from the same place; we just met in the camp, and the army just came one fateful day and ordered us to undress. The old and the young, we removed our clothes and threw them away. They did not find anything, yet they tied us up with ropes and threw us all in their vehicles like sacks. All in the name of trying to get information, and there was none. Some people never returned” (Respondent 1, male IDP peer group).

Similarly, a second respondent from the group gave an account of his own experience in the camp, stating that:

“Yes. I have witnessed such instances before. For instance, even in this IDP camp, there was a time the army came and took one man, tying his hands and legs behind his back in such a cruel manner that the man even puked on his body. They took eight people from this camp that very day and only two of them were returned. No one knows where the rest are to date” (Respondent 2, male IDPs peer group).

A 2019 Human Rights Watch report which reveals that the Nigerian military arrested children suspected to be Boko Haram members during military operations and screening exercises for IDPs living outside camps based on intelligence from informants supports the two responses above. On several occasions, some reports suggest that children were arrested by security forces without any substantive evidence (HRW, 2019). Furthermore, the findings from 32 interviewed detained children and youths at Giwa barracks in Maiduguri, Borno state, conducted by HRW, show that they were all arbitrarily arrested and detained for more than two years. All the 32 children interviewed were never tried by a judge in a court of law and were not convicted for any crime or act of terrorism (HRW, 2019).

All the narratives and descriptions of the alleged unlawful arrests of civilians by the Nigerian military given above, if true, would be a contravention of Article 9 of the 1948 Universal Declaration of Human Rights (UDHR), which decrees that “no one shall be subjected to arbitrary arrest, detention or exile,” i.e., no person, irrespective of situations, should be denied their liberty or be banished from their country without any legal backing. In addition, both Article 9(1) of the International Covenant on Civil and Political Rights, Section 35 of the 1999 Constitution of the Federal Republic of Nigeria as amended, and Article 6 of the African Charter on Human and

Peoples' Rights provide for the individual's right to liberty, freedom, and security, and prohibits the arbitrary arrest or detention of individuals.

The description above is not only worrisome but also *prima facie* unlawful, as they both constitute a contravention of the Constitution of the Federal Republic of Nigeria and the International Human Rights Law and should not be condoned even in the most brutal of despotic states. Therefore, for a democratic state such as Nigeria, these sorts of violations by the military are highhanded and in contention with the international human rights law of which Nigeria is a signatory.

During an accountability forum on civil-military relations in 2019, the Nigerian army's human rights desk officer disclosed that the body had received 350 petitions of alleged human rights violations from the public in three years. Among the 350 petitions, assault, torture, cruel, inhumane, and degrading treatment constitute 15% of the total petitions and stand out as the highest number of complaints received. While arbitrary arrest, detention, and enforced disappearances constituted 10.6% of the overall petitions (Pulse Nigeria, 2019). All of these are further confirmations of the allegations of human rights violations in the Boko Haram conflict.

Commenting on the issue of enforced disappearances, one respondent from the male IDP peer group stated:

“I have also experienced it in this camp. So many people who knew nothing about Boko Haram were taken to prison, and only a few came back. We never heard anything about the whereabouts of the other people. This sort of action is unacceptable. You make a judgment without any substantive evidence” (Respondent 3, male IDPs peer group).

A report by the UN Office of the High Commissioner for Human Rights (OHCHR) in 2015 confirmed that men, especially the youths in the northeast, are faced not only with the danger of being recruited by Boko Haram but also of being arrested and detained unlawfully by the army, other security forces, and the Civilian JTF as suspects (Dietrich, 2015; OHCHR, 2015). Furthermore, some of the detainees lamented the terrible state of the detention facility and how they are being inhumanely treated by the army, resulting in an average of 5 deaths incidents daily in the cells. Other forms of degrading treatment in detention facilities include food and water deprivation (OHCHR, 2015).

According to the 2020 annual report of Amnesty International, the arbitrary arrest and detention of thousands of suspects linked to Boko Haram have continued without access to legal counsel or family members. The military also arrested children escaping Boko Haram strongholds and kept them in detention camps in the popular Giwa military barrack in Maiduguri, the Borno state capital, and another military base in Kainji, Niger state. The report added that a total of 602 suspects were freed and handed over to the Borno state government in June 2020 for resettlement after a long period of illegal detention (Amnesty International, 2020).

5.3 Violations of privacy, rape, and extortion.

Privacy is, and should continue to be, a fundamental dimension of living in a free, democratic society (National Research Council, 2008) and is clearly stated in Article 12 of the Universal Declaration of Human Rights (UDHR) that "No one shall be subjected to arbitrary interference with his privacy, family, home or correspondence, nor to attacks upon his honour and reputation. Everyone has the right to the protection of the law against such interference or attacks." Though these rights are meant to be always protected, some states see these rights as standing in the way of security, especially during conflicts or crises. As such, states often find it challenging to ensure both the security of lives as well as the protection of individual rights in such situations. This is rightly coined by Gross (2004), who argues that the genuine and conceivably most challenging test of any democratic government is dependent on its capability to find an appropriate balance between these two inseparable values that will avert the obligation of unnecessary limitations on individual freedoms (Gross, 2004).

In reaction to the increasing threat from terrorism, the U.S. stepped up its efforts to fight terrorism to strengthen the government's capability to thwart terrorist attacks before they happen. There are concerns, however, that such efforts may negatively impact counterterrorism programmes with respect to the privacy of U.S. citizens and the sufficiency of the protection of related civil rights. This is a result of how terrorists use civilians as a shield to orchestrate acts of terror, which in turn makes efforts to detect and counter their attacks before they are executed difficult, hence raising concerns about the impact such efforts may have on a democratically free society (National Research Council, 2008).

Privacy violations in the Boko Haram conflict are linked to, among other factors, the Nigerian military's lack of professionalism. An ex-officer of the Nigerian military supported this position and observed that:

“Sometimes, these conflicts are very complicated ahh... I mean complex in such a way that there are some operations that we carry out in which we must violate human rights. Do you understand? For example, due to lack of professionalism, i.e., If the soldiers are not professionals, they are bound to violate these laws” (Sgt. X).

Regarding the Nigerian military's unprofessionalism, Iheduru (2017) contends that the military's reputation became highly questionable eight years after the Boko Haram insurgency began due to embarrassing defeats it suffered in its counterterrorism and counterinsurgency operations against the sect in northeastern Nigeria. Their lack of professionalism was further exacerbated by allegations of human rights abuses and violations of the rules of engagement in armed conflicts. Despite their recent combat successes against the insurgents, public perception regarding their professionalism and capabilities has continued to decline in that the longstanding problem of corruption and embezzlement of funds deeply rooted in the Nigerian military persists (Iheduru, 2017).

Several other cases of harassment, intimidation, and violations of privacy committed by the Nigerian security forces in the counterinsurgency operations in Nigeria's northeast have been reported by many civilians. One of the common among these violations is the house-to-house searches, stop and search at military checkpoints and raids in worship and public buildings. In his comment on illegal searches in the counterterrorism operations in the northeast during our interview, senior personnel of the Department for State Security Service (DSS) disclosed that:

“Properties have been searched without acquiring search warrants, arrest warrants, and when suspects are being arrested, they are also often tortured” (Agent X).

In their 2015 report *When We Can't See the Enemy, Civilians Become the Enemy* The Centre for Civilians in Conflict noted that the situation is so bad that the military that is supposed to protect the people is, on the contrary, protecting the government from its people. Thus, a significant structural reform and the political drive to re-orient the military to a more professional and civilian-friendly institution is urgently needed. Narrating a teacher's experience in Yobe state from their fieldwork, the Centre's report reveals that military operations in the region have

threatened civilians and created fear and distrust among the locals due to harassment and disrespectful conduct of the military personnel. Regarding privacy violations, she added that they conducted house searches in her hometown without prior notification and harassed and abused people in their homes. Another account given by a 68-year-old woman from Michika, a local government area in Adamawa state, suggests that the military intrudes on people's privacy during house-to-house searches and sometimes doesn't care even if the residents are naked. Furthermore, this form of violation is also rampant in military security checkpoints across the northeast. An account given by one civilian in Gombe state suggests that military conduct at checkpoints is abusive and intimidating, including extortion and unfair treatment of minority groups.

The staff of the National Human Rights Commission (NHRC) gave a similar account of this alleged disregard for people's privacy by the Nigerian military when conducting house searches or raids on villages suspected of harbouring insurgents. In his statement, he narrated that:

“There was a guy; they were in their house, and then the security barged into their house and brought all the males outside, lay them on the ground, and terribly beat them. After they searched the house and found nothing, they took two of them and later brought them back again. So those two men came back with bruises and pain all over their bodies. They had to treat themselves for some time” (NHRC Staff).

Similarly, some of the affected communities' perception of the Nigerian military is rather devastating due to the extreme counterterrorism measures they use and their propensity to treat civilians as terrorists. A one-year investigation by The New Humanitarian gathered evidence from satellite pictures, images, videos, and numerous reports from local and international NGOs and security experts that support the several allegations of human rights abuse, including those committed recently in May 2023. In addition, more than thirty Bama residents interviewed by the organisation and VICE News reveal that military operations in the area in late 2022 have destroyed villages and farmlands and forced many into exile (The New Humanitarian, 2023). Even international NGOs have had their share of unauthorised and forceful military raids and searches in the northeast in the past. For instance, the Nigerian military forcefully raided the U.N. office in Maiduguri for nearly four hours, and the incident was confirmed by the military authorities, who stated that they suspected the late Boko Haram leader was hiding in the office. A 2020 Amnesty International report also reveals that the Nigerian military didn't just raid and

burn villages but, on several occasions, killed older people left behind in Boko Haram-controlled villages (Ojigho, 2020).

5.3.3 Sexual abuse

Aside from privacy violations, rape and the extortion of IDPs are among some of the violations observed by one of the senior legislators of the Nigerian House of Representatives, which supports the 2015 Human Rights Watch report. According to this report, security forces and the civilian JTF have committed violence against women in their counterinsurgency operations in northeastern Nigeria. These allegations are not limited to the confines of Nigerian territory alone; they are also being perpetrated in neighbouring Chad, Cameroon, and Niger, where the multinational JTF operates. Also, several reports suggest that the military often preys on women and young girls in IDP camps and villages who have become vulnerable because they are cut off from their families and loved ones (HRW, 2016). In giving his opinion on the allegations of rape by the Nigerian military in the north-east, a legislator noted that:

“We have heard of cases where the Nigerian military was accused of raping young girls and innocent women, you know? Though I have heard that some of the officers were tried, to the best of my knowledge, none have been prosecuted as of yet. Some even go extorting because..., I don't know why. Unverified sources said that sometimes they are not paid their allowances, so sometimes they even extort.”
(Member B).

According to research by NOI Polls, 66% of 400 IDPs in Yobe, Adamawa, and Borno states admitted that women and teenage girls were sexually abused by camp officials (Polls, 2016). Worse still, the lack of adequate living essentials such as food, medicine, and clothing further compounds victims' vulnerability to such criminality. As such, these victims, largely widows and orphans, are often exposed to sexual abuse by security personnel, camp officials, and even the wider public (Polls, 2016).

While the issue of rape and other sexual abuses by the camp officials, and the various security personnel, including the military, are quite evident, none of the male or female IDPs I interviewed made mention of any sexually related abuses. This struck me as a surprise and begs the question as to why the respondents failed to mention any rape case or incident in their camps.

While remaining objective with my research, and as Becker (1967) rightly observed, when undertaking research work for whatever private reasons, we develop a deep sympathy for the people we are investigating and, as a result, fail to give a complete picture of the issue. Hence, our general assessment of the problem being examined becomes one-sided and whitewashed (Becker, 1967). However, the understanding of bias in research has evolved since 1967, and it has now become a contested and ambiguous concept, which in contrast to previous assumptions, can be a positive thing (Su et al., 2023; Montgomery et al., 2023; Stockinger, et al., 2023). However, to avoid a lopsided and opinionated analysis, I refrain from engaging any of the IDPs about any rape-related incidents during my fieldwork.

A report by Human Rights Watch supports my above propositions. According to the report, rape and sexually abused victims are often reluctant to seek medical care or psychological counselling out of fear and shame. In one of the research conducted by HRW in which 43 women were interviewed, only five admitted to receiving formal counselling after being sexually abused or raped (HRW, 2019). These highlighted abuses are a potential violation of the provisions of Article 2 Section (b) of the 1993 United Nations Declaration for the Elimination of Violence against Women, which prohibits any form of physical, sexual, and psychological violence, women trafficking, and sex slavery in any society, including sexual harassment, and intimidation in a workplace, in schools and elsewhere.

Furthermore, Article 4 section (a) of the Protocol to the African Charter on Human and Peoples' Rights on the Rights of Women in Africa (Maputo Protocol) also prohibits all forms of physical and psychological violence against women, such as unwanted or forced sex regardless of whether the violence is committed privately or publicly. Sexual abuse against women is also prohibited in Nigeria's Constitution. Section 358 of the Constitution of the Federal Republic of Nigeria prohibits all forms of forceful or violent sexual abuse against women, including sexual harassment, intimidation, or threat. The penalty for committing this crime in Nigeria is life imprisonment. However, public perception of this law is rather disappointing, and neither is there any confidence in the judiciary by the majority of the women population in Nigeria for the lack of enforcement of the law against rape and, by extension, the prosecution of offenders. This is largely due to the large volume of rape cases awaiting trial and the utter lack of interest from the

government in the ever-increasing cases of rape in Nigeria in recent times (Ezeilo, 2020; George, 2021; Ojigho, 2021; Gbadamosi, 2021).

From a global context, there is a long history of sexual abuses in war times, yet it was only after the outrageous atrocities perpetrated in the Rwandan genocide and the Bosnia and Herzegovina war were exposed to the world that this sort of war crime began to attract global concern (Marsh et al. 2006; Palmer et al., 1999). Several humanitarian policies on sexual and gender-related violence spiralled in the 1990s in conflict-ravaged areas (Palmer et al. 1999), including a resolution of the U.N. Security Council that recognised gender-related experiences of war as well as the significance of dealing with sexual violence in armed conflict (Barrow, 2010; Engle, 2005; Leatherman 2011; Scully 2009).

Rape is a grave violation of human rights and involves acts of violence, which impact the health of victims and have wide-ranging consequences. Sexual violence is also a war tool that can occur before, during, and after conflict and contradicts the values and generally accepted norms in a civilised society (Leatherman, 2011). Anholt (2016) contends that large-scale sexual violence persists in present-day conflicts despite many efforts in international politics to end it. A typical example of such conflict is the Islamic State (I.S.) war in Syria and Iraq, which attracted serious media attention given the magnitude of sexual violence committed by the group (Ahram, 2015; Berenson, 2014). Thus, sexual violence is a top issue of international debate, especially in top donor countries (Anholt, 2016).

In the interminable conflict in the northeast, a plethora of reports suggests rampant sexual abuses by the Nigerian military. These reports are often neglected or given little to no attention by the government. In an interview with The Centre for Civilians in Conflict, a Borno state university student explained that the military operation in the state caused more harm than good and that she once witnessed a rape incident involving a hawker at a military checkpoint in Maiduguri the Borno state capital but could not do anything to help and had to flee the scene as she was threatened by the soldiers (Dietrich, 2015). However, despite all this evidence from media reports and other accounts by civilians, it is commonplace for the government, especially the Nigerian military, to deny allegations of sexual abuse by the victims. In fact, the military has a habit of sweeping these allegations under the carpet and often covering them up under the guise of national security (Amnesty International, 2018). Even though Amnesty International is

criticised for being anti-government in some of their reports, the plethora of similar publications in the media and court cases in Nigeria have, to a greater extent, given these allegations' weight. A senior legislator in Nigeria's National Assembly confirmed this during my interview with him, where he stated:

“Every day, there are reports of human rights violations by security agencies all over the country, but they keep denying it. Even some of the allegations of human rights violations by the Nigerian army are true” (Member B).

One typical example of such denial was made in a letter in 2015 by the then defence spokesman Maj. Gen. Chris Olukolade, who stated that naming military personnel for alleged human rights abuses was equivalent to "blackmail" and that the statistics in the report were "spurious or manipulated" and the allegations were extremely biased. This was in reaction to Amnesty International's report in which 5 top military commanders were listed for alleged war crimes and four other senior officers for being reluctant to prevent the crimes from being committed (Childress, 2015).

Additionally, several similar cases exist that are usually not reported either by the victims or witnesses to this crime. In sharing her opinion on this, the Amnesty International staff commented:

“Ehm, there have been a lot of allegations of ehm violations of human rights committed by military officers in their quest to tackle the insurgency. Some of this is largely underreported because a lot of focus has been on Boko Haram crimes, and ehm whenever issues of military activities have led to wrongdoing and rape, they tend to be shut down in the media” (A.I. Staff).

However, sometimes, the government also accuses the opposition political party of blackmail, misinformation, and misleading the electorate for political gains. This was common during Goodluck Jonathan's administration when the opposition party, the All-Progressive Congress (APC), was accused of politicising the incident of the kidnapped Chibok girls by Boko Haram. This game of pointing fingers by the Nigerian military has done more harm than good in the government's counterterrorism efforts in the northeast. As a consequence, it has dented the Nigerian military's image and damaged public trust and confidence in their ability to protect and safeguard the lives and property of the citizenry in conflict and peace times. A response from the

Amnesty International staff suggests that unless the government address these injustices and impunity, public trust and confidence will continue to deteriorate when noted that:

"Justice needs to happen first. Ahm, a lot of things have happened that have led to people distrusting the government and its agencies. And whatever the government does will be clouded by those biases. But if people see that the government has apprehended a perpetrator, even if it is just one. Even better so, someone who is within their ranks. It will lead to more accessibility to people" (A.I. Staff).

This deteriorating public trust is one of the factors responsible for the setbacks being experienced by the Nigerian military and other security agencies in the area of intelligence gathering and community policing, which are all very crucial aspects of combating the Boko Haram insurgents in Nigeria.

5.4 Evidence and prevalence of human rights violation

There have been many incidences of human rights abuses by the Nigerian military throughout the Boko Haram conflict. The most common of these violations include illegal arrest and detention of suspects, torture, extrajudicial killings, rape, and degrading and inhumane treatment of suspects (Taiwo, 2018; Amnesty International, 2020; Human Rights Watch, 2022; Point Blank News, 2022). This is especially evident in the 2020 Amnesty International report, which reveals that apart from adult detainees, the Nigerian military also detained children for a prolonged time, during which they were beaten, tortured, and subjected to other forms of physical harm to extract information. Most often, these detentions are illegal, and detainees are usually not charged with any crime and are denied access to legal counsel or given a fair hearing before a court of law. The report further indicates that the detention facilities are inhabitable to humans in that the cells are overpopulated, extremely hot, and without good hygiene facilities. In addition, the children are mixed with adults and are forced to sleep sitting down with bad ventilation. They also urinate and defecate in the cells due to having just one toilet, which is obviously incommensurate with their population. Over 10,000 people are estimated to have died in detention in the conflict due to hunger and starvation, lack of medical care, and horrible living conditions, leading to outbreaks of diseases and infections (Amnesty International, 2020).

A retired military officer gave an elaborate explanation of how common human rights violations were when he was serving at the peak of the Boko Haram conflict explained that:

“To be very open with you, you see, before the start of Boko Haram, I will just say that most of the soldiers were primitive. We did not know most of these human rights laws. For instance, when we were serving in Sierra Leone during the Economic Community of West African States Monitoring Group (ECOMOG), all these human rights laws were not taught to us. We were even allowed to bring women to our tents. Officers would often ask what would make us happy. However, when the U.N. came, the concept of the United Nations exposed us to the knowledge of all these things” (Sgt. X).

The officer did not dispute the existence of human rights violations in the Boko Haram conflict. On the contrary, he affirmed that prior to the Boko Haram conflict, the majority of the officers were ignorant of human rights law and the principles of civil-military relations. In fact, he disclosed that during the peacekeeping mission of the Nigerian military in some African countries, some of the officers behaved irresponsibly until the later involvement of the U.N. forces. This lack of knowledge of human rights laws and the rules of engagement during combat is responsible for the rather unconventional counterterrorism approach of the Nigerian military in combating Boko Haram and the resultant human rights abuses that ensued.

5.4.1 Extrajudicial killings

Extrajudicial killings of civilians and public execution of Boko Haram members are also found to be rampant throughout the conflict. According to Callamard (2019), nearly 500 civilians in Duguri, Baga, and Bama towns were killed by the Multinational Joint Task Force (MJTF) between February 15th, 2012, and July 23rd, 2013. Also, over 200 civilians were killed and more than 150 injured as a result of an aerial bombing of the Rann IDP camp by the Nigerian Airforce during a humanitarian distribution of food in January 2015, in which three humanitarian workers also died. The military was also reported to have executed 640 recaptured escapees from Giwa barracks in March 2014, and recently, in March 2018, another 28 suspects were allegedly shot by the Nigerian military and dumped at a mortuary with bullet wounds after a screening at one of the camps in Bama town (Callamard, 2019).

In the 2014 Frontline report, *Hunting Boko Haram*, evidence of other forms of human rights violations was further revealed. In a collection of recorded video clips by eyewitnesses and testimonies of atrocities meted out by the Nigerian military and the Civilian Joint Task Force (CJTF), the report shows that around 1,200 men, including children, were executed. A death toll of 100 is sometimes recorded in a day, and the corpses were usually dumped outside the villages. There were instances where the military poisoned the poorly ventilated detention cells with fumigation chemicals, and the number of fatalities was never reported or probed (Childress, 2015).

In addition, an investigation by Reuters reveals one of the largest and most horrible extrajudicial killings and war crimes yet in Nigeria's history. The investigation, which started in 2013, exposed a secret mass abortion project targeting thousands of women settled in Giwa Barracks who got impregnated during detention under Boko Haram. There was international condemnation after a second report from Reuters investigation further revealed that the Nigerian military also carried out targeted killings of children born by Boko Haram's rape victims. This discovery prompted the U.S. and U.K. governments and the United Nations to demand an inquiry by the Nigerian government on the allegations. However, the Nigerian military, just like in the past, initially denied the allegation, calling the report "evil" and distancing itself from the accusations. The Nigerian Defence Chief, however, later promised to cooperate with Nigeria's National Human Rights Commission's investigations committee (Lewis et al., 2022).

Following a directive from the presidency, The National Human Rights Commission launched a seven-member Special Panel of Inquiry on abuses by the Nigerian Military in February 2023 with a former Supreme Court judge as the chairman, a retired major general, a member of the Nigerian Bar Association, and an expert gynaecologist. Investigating Reuters' allegations of the Nigerian military's involvement in the mass abortion of women impregnated by Boko Haram for over ten years shall be the Panel's main agenda. A compilation of several witness accounts and narratives in Reuters' December 2022 report suggests that an estimated 10,000 abortions involving women and young girls were orchestrated by the Nigerian military (Dzirutwe, 2023).

Furthermore, soon after the commencement of the NHRC hearings on the Nigeria military's abortion scandal, two women confided in Reuters that they were among the abortion victims, disclosing that their pregnancies were removed without their consent. Their confession further

supports similar claims by thirty other women, military personnel and health officials involved in the program. In a recent interview with Reuters, two other victims also narrated that they had horrible experiences after being administered pills and injections by the officers of the Nigerian military that terminated their pregnancies at the military detention centre. One of the victims wants the world to know about her ordeal so that relevant human rights organisations may help stop the future reoccurrence of such violations. Reuters investigations also reveal that some of the victims are as young as 12 years old and were forced and intimidated at gunpoint to have their pregnancies removed. Additionally, data gathered from interviews with five health officials, nine military officers involved in the abortion programme, and information from military and hospital records form a major part of the Reuters report. In their accounts, some military officers claimed that their participation in the abortion programme was based on the conviction that the children may join the insurgents and fight the Nigerian government in the future. Both the military personnel and health officials interviewed by Reuters insisted on anonymity for fear of prosecution by the Nigerian military, but the two female victims, who are now outside Nigeria, allowed their names to be disclosed. While the investigation efforts of the NHRC in the abortion scandal, as evidenced in the establishment of a panel of inquiry, is a good development, the commission's inability to secure the prosecution of government elites in the past has not raised an iota of confidence among human rights advocates and academics on any positive outcome from their investigation (Levinson, 2023).

Apart from extrajudicial killings, other reports also suggest that the Nigerian military had destroyed villages it suspects of supporting Boko Haram on numerous occasions, regardless of whether they were once terrorised by the sect themselves.

One IDP narrated one of such incidences in her village:

“I experienced this back at home. They picked someone from (town’s name) to (town’s name), a nearby town tied up all through. People even say that the person is mentally ill. He was not a Boko Haram member, but because the military was given information that he was also a terrorist, they believed it. They beat him so badly that he died right in front of my house a day after he was released from detention. And that man was said to be innocent. So, what will you say about this kind of act?” (Respondent 2, female IDPs peer group).

The counterterrorism tactics of the Nigerian military, for the most part, constitute war crimes, including deliberate attacks on civilians, massacres, and the unnecessary and unprecedented displacement of civilians (Amnesty International, 2020). The U.S. State Department recently approved close to one billion dollars in April 2023 to support Nigeria's counterterrorism efforts in the northeast after Congress previously denied it on the grounds of human rights violations. Having seen the catastrophe caused by the insurgency in Nigeria's northeast, the U.S. and U.K. governments have committed to ending the conflict. However, the level of abuses and complacency of top military officials in the insurgency remains a threat to this commitment (Lewis et al., 2022).

5.4.2 Torture and interrogation of suspects

Torture is one of the common techniques used by security personnel and law enforcement officials to extract information from suspects, be they terrorists, criminals such as armed robbers, kidnappers, gang members, or drug cartels. Torture involves the infliction of extreme physical pain by an interrogator or public official to extract information or intimidate a defenceless, nonconsenting individual (Gold, 2016; Kamm, 2011; Skerker, 2010; Lauritzen, 2013). Torture is also used to break an individual's sensual and mental being to control the person's power (Gordon, 2014). This technique, called torture, is globally acknowledged as a monstrous and inhumane act that should not be condoned by both state and non-state actors, even in the most challenging of times, such as wars. According to Goodale (2013), torture in its own right is a monstrous crime that is in contradiction with civilised morals and goes beyond all boundaries (Goodale, 2013). The West has, since the 19th century, recognized torture as the ultimate adversary of humanitarian law and liberalism and the utmost danger to law and reason (Gross O., 2004). However, despite all these outright condemnations by liberal governments globally and the absolute prohibition of torture as contained in both the Universal Declaration of Human Rights Law (UDHR) and the European Charter on Human Rights (ECHR), its use in armed and non-armed conflicts in both liberal and non-liberal states have remained perverse, especially in counter-terrorism warfare.

More often than not, states tend to sweep all allegations of torture against their security operatives under the carpet or find excuses to justify their actions. These excuses are commonly

based on national security interests, which have remained a topic of debate in the field of terrorism and counterterrorism studies. For instance, in the US, there is legislation designed to enable the military to combat terrorism domestically and abroad, which are pro-torture and in conflict with civil liberties. According to Ratner (2006), the Military Commission Act of 2006 empowers the President to set up military courts for enemy fighters where confessions coerced through torture and other inhumane interrogation techniques are condoned. An aspect of the Act retroactively modified the War Crimes Act, effectively exempting political and military leaders and law enforcement agencies from legal prosecution for involvement in acts of torture, which was initially a war crime under US law (Ratner, 2006).

Before the 9/11 attack, US officials engaged in counter-insurgency operations (Phoenix Program) during the Cold War between the 1960s and 1980s not only tortured suspects and enemy combatants but also influenced their allies to indulge in the act (Andrade, 2006). However, since the 9/11 attack, torture and other degrading methods have become the most frequently used interrogation techniques by counter-terrorism agencies, especially the US military, both at home and abroad. In their 2014 report to the UN Committee Against Torture, The International Human Rights Clinic at Harvard Law School condemned the alleged torture program run by the US government, considering it worrisome and appalling. The report further suggests that the US military uses all forms of torture and other inhuman and degrading treatment on detainees in the Guantanamo Bay detention facility, including other similar detention facilities in 54 countries under the Bush administration. The report also faults the Obama administration for complacency in failing to bring the perpetrators to justice (The International Human Rights Clinic, 2014). Some of the most common forms of torture and inhumane and degrading treatment being used in Guantanamo Bay and other US detention facilities around the world include stress and duress, e.g., waterboarding, sleep deprivation, solitary confinement, suspension of suspects in awkward positions for a prolonged period, and other physical harm (Gellman, 2002).

Furthermore, after 9/11, the UK Government was not spared from allegations of human rights abuses. Notably, the UK was accused of allowing the rendition, abduction, and torture of terrorism suspects in their anti-terror campaigns. This is contained in the 2018 UK Government's Intelligence and Security Committee publication. Based on this report, the UN Committee on

Torture appealed to the UK Government to set up an independent panel of inquiry to investigate the allegations in May 2019. According to a UK human rights group, Freedom from Torture, the failure of the UK government to conduct this investigation during and beyond Theresa May's administration has dented the UK's image as a beacon of Justice and the rule of law in the international community (Freedom from Torture, 2022).

Just like the US and the UK, the Nigerian government has also had its share of challenges and criticism in terms of adherence and compliance to the provisions of the International Human Rights Law against torture since the start of the Boko Haram insurgency over a decade ago. The report of the UN Office of the High Commissioner on Human Rights Committee on Torture stated that the Nigerian military has had a history of torturing suspected Boko Haram members in their efforts to end the activities of the sect. The report further states that the counter-terrorism operations of the military have resulted in acts of violence and extrajudicial killings (OHCHR, 2021). Some of the common forms of torture used by the Nigerian military include the beating of suspects with gun butts/machetes/batons/sticks/electric cable, nail/teeth extractions, starvation, shootings, rape, sexual violence, suspension of detainees upside-down, and Tebay, which involves tying detainees' elbow behind their backs and suspending them on a stick (Amnesty International, 2021).

The response of a retired officer in the Nigerian military corroborates these allegations. He stated that:

“When officers capture a Boko Haram member or a suspect, they are very likely to torture them. But in most cases, the officers would hand them over to a specialist. We have officers in the Nigerian army who specialise in torture. They are well trained in all manners of torture techniques and can even extract information from suspects without necessarily torturing them” (Officer, X).

Besides confirming the acts of torture by the Nigerian military, the above response also reveals that some military officers are being given special torture training. This new revelation is an indication that there is a deliberate effort by the military to institutionalise torture as one of their interrogation techniques to force confessions from suspects. Another report by Amnesty International supports this claim. The report noted that the use of torture remained widespread and routine within Nigeria's police and military. Countless people were subjected to physical and psychological torture and other ill-treatment. Suspects in police and military custody across the

country have been subjected to torture, particularly in cases involving armed robbery and murder or terrorism-related cases (Amnesty International, 2015).

During my interview with both the male and female IDP peer groups in the Adamawa state IDP camp, some of the participants also attested to the allegations of torture by the Nigerian military. The majority of the male IDPs agreed that the torture of Boko Haram suspects is common in the conflict. According to them, when the Nigerian military captures any Boko Haram suspects, they usually subject them to torture. They further stated that most of the time, they tie and beat them until they confess to alleged membership in Boko Haram. Sometimes, they beat the suspects to death if they insist that they are not Boko Haram. This has scared many suspects to falsely confess and even give misleading intelligence just to avoid the gruesome pains of torture at the hands of military officers.

However, reflecting on my interview with the IDPs on the issue of torture, their responses were usually brief and short due to their lack of knowledge of the concept of torture. In this regard, language was part of the compounding factor in that there is no single word for torture in their native language. Nonetheless, after giving examples of different forms of torture, they were able to understand what torture is.

The inability of participants to give comprehensive responses almost made me question the quality and admissibility of the data. However, after applying the concept of ‘reflexivities of discomfort’ in a failed research as propounded by Pillow (2003: 187), i.e., “a positioning of reflexivity not as clarity, honesty, or humility, but as practices of confounding disruptions – at times even a failure of our language and practices” (Pillow, 2003: 192), and after a deep and objective reflection on the data, I concluded that what matters is not the volume or the length of the data but the major contribution to knowledge that comes with it especially, in this research, and as Miles and Hubberman (1994) rightly put it, generating meaning from data is the main goal of any research. Therefore, having revisited my interviews with the IDPs, I had the opportunity to reflect on what transpired and to consider data instead of spoken word (Mazzei, 2003; St. Pierre, 1997). This is not only because their responses confirm the allegations of human rights abuses by the Nigerian military being investigated in this study but also because they provide primary data, which is currently lacking in the existing literature on the Boko Haram conflict from original research such as this.

Another contributing factor to the high rate of torture in the Boko Haram conflict is the lack of commitment by the Nigerian Government to create enforceable laws against torture. According to the DFAT country information report on Nigeria, even though Nigeria's constitution prohibits acts of torture, as of 2017, torture is yet to be criminalised under the constitution. Empirical data generated from a study by Bukar (2021) also confirm this proposition. The study highlighted three major issues that often impede the effective enforcement of international human rights law in the Boko Haram conflict, which include a lack of commitment by the government, unprofessional and poorly trained security personnel, and a weak judicial system.

Under the Nigerian constitution, terrorism is a federal offence and provides for the trial of terror suspects under the Office of the Attorney General. However, in 2017, only 205 out of the 2,300 suspects secretly tried were prosecuted. And worse still, they were only prosecuted for minor offences relating to associating with or aiding Boko Haram. Some reports have even shown that Boko Haram members that have been convicted since the conflict began in 2009 are not up to 400. The Attorney General of the Federation (AGF) had in May 2021 stated that 400 names of Boko Haram sponsors and an additional 800 suspects would be published and prosecuted, but nothing close to that has been done since the announcement (Irede, 2021).

These factors have hindered the smooth enforcement of human rights law and compliance with the rules of engagement during conflict (Bukar, 2021). This lack of political will on the side of the government, particularly the Nigerian military, is further amplified in the response given by an official of Nigeria's National Human Rights Commission (NHRC) who stated that:

“Human rights violation, especially torture, is a common interrogation technique used by the Nigerian military before and throughout the Boko Haram conflict. There are many victims out there who have had terrible experiences at the hands of the military, but nothing has been done to arrest or try the officers responsible in a court of law. We often see the military claiming to have certain court-martial numbers of military personnel for torture-related offences, but that is only in the media. There is no proof or evidence that the officers are indeed serving any prison time. And there are rumours that the military used to secretly persuade victims or compensate them to withdraw allegations against them” (NHRC Staff 1).

Furthermore, inhumane treatment of suspects, often leading to deaths in detention, killings, and forced disappearances, is also prevalent in the counter-insurgency operations of the Nigerian military in the northeast. The examination report published by the International Criminal Court

identifies two potential incidences of war crimes in the counter-insurgency operations committed by the Nigerian military in the Boko Haram conflict (Jimoh, 2015).

The use of torture in the Boko Haram conflict, to a greater extent, has already been established. The overarching question now is the frequency at which they are being committed. In his response to this question, the personnel of the DSS noted that:

“Yes, torture is being used by security agencies in the Boko Haram conflict. They indulged in this act day in and day out. But whenever they are reported or petitioned, they say it is a lie or give flimsy excuses. However, because I am not in the military, I cannot outrightly say that I know the extent to which torture is being used. I speak based on what I have read and seen in the media, and from pockets of complaints and petitions by some of the victims on social media” (Agent X).

Some media reports support the above statement. For instance, the New York Times report in 2015 suggests that the Nigerian government has a history of defending the conduct of the Nigerian military during interviews (The New York Times, 2015). The agent further asserts that the military always finds a way to dodge these allegations by suppressing the truth to protect its public image. Responding to this allegation, a staff of Amnesty International also shared a similar view and suggested that:

“There have been a lot of allegations of violations of human rights committed by military officers in their quest to tackle the insurgency. Some of this is largely underreported because a lot of focus has been on Boko Haram crimes, and whenever issues of military activities that have led to wrongdoing and rape are reported, they tend to be shut down in the media” (A.I Staff).

Deducting from the statement above, though there is a widespread outcry of human rights violations committed by the Nigerian military, much emphasis is being given to the crimes committed by the insurgents, but whenever any allegation of human rights violations by the Nigerian military is reported, the government often prohibit or ban the broadcasting of such information by both the media and human rights organisations. For instance, when Amnesty International reported the killing of over 150 pro-Biafrans by the Nigerian Army between August 2015 and 2016, the Army denied the allegations, stating that it was a plot to tarnish its image. In addition, when Human Rights Watch published another report which revealed that the Nigerian Army killed 300 Shiite members in December 2015, the Nigerian Army again denied these allegations despite the compelling evidence circulating on social media at that time. The same

was the case when the Nigerian military massacred several civilians during the end of the SARS protest in October 2021. As these violations continue, the government's reluctance to create enforceable laws to check law enforcement agencies, particularly the military, remains unchanged. This postulation is supported by the 2015 annual report of Amnesty International, which reveals that “In the past decade, at least five presidential committees and working groups on reforming the criminal justice system have been set up. However, the majority of their recommendations, including the ban on torture, had not been implemented by the end of 2015” (Amnesty International, 2015).

Taiwo (2018) also contends that the high rate at which international human rights laws, especially the rules of engagement in combat pertinent to the counter-insurgency operations in the Boko Haram conflict, are being truncated is very worrisome given the level of impunity with which they are committed (Taiwo, 2018). It is, therefore, appropriate to state that notwithstanding Nigeria's commitment to international human rights law, it is highly doubtful whether the Boko Haram violent attacks and, worst still, the counter-attacks of the Nigerian military conform with the provisions of the law in conflict times (Didymus, 2013).

5.5 When it is an issue of life and death, torture is inevitable

Sometimes, rather than outright denial, security forces such as the police and the military give justifications when accused of committing acts of torture. Most often, these justifications are based on national security concerns or the necessity to protect life and property. This issue is one of the most debated in counter-terrorism studies and presents a big conundrum in the checks and balances of the excesses of states in the “war on terror”. This is challenging because it is the fundamental responsibility of the state to safeguard both its citizens and territorial boundaries from both external and internal threats such as terrorism and sometimes, to achieve this, desperate measures must be taken.

However, the Universal Declaration of Human Rights (UDHR) declared an absolute prohibition of torture. The question now is, at what point can a breach of human rights law be deemed legitimate, and in what circumstance or situation can torture be justified? In responding to the

question of whether torture can be justified under certain conditions, a retired Nigerian military officer narrated that:

“If this torture can bring out something positive like saving lives, I think it is reasonable. But if this torture does not bring out an outcome that will save lives, I think it is not justifiable. In practice, I will say no. Let me be sincere with you. In the Geneva Convention, the right of the individual against torture is very strict. But in a situation that requires an urgent response, the use of torture may be resorted to. Even though it is illegal, some circumstances may warrant that, depending on the urgency. But generally, it is not a good approach. But when you don’t have the luxury of time, especially when it is an issue of life and death, torture is inevitable. But if it is not an emergency, it is not advisable to resort to torture” (Sgt. X).

Here, the retired officer acknowledges that torture in any form is prohibited under the provisions of the Geneva Convention. Nonetheless, he suggests that torture is justifiable only when it will result in saving lives and in an emergency where there is no other available option. I am unsurprised by this view, given that it is coming from a military officer. This is because security personnel, more often than not, tend to use security interests to trade off human rights obligations. This view has its roots in the realist school of thought where it is argued that sometimes the greater good of the larger society outweighs that of a few individuals. What this entails is that if torturing one or few individuals will help save many lives, then torture is justifiable, especially in the face of imminent danger, such as in the ‘ticking bomb’ scenario advanced by Dershowitz (2002).

However, what I found fascinating and surprising is the responses of the female IDPs, which appear to support the realist point of view. All the female IDPs agreed that:

“Torture is justifiable if it will help trace Boko Haram members and their hideouts so long as it does not result in their death” (Female IDPs peer group).

Ordinarily, I expected their responses to contrast with that of the officer (who in this research is the alleged violator) and they, the IDPs, the victims of these violations. This has made me reflect on my own bias as a researcher and has helped shape my views and expectations on some of the issues under investigation in this research, i.e., “how does who I am, who I have been, who I think I am, and how I feel affect data collection and analysis” (Pillow, 2003:176). One of the female respondents went further to support the introduction of torture warrants for the interrogation of suspects by recounting an event she witnessed during a military operation in her

hometown. She recollected that at the conflict's peak, many Fulani people were captured by the military roaming about in Boko Haram-controlled areas. Some of them used to reveal the whereabouts of the terrorists after being detained and tortured for a few days. Most of them would never confess unless they were tortured. So, some of them will only speak out if they are subjected to painful treatment.

In contrast, the male IDPs argued that most of the people who suffered torture at the hands of the military are not the real Boko Haram. They further suggest that the victims are often innocent civilians who had no involvement whatsoever in the activities of the group and added that their rights are simply violated for no good reason. Also, the staff of Amnesty International condemns any form of justification for the use of torture. In her statement during our interview, the staff noted that:

“Under international law, torture is never justified under any circumstances. It is the most harmful and degrading of treatments, and there is no guarantee that if you torture the person, you will get the information you need on time and can stop the act from happening. Also, torture actually takes something from the person that tortures. You lose a bit of your humanity. Because you have treated someone in a more inhumane manner, and that was why I think the drafters of the international covenant took into consideration when they said, this is one of the rights you cannot derogate from” (A.I Staff).

Here, the respondent disagrees with any justification that may warrant the use of torture. This is because there are no assurances that torture will always produce a positive outcome or generate the information that will help stop an attack from happening or save lives and property. In addition, the respondent cautioned that due to the cruel nature of torture, whenever a man tortures another man, he loses a part of his humanity, too. Conversely, a staff of the National Human Rights Commission pointed out that:

“Torture does not ultimately generate good and reliable information. As such, I see no reason why it should be used during an interrogation. There are many other ways of getting information from suspects without necessarily resorting to torture. All this talk about justifications is just excuses and another way of covering up the evil called torture. My stand on this is that there is no circumstance in which torture is acceptable or justified” (NHRC Staff 1).

5.5.1 Torture: a waning technique

One of the most controversial debates on torture in the field of security studies, particularly counterterrorism, goes beyond the question of why it is being widely used by security agencies to how effective and reliable the technique is in intelligence gathering. This is rightly observed by Levinson (2004), who postulates that there is no existing proof to indicate that torture is a reliable way of extracting information. Whereas the effectiveness of coercive interrogation is indeed surrounded by uncertainties, its reliability, however, cannot be ascertained. What is required, instead, is the discourse on evidence to understand its efficacy (Levinson, 2004).

From the data analysed in the preceding section, the use of torture by the Nigerian military has already been established. However, that is not enough. There is a need to further understand the rationale behind its use and whether it is effective and reliable in terms of information and intelligence gathering in the context of the Boko Haram conflict. To achieve this, the respondents were engaged to share their opinions based on their experiences and knowledge throughout the conflict.

According to Human Rights First, a US human rights organisation, torture is a demonstration of primitive instincts to degrade, suppress, and dehumanise persons adjudged to be a threat to the safety of an individual or the larger society. It also suggests that torture is not a reliable method for sourcing precise, timely, and complete intelligence. This claim, according to Human Rights First, is supported by relevant research in the behavioural sciences and other accessible evidence to the public (Human Rights First, 2014).

Expressing his opinion on the effectiveness of torture, personnel of the Nigerian DSS noted that:

“In the past, yes, but now, new ways have been introduced. For example, interviews and persuasion. Most interrogation rooms are now bugged with cameras. Sometimes, when you engage a suspect in a conversation, it may result in getting a confession. However, this method is a gradual process, and it is effective only when a suspect becomes comfortable with the investigator and eventually begins to open up. Therefore, my overall opinion on torture is that it is not only inhumane, but it also does not always yield the expected result” (Agent X).

According to the DSS officer, torture is an outdated technique and should not be used in this present day since there are new conventional interrogation techniques such as persuasion, which

are more productive and effective compared to torture. He, however, noted that the techniques are slow in terms of getting the desired information and require a lot of investigative resources. The 2017 research findings of the United Nations Human Rights Office of the High Commissioner (OHCHR) also correspond with this opinion. The findings reveal that torture is not only ineffective, but it also forces false confessions from victims just to end the pain they are subjected to (OHCHR, 2017). Similarly, according to a declassified summary of the CIA's torture report, there was never a time when coercive interrogation methods provided intelligence of an impending threat. Instead, the CIA's memo shows that detainees who provided credible intelligence in their black sites did so without being subjected to any form of coercive interrogation. On the contrary, most of the detainees who were tortured gave concocted information, leading to misleading intelligence on serious terrorism threats (Epstein, 2022).

A retired officer of the Nigerian military also shared his opinion and narrated a torture experience he had while in service. According to him:

“Torture is not an effective interrogation technique. Although, in some cases, I have seen it work, in most cases, it ends in disappointment and a waste of time. But let me also tell you, there was a Boko Haram suspect who was tortured during one interrogation, and in his confessions, he gave out some information which the military later found to be all false. When they came back and asked the man why he gave false information, the man said it was because he just wanted to end the torture. Do you see? So, you may torture a suspect, and out of pain, he will end up giving false and misleading information. So, it is not even advisable to torture” (Sgt. X).

The retired officer confirmed that though torture on rare occasions produces information, in most cases, the information is often false and unreliable, and this is because suspects tend to confess anything when the pains of torture become too unbearable for them. This view is popular amongst human rights organisations all over the world. For instance, Human Rights First, a US-based human rights group, affirms that the use of physical or psychological force can compel a suspect to confess anything to end the pain of torture during interrogation. Also, he added that the challenge is not forcing suspects to talk during interrogation but instead getting accurate and reliable intelligence. According to the group, history has shown that forceful interrogation has yielded results only in support of propaganda crusades where small pockets of truth are overshadowed by lies and baseless allegations (Human Rights First, 2014).

The Amnesty International staff further narrated:

“If torture had been an effective and reliable interrogation technique in information and intelligence gathering in the Boko Haram conflict, we would not have been where we are. Because they have been torturing people since 2009 and to date, the conflict persists” (AI staff).

In this respondent’s opinion, the ineffectiveness of torture is evident in the deficit of intelligence required to end the Boko Haram conflict for more than a decade despite the high rate at which the Nigerian military and other relevant security agencies used it. Also, if torture had been effective, the information and intelligence generated from it would have, to a greater extent, helped end the war by now. In addition, it is also illegal to force a suspect to confess to any crime, and if the victim is given a fair hearing in a court of law, the security institution involved would be found culpable.

5.3.1 Data mining and security surveillance

The mining of personal data is among some of the most controversial violations of individuals' privacy in the US and UK. According to DeRosa (2004), the term data mining has a rather narrow meaning: it is a process that involves the use of algorithms to detect prognostic patterns in data sets (DeRosa, 2004). Security agencies, particularly given the present emphasis on terrorism, continuously struggle to cope with information overload and the lack of innovative, computerised techniques for analysing criminal and terrorism activities efficiently. As such, the use of data mining in the context of law enforcement and intelligence analysis, known as Investigative Data Mining (IDM), is the key to solving this problem. This technique involves "the organisation, sorting, visualisation, determining associations and predicting criminal behaviour in terrorist networks to destabilise them." IDM is mainly focused on the identification of key actors, network attributes, crucial links, smaller groups, and roles to explain fundamental questions regarding the structures of terrorist organisations (Shaik et al.).

Furthermore, data mining is increasingly becoming central in the processes of decision-making and, more broadly, in the extraction of secret information from large data sets. Though it does not necessarily contain the original data, it might be exploited to gather the information contained in the primary data, which may potentially infringe on the privacy of the individual or

entity (Ciriani et al. 2008). The issue of individuals' privacy has recently attracted debate among civil liberty unions, counterterrorism experts, and human rights activists. The debates revolve around information gathering and mining, surveillance activities, and the examination of email messages and phone conversations and their potential threats to individuals' privacy and civil liberties (Thuraisingham, 2002).

Data mining intrudes on an individual's privacy in that it allows law enforcement agencies access to people's phone numbers, call records, emails, and airline passenger records. According to Kantarcioglu (2008), data mining technology was born out of the need to identify patterns and trends from large data sets, and while it generally seeks to produce holistic models and not to study specific individuals, the integrated warehouse of this process poses concrete privacy concerns. When integrated, even less sensitive data would ultimately become highly sensitive, and the tendency for abuse increases when stored in a single database (Kantarcioglu, 2008).

Terrorism prevention and investigation security agencies are increasingly becoming interested in information technology to access and monitor communications provided by public and private communication companies to thwart, investigate, and prosecute serious crimes such as terrorism. One such example is the use of security surveillance in detecting and countering terrorist activities. Gross (2004) explains that visual surveillance involves mounting visual cameras in public places such as airports, train stations, sports complexes, banks, bus stops, and residences to help monitor potential terrorist activities, identify collaborators and security threats or gather intelligence to prevent future terrorist attacks. Recently, high-risk surveillance technologies have been increasingly used in counterterrorism by both state and non-state actors without any recourse to its consequences on human rights. The U.N. Special Rapporteur on human rights, Fionnuala Ní Aoláin, in her report to the 52nd Human Rights Council's session, cautions against the alarming rate at which intrusive technologies such as artificial intelligence (A.I.), drones, and biometrics are used in the global counterterrorism campaign. Exceptional excuses for the temporary use of sophisticated surveillance technologies in low-level counterterrorism operations are often normalised, which in turn impact individuals' rights to freedom of movement, expression, peaceful assembly, and private life. The Special Rapporteur further noted the worrisome level in the domestication of drones and the misuse of spyware on civil society bodies, journalists and human rights activists in many countries and emphasised the need for the

effective regulation of surveillance technology companies by states, else privacy violations will worsen (OHCHR, 2023).

There is also a growing privacy concern regarding how some security and counterterrorism agencies collect large amounts of individuals' data from the internet and telephone in the form of metadata during counterterrorism operations. The Internet Protocol address linked to a computer, a list of websites visited by a person, and an individual's call records are all examples of metadata (Council of Europe, 2015a; 2015b). The use of metadata in counterterrorism is sometimes justified, given that the causes of terrorism are connected to psychological and sociological tendencies and can help identify terrorist networks (Taylor, 2016) and trace terrorist recruiters and new recruits. Also, metadata helps detect symbols used by propaganda and radical groups and locate and monitor terrorist collaborators and supporters. In addition, metadata can also help in understanding the possible triggers of social conflict and drivers of violent extremism through the collection of information on an individual's internet activities, which can be used by intelligence and security agencies as an all-encompassing counterterrorism tactic through the involvement of local communities (UNODC, 2018). Yet, regardless of all its advantages, metadata is viewed as too invasive, and a third-quarter of U.S. citizens in a 2017 poll opposed its use by intelligence agencies in counterterrorism operations (Ruvic, 2017).

Similarly, privacy issues associated with metadata have become a serious concern among civil societies and human rights advocates regarding how metadata is collected, the information used, and how states can be held accountable (UNODC, 2018). Moreover, it is difficult to monitor data movement due to its fluid nature (Lyon, 2016) and how states with weak data protection laws share information with ally countries (Council of Europe, 2015b). While there is much benefit in intelligence gathering for intelligence bodies, the Council of Europe is sceptical of metadata's effectiveness in counterterrorism. Similar privacy concerns regarding the negative impact of mass data surveillance, like metadata, have been expressed by the U.N. urging states to ensure that individuals' data are protected online and offline through legislative reforms on communications surveillance and personal data protection policy. The 2017 U.N. Human Rights Council advised states to comply with international human rights practices and put stringent laws in place to prosecute violators (UNODC, 2018).

In addition, electronic wiretapping is also used by security agencies in intelligence and information gathering to track terrorist activities. This can also be done in person by surveillance officers during counterterrorism operations. Atkinson (2005) asserts that this technique is used to gather essential information undetected. The process involves connecting to a wire or other conductor used in transmitting messages. The wire is usually a telephone line, a CCTV camera, a local area network, or an alarm system (Atkinson, 2005). Wiretapping and other intrusive counterterrorism measures became widespread after the enactment of the Patriot Act of 2001 by the U.S. government soon after the 9/11 attack.

So far, the four counterterrorism measures that are found to intrude on the privacy of civilians are more common in the U.S., the U.K., and the rest of Europe. Though these technologies, such as surveillance cameras, are also used in some African countries like South Africa (Duncan, 2018), the most common forms of privacy-violating surveillance tactics in Nigeria's counterterrorism, as observed by Lawal (2015), include tapping phone calls, internet surveillance, and the illegal house-to-house search including offices, hotels, and worship places, which are often without a search warrant (Lawal, 2015). Most prevalent in the Boko Haram conflict-stricken region is the house-to-house search and stop-and-search at military and police checkpoints on the highways and during military raids. Responding to these allegations, a senior legislature in the Nigerian National Assembly disclosed that:

"Concerning the discharge of duties of the..., what do you call them? The security agencies, I think, in the process of executing their operations, several violations have occurred, such as setting up checkpoints on the highways and how they intrude into people's privacy and also infringe on people's rights of movement and a lot of other forms of violations" (Member A).

Although given the threat terrorism presents, one cannot but concur that counterterrorism is not only a noble cause and necessity but a state's major obligation to its citizens; it is also unwise to lose consciousness of the responsibility of states to create innovative approaches to regulate the development, use and transfer of high-risk surveillance technologies to ensure adherence to human rights standards stipulated in the European Convention on Human rights (Council of Europe, 2023).

Conclusion

The need for the protection of civilians is one, if not the most contentious, topic of debate in almost every violent conflict all over the world. This is because even the most democratic of governments fall short of observing the very democratic values and tenets they stand and advocate for, with human rights and individual freedom at the forefront. This is even more challenging in armed conflicts such as terrorism and insurgency in that states often resort to the use of force as the major and, in most cases, the only counterterrorism strategy. The Boko Haram conflict in northeast Nigeria is a typical example of such conflict, and ever since the start of the conflict, many allegations of human rights abuses have been levied against the government's security forces both locally and internationally. The main discussion of this chapter covered some of the major and most prevalent forms of violations in the Boko Haram conflict. This includes allegations of illegal and prolonged detention of suspects, the use of inhumane and degrading interrogation techniques such as torture and its effectiveness, violations of individual privacy, and rape. The proceeding analysis chapter will address other major areas of this research relating to the effectiveness of the use of military force in the Boko Haram conflict and the wider international context, alternative counterterrorism strategies such as dialogue and community policing, and the respect for and protection of individual rights and liberties in armed conflicts.

CHAPTER SIX (6)

A HUMAN RIGHTS APPROACH TO COUNTERTERRORISM IN NIGERIA

6.0 Introduction

Conventionally, the idea of security in the social sciences has been understood in terms of socio-political integration, i.e., the nexus between a community and a public security provider. In the West, where the Western political ideology is predominant, this nexus has been interpreted to be between the citizenry, state, and the legally recognised security body. From the standpoint of a social contract as a mutual security agreement between the state and society, security is the state's responsibility for the public good of society (Hobbes, 2004). The capability of the state to secure the nation is what gives it legitimacy (Locke, 1689).

This chapter, therefore, employs a human rights-centred approach to counterterrorism for a greater understanding of the multifaceted nature of human rights abuses and how effective this approach is compared to the coercive use of military force in the Boko Haram conflict. The analysis will examine some of the contentious issues associated with the use of military force and the protection and respect for individual rights and liberties during military operations throughout the conflict. The chapter will also analyse data on the various counterterrorism strategies and interventions that will help address the failure of the over-relied militaristic approach by the Nigerian government in the Boko Haram conflict.

6.1 Military force and counterterrorism: a strategic failure

After the September 11, 2001, attacks, the GWOT came short of the common characteristics that explain, validate, and limit the act of war. The enemy disguises amongst the civilians (just as in the case of Boko Haram) to carry out attacks against the state, including civilians. In this type of conflict, the conventional concept of enemy combatant is not applicable in that the terrorist's enemies are largely non-combatants and citizens of all states. Also, with terrorism, the battlefield does not have an exact identifiable location. As such, the defeat of terrorist organisations is

difficult to conceptualise, and hence, how to predict the end of such conflict. These uncertainties regarding how or when the conflict will end constitute a serious debate on the suitability of orthodox military powers to combat the enemy (Goldsmith, 2005).

Immediately after the 9/11 attacks, the US government launched its GWOT to track, hunt, and end al-Qaeda and similar terrorist organisations wherever they exist in the world (Shanker, 2005; Wallace, 2021). However, it is pertinent to note that not all its military counterterrorism operations were conducted on US soil. They were all military expeditions to foreign lands such as Afghanistan, Iraq, and Syria. For instance, the invasion of Afghanistan, which lasted for 20 years with over 1 trillion US dollars spent, and the resultant death of over 2,300 US soldiers ended in what Todd (2021) called a “strategic failure” (Greentree, 2021).

The decision to withdraw all US and allied troops by President Biden and the almost immediate takeover of the Afghan government by the Taliban has been widely seen as a failed end to the occupation and a big blow to the US-led GWOT campaign, and as admitted by General Mark Milley, the chairman of the Joint Chiefs of Staff and the nation's top-ranking military officer, the outcome of the war is a strategic failure and the enemy is in control of Kabul (Seldin, 2021). This is where the question of the effectiveness of the use of military force in counterterrorism comes into play.

The use of military force in the conduct of the GWOT has gained acceptance, especially by countries that are grappling with domestic terrorism and insurgencies, such as in the case of Iraq and Syria (Tesón, 2016). Just like these countries, Nigeria is also indifferent in its approach to the Boko Haram insurgency (Oriola, 2021). According to Jerome (2015), the major response to Boko Haram by the Nigerian government is the deployment of the Joint Task Force (JTF), which is a combination of the armed forces, State Security Services, and the Police with a unified command structure (Jerome, 2015). The JTF's operations have been relatively oppressive, with reliance on military force to kill and arrest Boko Haram members (Waterman, 2014). During my interview, the retired military officer confirmed this and stated:

“From the beginning of the conflict, the main strategy of the Nigerian government has always been Military force. The government has not been negotiating or engaging Boko Haram in dialogue” (Sgt. X).

From the opinion of the retired officer, from the onset, the use of military force appears to be the ultimate solution to ending the Boko Haram insurgency in the northeast from the viewpoint of the Nigerian government. According to Thurston (2017), after the extrajudicial execution of Ahmad Yusuf, the first leader of the group, in 2009, the Nigerian government and its security forces thought they had defeated Boko Haram (Thurston, 2017); however, the group re-surfaced in 2010 with Abubakar Shekau as its new leader. Using guerrilla warfare, Boko Haram, under a new leadership, began launching random attacks across the length and breadth of the northeast (International Crisis Group, 2014). This tactic steadily became their main combat strategy, leaving the Nigerian government and the security agencies clueless and handicapped on how to fight back. As Akali (2018) rightly observed, Boko Haram harnessed several benefits of guerrilla warfare and made covert operations its main resistance against government forces between 2011 and 2014. Even after switching its tactics to overt operations for territorial annexation, the covert front of Boko Haram was still an ever-present and formidable threat (Akali, 2018).

6.2 The state vs human rights

Soon after the emergence of the Universal Declaration of Human Rights (UDHR), human rights as a concept gradually started to reach different parts of the world. From the public struggles for the mass acceptance and safeguarding of human rights down to the local areas, people's lives gradually improved. The rule of law almost took precedence above the nation-state, and many years later, the international human rights system gradually became fully established with the corresponding rapid emergence of regional and international human rights monitoring mechanisms. Although the United Nations pioneered the project for decades (Moyn, 2010), it was not until the first human rights treaties were adopted in the mid-1960s that the processes for monitoring states' human rights obligations were established. However, only after a decade did these processes start functioning after the treaties were enforced. In addition, many international bodies were formed to serve as ombudsmen and advocates of human rights in general and rights-based programmes.

Whereas this change in some countries was rapid and fast compared to others, the democratic system of government experienced unprecedented acceptance for the latter half of the twentieth century (Fukuyama, 2015). The shift towards democracy was, for the most part, not only pushed

by the resilience of human rights advocates for the people in these reforming states but also by promoting this system of government by the UN and its strongest Member States at the international level. The notion that human rights would bring stability and peace to the international system, as advanced by liberal states, made it more popular (Doyle, 2011). As such, at its early development stage, human rights constituted liberal democracy's core values and defined their relationship with other sovereignties and institutions in the global arena (Fukuyama, 2015).

However, the interdependency of liberal governments and human rights has steadily been wearing down in recent times. Human rights in most liberal democracies are now perceived and adjudged to constitute hindrances on the policies and programmes of democratically elected entities of governments and in opposition to fundamental liberal principles. National security, especially with regard to terrorism, is at the crux of this transformation. Also, human rights and security are not usually known to be two competing values or in conflict. As the human rights concept advanced, the responsibility of states to safeguard human rights further expanded to include the protection of individuals from alien or foreign entities, including terrorist groups (Nolan, 2009).

Therefore, national security requirements are, to an extent, a portrayal of states' obligation to human rights. Hence, the conflict between a state's national security interest and human rights obligation comes to bear only when certain states use extreme measures to the extent that existing human rights norms and standards are encroached upon for national security preferences. Since the 9/11 attacks in 2001, counterterrorism rhetoric has been used to undermine human rights in the US and the rest of the world. Ever since, the UN's efforts to establish universal human rights norms have suffered a serious setback due to state security concerns, usually to the detriment of human rights (Gilmore, 2018). Even though states can sometimes limit certain rights for their citizens' security, the UN has been resilient in reminding them to do that within human rights provisions and the principles of the rule of law and hold those in power accountable (UN, 2005a).

However, despite the UN's efforts, many states have persistently employed non-human rights-compliant security approaches. This is common even in leading democracies like the US, attracting widespread scepticism on their commitments to human rights. As Freedom House

(2019) observed, the rule of law in the US is on the decline, and its immigration and asylum policies and programs are discriminatory and undermine immigrants' rights. The situation is the same in many other democracies: highly questionable electoral processes and authoritarian rule in Venezuela; stringent restrictions and often intrusive surveillance on social media, harsh tax policies, oppression of political oppositions in Uganda (Freedom House, 2019); the lack of adequate checks and abuse of power by the executive arm of government, resulting in the excessive control over the judiciary in Turkey; legal and constitutional-related issues that undermine judicial powers, oppression of civil society organisations, and restrictions on media freedom in Hungary (HRW, 2019).

Guaranteeing human rights during armed conflict has always been challenging, especially for state actors. This is because, according to Gaggioli (2013), counterinsurgency operations, at times, take place outside the battlefield, where battle lines are not drawn or defined, and the use of force may be justifiable in terms of lessening casualties among the inhabitants of the warring state. In the Boko Haram context, suicide bombing tactics involving women and children is a case in point and which, according to Akali (2018), has complicated the Nigerian military and security forces' efforts to counter the insurgents.

In addition, in present-day armed combat, military attacks are incrementally executed in civilian-populated areas. The enemies often intermix with civilians and, as a consequence, make it seriously hard in practical terms to draw a line between enemy fighters and their supporters from the general populace (Gaggioli, 2013). There are many incidences in the counterterrorism operations of the Nigerian military with high civilian casualties as a result of the integration of Boko Haram fighters with the local communities in the northeast. Commenting on this, the retired military personnel during my interview with him stated:

“There was a particular area in Yobe state they used to call eh, I have forgotten the name. Even though we used to patrol around that parameter, we did not know that Boko Haram fighters were hiding there until the day they killed one of our officers. When our men invaded the area, we all assumed that the entire village was Boko Haram members. Still, during our attack on that village, I didn't need anyone to tell me that many villagers were innocent civilians. Many of the civilians fell as war casualties” (Sgt. X).

Brechenmacher (2019) acknowledges this challenge in her paper ‘Stabilisation of Northeast Nigeria after Boko Haram’, where she contends that one of the most challenging issues of stabilisation programs at the local level is that the security forces themselves have been responsible for the insecurity, displacement, and radicalisation of local communities. She also states that at the start of the conflict, there was an overreliance by the military on the general chastisement of communities suspected of hiding Boko Haram members. The military treated civilians, including women and children, as terrorist suspects as they recaptured territories from the insurgents. Screening processes intended at detecting individuals’ links with terrorist organisations often resulted in family separation, inhumane treatment, illegal detention, and, in some cases, torture. Such flagrant abuses worsened the conditions of those communities that had experienced Boko Haram’s cruelty. The human rights violations of the Nigerian military also hampered security support from the US due to the Leahy Act, which prohibits the US government from rendering any form of military support to foreign forces complicit in human rights violations (Brechenmacher, 2019).

Additionally, disregard for the rule of law and incompetent judiciary, coupled with chronic impunity by state actors in many democratic states in Africa, have led to serious human rights abuses. Violations of freedom of expression and association, rights to a fair hearing in a court of law, unlawful and prolonged detention and torture have enjoyed the backing of the law for state security interests (Sigsworth, 2019). In Nigeria, for instance, even after transitioning to a democratic rule in 1999, successive governments have continuously derogated from human rights obligations, shown disregard for the rule of law and court orders, restricted freedom of expression and association, illegally arrested, and detained unarmed and peaceful protesters, journalist, political and human rights activists, religious leaders, and oppositions. In the account given by one of the participants on the current state of human rights under democracy in Nigeria, Amnesty International staff noted that:

“On the face of it. So, looking at the laws that have been passed, such as the Anti-Torture Act of 2017, the renewed Police Act of 2002, and the institutions that were established like the National Human Rights Commission (NHRC). It looks like Nigeria at least has the structures and the institutions that can monitor, promote, and protect human rights. But in peoples’ lived reality, Nigeria is struggling” (A.I Staff).

Personnel of the Department for State Security Service (DSS) also indicated that not much has changed with respect to the advancement of or adherence to human rights provision since the start of a democratic system of government in Nigeria. According to him:

“Nothing has really changed on the issue of human rights protection under the democratic dispensation. When you look at the current issues, such as the Lekki incident, the government has not prioritised human rights protection” (Agent, X).

The Lekki incident referred to by the officer was the ENDSARS protest in Lagos state, Nigeria, on the 20th of October 2020 against an enduring and increasing brutality by the Special Anti-robbery Squad (SARS) of the Nigerian police against civilians, especially the youths that were violently handled by the military and the police killing twelve civilians mostly young people (Paquette, 2020; Oyekanmi, 2020). The Lagos state governor, Nigerian military and Nigerian police have initially denied the allegations of the massacre, insisting that only two people were killed (Adediran, 2020), but later admitted to the allegations after compelling evidence from the investigation of a panel of inquiry was presented to the state governor (Elbagir et al., 2020).

Similarly, in their responses to how human rights protection is faring under democracy in Nigeria, both the NHRC staff and retired military officers stated that human rights violations in Nigeria are still worrisome, and the government has not done enough to improve the situation. Prior to the Lekki massacre, several similar incidences have occurred in the past. Some of the most recent cases include the Zaria massacres in 2014, 2015 and 2018 against the Shiite Islamic movement in Kaduna state that led to the arrest and detention of the group’s leader, El-Zakzaky, the murder of thirty of his followers, including three of his sons in 2014 and the killing of forty-five members of the group in 2018 protesting for the release of their leader (VOA News, 2015; Isenyo, 2015; Melvin, 2015).

6.3 Human rights in armed conflict

In times of conflict, civilians are usually the victims. They may frequently encounter threats of violence and death when trapped in the middle of a conflict. Though civilians are protected under international human rights and humanitarian law, they keep falling victim to violence and, in some cases, are intentionally targeted by combatants. The attacks on civilians can be in the form

of sexual violence and extrajudicial killings to intimidate and force compliance from the locals (Foreign and Commonwealth Office, 2016).

In recent times, violent conflicts have cost millions of civilian lives and gross contraventions of international humanitarian and human rights law. Civilian casualties have also become prevalent in many armed conflicts (OHCHR, 2019). In some contexts, these violations may be classified as war crimes or genocide. As such, in the past 20 years, governments, civil society organisations, political leaders, human rights advocates, and journalists have increasingly made reference to international humanitarian law and human rights in armed conflicts. In addition, both the Commission on Human Rights and the General Assembly and, not long ago, the Human Rights Council proposed that in armed conflict, all parties involved have legally binding commitments regarding the rights of individuals in conflict times. While international human rights and international humanitarian law are dissimilar in scope, they all provide a certain form of protection to people in armed conflict, regardless of whether they are civilians or individuals who are actively or inactively engaged in the conflict (Henckaerts and Doswald-Beck, 2005). According to the Icelandic Human Rights Centre (IHRC) (2019), human rights abuse occurs more often during armed conflict. As such, over the years, much emphasis by experts has centred on establishing mechanisms to alleviate human suffering in times of war and conflict (IHRC, 2019). Similarly, Behnke (2019) also advocates that conflict, security, and humanitarian circumstances have tendencies to exacerbate or elicit human rights concerns. Therefore, it is crucial to guarantee protection and adherence to human rights and international humanitarian law, particularly by armed and security forces, in the discharge of their duties.

6.4 Human rights and security: Two different sides of a coin?

Security and human rights could be argued to be the two most important defining elements of any sovereign state, liberal or authoritarian. While the first protects the state against external and internal threats, the latter is concerned with the protection of the dignity of persons within that state. And until recently, these have endured and have come to be understood as complementary in liberal democratic states. Suddenly, however, it has almost become normative to view these values as conflicting in the contemporary national security discourse in many liberal democracies, especially in the context of counterterrorism, with more preference given to

national security interests. It is, however, unclear, according to McCall-Smith et al. (2020), whether it was the 9/11 attack (and if it was, it could be the reason for the increased use of questionable counterterrorism measures) or the new form of imperialism that is responsible for the unprecedented preferences state attached national security over human rights. He, however, suggests that perhaps states' experience with terrorism or the influence it has on international security debates are among the factors responsible for the overriding importance accorded to it by states.

Nonetheless, the most pressing question is not when national security began to take precedence over human rights but whether they are, in their true meaning, conflicting or irreconcilable. When asked this question, the DSS personnel opined that:

“Yes, they are antithetical as far as Nigeria is concerned. Because we always have issues of security and human rights. E.g., the Lekki tollgate. The citizens felt that they had the right to protest, while the government always felt they didn't” (Agent X).

While I was surprised at his response at first, it soon became sensible upon the realisation that the officer's response was rather specific to Nigeria. That is to suggest that when objectively viewed in their real context, it ought not to be so, but the reality on the ground speaks otherwise. Or put better; these two values are against each other based on the existing realities in Nigeria. A similar opinion is also expressed by the NHRC staff, who pointed out:

“Yes, they are against each other. Because security agencies always complain that the NHRC is protecting people who violate the law. So, most of them don't like NHRC intervening in their cases” (NHRC Staff 2).

This response reinforces the DSS personnel position and suggests an interference of Nigeria's security forces in the NHRC's efforts to get justice for victims and hold them accountable for human rights violations. However, in contrast to these two previous opinions, the retired military officer suggests that, in fact, one cannot separate human rights and security, as they work side by side, and elaborately explained that:

“Well, I don't think security and human rights are two opposite things. They are not opposite in such a way that you will say let me face security and then ignore human rights. They are supposed to work hand in hand. They are not two different things. They are supposed to be on the same side. I don't buy the idea that they are against

each other. I don't buy it! What I am trying to say in essence, sir, for example, now, when we talk about security, let me just be very specific. Maybe in this town, there has been a rampant armed robbery, and robbery is also part of insecurity. So, when the government try in its own power to curb the robbery in the town and clamp down on those robbers and then make the town safe. By doing that, they have also promoted human rights. Because these people were being robbed, their human rights were also violated. So that is what I am saying. When you bring security, you are also promoting human rights" (Sgt. X).

From the military officer's perspective, security and human rights are complementary, and the achievement of security is as good as human rights protection. In essence, human security is also a human right. This response corresponds with Ramcharan's (2004) position in the literature review. From these varied responses, one can deduce that while the three respondents look at the issue from different angles, they don't entirely disagree with each other when critically viewed. This is because the first two responses are based on Nigeria's current situation, while the last is based on the ideal or real context of the two values. Therefore, one can say that, but for Nigeria's current realities, human rights and security ought not to be antithetical.

If human rights and security are not antithetical, why then is or should security take precedence over human rights? As well discussed in the literature review, the doctrine of necessity and emergency seem to state' the main moral arguments for the overriding consideration given to national security. For instance, it is common for states to take extreme measures when faced with an imminent security threat, such as in a "time-bomb" scenario, even if it trumps existing human rights and civil liberty obligations. When confronted with these debates, a top staff of Amnesty International in Nigeria argued that:

"I don't think that there is a situation where security will take pre-eminence. Because human right is the foundation [sic]. Human rights are [sic]something you cannot wish away; you cannot give up. Rather, what they should be looking at is how someone's human rights are enhanced through their interventions. Very often, security forces take the easy way around to say oh, it was for security reasons, and they use it as an excuse. Whereas security is not done in isolation. There is a body of rules and principles to be taken into consideration. And the people that implement the security apparatus are well-trained. So, I don't want to believe that they cannot use their training to apply when to act and how to de-escalate a violent situation" (A.I Staff).

This response is a clear insistence that under no circumstance or condition should security be given importance over human rights and that state's security measures should also advance individual rights (a view extensively captured by Howard-Hassmann (2012) in the literature review). Most importantly, security forces must be guided by established laws and apply their training in their operations instead of using security to justify human rights abuses.

The NHRC staff also expressed a strong rejection of the doctrine of necessity, noting that:

“Seriously, it is not good to trample on people's rights because you want to achieve security. That is what will even make some people become terrorists if you deny them their rights” (NHRC Staff I).

Several academic literature on terrorism and counterterrorism and expert opinions linking human rights violations with radicalisation support this opinion, and this is also true in the case of the Boko Haram conflict, as evidenced in the literature and the data collected in this research. And as McCall-Smith et al. (2022) rightly observed, national security interest impacts the demand for safeguarding human rights amongst states in a varied way and affects how they approach national security debates in the global setting. Adequate consideration of national security demands must, therefore, be taken in inter and intra-state policy processes as it directly affects a state's relationship with its citizens (McCall-Smith et al., 2022). And though the laws that stipulate state human rights obligations appear straightforward, even the most unnoticeable discrepancies in their implementation can have grave consequences on the enjoyment and protection of individual rights (OHCHR, 2020). Therefore, despite the controversially reassuring relationship between human rights and liberal democracies, the constantly changing nature of the world suggests that a shift in human rights was an inevitability. What was not inevitable, however, was where and when that shift would actualise or what the defining moment might be (McCall-Smith, 2022: 6).

6.5 Compliance and the issue of balancing

In my literature review, I interrogated the debate on balancing security and human rights, where the proponents of the respective schools of thought argued that the pursuit of security and the demands for individuals' rights could be achieved in times of conflict. Because this argument is grounded in liberal ideology and forms part of the core research question of this study, I engaged

the participants to elicit their views on whether or not it is possible to achieve the protection of life and property during counterterrorism operations. In responding to this question, one of the participants explained:

“To some extent, the Nigerian military is taking human rights into consideration when fighting the insurgents. However, they are not consistent. That is the reason we still have reports of human rights violations here and there” (NHRC Staff).

In further confirmation of the above response, the Norwegian Refugee Council (NRC) also observes that the security agencies have persistently treated civilians in the areas under Boko Haram or ISWAP control as potential terrorists and, as such, denied those areas access to resources to punish Boko Haram thereby causing hunger and starvation. The military has also stopped international organisations from entering areas that are not fully under government control and disregarded estimations of the civilian population trapped in those areas as incorrect (Norwegian Refugee Council, 2018). While there appears to be a renewed commitment towards military support and collaboration from the West, especially the US, since the ascension of Buhari to power, the government, however, has done little in the area of prosecution of human rights violations, which persist in the counter-insurgency operations in the northeast. The military has also demonstrated a lack of commitment to transparency in its operations. Lately, military training and arms transactions have been stalled by the West in a renewed effort to pressure the Nigerian military to improve compliance with human rights obligations (Brechenmacher, 2019).

In addition, the DSS personnel I interviewed were not fully confident of compliance with human rights protection in the counterterrorism operations in the northeast. In his response, he noted that, to a lesser extent, the military does comply with human rights obligations. What this entails is that their compliance with human rights laws is limited and inconsistent. A similar view is also shared by the second NHRC staff I interviewed. He is also of the opinion that the military does occasionally respect civilian rights when fighting Boko Haram, but not all the time. They have encroached on civilian rights from time to time. The Amnesty International staff, on the other hand, believes that in the past, the Nigerian military was culpable of gross human rights violations, especially at the start and peak of the conflict. However, she observed that:

“If we look at it in the last few years, they have changed certain interventions which were not there at the beginning. So, for example, now they have human rights

screening forms for military officers going into the theatre of war. I am aware that they also ask for specific ehm rules of conduct (ehm rules of engagement sorry) to be agreed upon before people are deployed” (A.I Staff).

Despite these developments, she is critical of the level at which compliance with these rules is monitored and the evidence of the training given. She also noted that the lack of transparency on how these training and rules have improved the conduct of officers and their practicality makes it difficult to measure their impact. But overall, there is improvement in the area of personnel training.

In his response on whether security personnel, especially the Nigerian military, comply with human rights law and the rules of war in combat situations, a staff of the National Human Rights Commission (NHRC) explained that:

“The way the situation has degenerated, it is difficult to distinguish between insurgents and civilians. So, I think it is really hard to safeguard lives and property while ensuring the protection of individuals' rights. Because you find out that the Boko Haram is fond of integrating with the community and after carrying out an attack, they go back to the bush” (A.I Staff).

The Amnesty staff did not also rule out the possibility of finding common ground to fight insurgency while ensuring that lives and properties are safeguarded but also acknowledged that it would be difficult, especially in an ongoing conflict. This, according to her, is because, in conflict times, civilians are always at risk of becoming casualties of war. Though a similar view was shared by some of the Male IDPs, they are divided on this issue. About six of the male participants were of the view that the protection of lives and properties is possible in war times. Whereas the remaining four insisted that it is difficult to achieve both requirements at the same time. One of the staff of the National Human Rights Commission was also sceptical about this during our interview. He worries that given the guerrilla warfare tactics of Boko Haram, which often uses civilians as shields, it will always frustrate the efforts of the Nigerian military to adhere to human rights obligations, thereby provoking indiscriminate counterattacks and brutal retaliation, which, for the most part, ends in extrajudicial killings and high-rate civilian casualties.

On the contrary, the retired military officer believes it is possible if there is strict punishment for violators and proper training of officers on the rules of engagement and human rights laws.

Additionally, some of the female IDPs have a similar view. They stated that if there is strong political will and commitment to human rights issues by the government, the military will be forced to comply. I, therefore, further asked if balancing human rights and security demands would help address the issue of human rights abuses in armed conflict, and the DSS personnel stated that:

“I think balancing both will help. Because the security apparatus of the state has faced a lot of criticism. So, I think balancing both will go a long way in addressing the matter” (Agent X).

Equally, the National Human Rights Commission’s staff also maintain the same view. According to him:

“Yes, that would be a good approach. It will bring about a 50/50 balance in the approach to tackling the crisis and the insurgency. Because you cannot prioritise human rights alone without the people who will protect those human rights. So that when you are talking about security, you are also considering human rights, and when you are considering human rights, you are also considering the security aspect of things” (NHRC Staff 1).

6.6 Contrasting opinions from the participants

There is a lack of consensus among respondents on the efficacy of the military approach to counterterrorism in the Boko Haram conflict. The male IDPs expressed varying opinions on the effectiveness of the military force. While six participants, on the one hand, are pleased with the achievements made by the Nigerian military in regaining back control of most territories from Boko Haram, on the other hand, they are not pleased with the prolonged conflict and the failure of the military to end it.

One of the male IDPs stressed that:

“I cannot say that military tactics are not effective because if not for them, many of us wouldn’t still be alive today. So, I think they are trying their best” (Male IDP I).

Another IDP is of the opinion that the military will do better if given sophisticated weapons. He stated that:

“I believe that the military is really trying because the terrorists have more sophisticated weapons than them. The soldiers will be more effective if the

government provides them with the same types of weapons the terrorists are using” (Male IDP II).

The other four IDPs are, however, unsatisfied with the military approach and believe that the tactic has not been effective. They argued that if the military tactic had been effective, the conflict would have ended long ago, and Boko Haram should have been annihilated by now.

According to one of them:

“My concern is that the conflict has been going on for more than ten years, and yet Boko Haram are still attacking and killing people in the northeast. They are now even carrying out attacks in other parts of the country. How can you say that they are effective?” (Male IDP III).

In the words of one Male IDP:

“We have seen the military running away and abandoning their post and even their weapons when they hear Boko Haram attacking nearby villages and neighbourhoods. There were many similar incidents reported from people in other states in the northeast” (Male IDP IV).

To confirm the above claim, another Male IDP narrated that:

“In my local government, many of the soldiers would remove their uniforms and throw away their guns when they hear Boko Haram approaching or shootings near their location. Some of them would even join fleeing civilians to escape from the terrorists. It was so shameful and embarrassing” (Male IDP V).

Some of the IDPs suggested that the government should engage the group through dialogue and negotiations for a total ceasefire and resolution. This opinion is also shared by Olojo (2019), who argues that since the use of military force has failed to restore peace and order in the affected communities, engagements and dialogue should be profoundly explored, and it requires genuine political will from the government. He also contends that attempts at negotiations by previous administrations failed not because they were not possible but due to a lack of political will and an unclear agreed set of goals by government officials (Olojo, 2019).

In contrast, during my engagement with the female IDPs, most of them argued that even though dialogue and negotiations are crucial to ending the conflict, they insist that the military approach is still the best. According to one of the women in the group:

“I don’t think dialogue will end this conflict. These people’s (referring to Boko Haram) hearts are hardened. They can not be trusted. If the military will do their job well, they will defeat them. They have killed too many innocent people, and to me, they should be killed too because the people they killed deserve justice” (Female IDP I).

Some of these claims carry weight in a practical sense of the conflict, given that not until recently, military efforts have largely proved ineffective for most parts of the insurgency. I would also not be surprised if this opinion is based on the fact that some of the participants have suffered serious losses at the hands of the terrorists and would rather have them killed, arrested, and prosecuted than be pardoned or given amnesty. Moreover, most of them believe that diplomacy alone cannot resolve the conflict because not all the Boko Haram members will be willing to lay down arms.

They also opined that they have reservations about the sincerity of the repentant insurgents as they believe that some of them would end up spying for Boko Haram. Many Nigerians, security experts, academics, and some civil society organisations have expressed scepticism about the sincerity of the repentant terrorists since the government introduced the amnesty program for repentant Boko Haram members. In fact, the Governor of Borno state, the origin and epicentre of the conflict, decried, "It has been confirmed that the concept of deradicalisation or Safe Corridor is not working as expected. Quite often, those who have passed through the Safe Corridor initiative or have been deradicalised usually go back and re-join the terror group after carefully studying the various security arrangements in their host communities during the reintegration process” (Owolabi, 2021). A similar concern has also been expressed by Maj. Gen Christopher Musa, the Theatre Commander of Operation Hadin Kai, suggests that repentant terrorists who have surrendered have hidden agendas, as some of them are converting back and undermining military efforts to end the conflict (Ikuomola, 2021). There is also widespread public frustration and doubts as to the extent to which these repentant terrorists can be trusted, and resentment of the government’s goodwill gestures towards the insurgents while ignoring the plight of the conflict’s victims (Breachmacher, 2019). The commander of Operation Hadi Kai has, however, observed that the surrendering of insurgents is a good development that may end the conflict sooner than expected if properly managed (Ikuomola, 2021).

6.7 Alternative counterterrorism strategies

The preceding analysis section examines the arguments and counterarguments on the effectiveness of the military force in armed conflicts such as the Boko Haram insurgency in Nigeria. From some of the literature used in the analysis and the participants' views, there is a clear indication that military force has not been the most effective approach in the global 'war on terror' campaign. This is evident in some case studies of the previous US counterterrorism military expeditions elsewhere since the 9/11 attacks. Though some may argue that the use of military force in the war on terror campaign is to some extent effective, this is, however, dependent on the context in which success is defined. However, the focus of this section is not to dwell on these arguments but rather on what effective counterterrorism strategies other than the traditional excessive use of the military could be employed to combat terrorism. Two major alternative strategies have been identified in the data, and they are dialogue and community policing.

6.7.1 Dialogue and community policing

Dialogue has numerous meanings depending on the context in which it is being used. Dialogue, according to Rieker (2015), is a word often used to mean formal negotiations among two or more groups in a conflict. It also depicts an informal communication process between conflicting entities, resulting in negotiations or preventing a conflict from escalating, with no intention to reach the negotiation stage (Rieker, 2015). Also, Sida (2018) contends that dialogue is a tool used to promote relationships and establish common ground among a large group of people. It is also a means of extending the range of an official process through extensive participation. Dialogues are designed in the form of conversations and are usually public, though some aspects may be confidentially conducted (Sida, 2018).

Dialogue has become an indispensable tool in conflict resolution globally. Unlike orthodox approaches to conflict that centre on power dynamics, negotiations and military intervention, dialogue fosters communication, mutual understanding and reconciliation through platforms for engagement between two or more opposing entities for building trust and sustainable peace.

Since the Cold War era, dialogue has remained a crucial and effective means for resolving disputes in pre and post-conflict times (Lederach, 1997; Lund, 2009 and Hayner, 2010). Dialogue is now one of the popular slogans in global politics today. Specifically, small states are increasingly emphasising the significance of dialogue and meditation (Rieker, 2015). In the words of Støre, ‘Engaging in dialogue with a group and its members is not the same thing as legitimising its goals and ideology., and when used skilfully, engagement may moderate their policies and behaviour’ (Støre 2011). However, Rieker (2015) argues that the effectiveness of dialogue as an instrument for resolving conflict is contingent on how it functions and influences actors in diverse settings. Much depends on whether dialogue seeks to advance understanding, influence the identities and interests of actors, or just aims to stop the degeneration of violence (Rieker, 2015). In the case of the Boko Haram conflict, the latter would and should be more beneficial for achieving peace.

According to Gideon (2018), a national dialogue approach and strong political commitment can help renew the social contract and help rebuild the democracy of a country, especially during conflict (Mabor, 2018). However, history has shown that dialogue also has its limitations (Rosen, 1995; Burbules, 2000; Rose-Redwood et al., 2018). It does not ultimately guarantee peace, especially if there is a lack of sincerity and commitment from both actors throughout the dialogue process. For instance, in the 1997 Kosovo-Serbia conflict, the joint military intervention of NATO, the US, and the EU that occasioned Kosovo’s independence in 2008, which ended the Serbian rule, was a result of several failed attempts by the UN administration to resolve the conflict through dialogue, and till date, there is still serious tension and uncertainties that threaten the much-desired peace in the region in the long term (Crisis Group, 2021).

Côte d’Ivoire’s decade of political violence is another example of the shortcomings of dialogue. The reconciliation process, which was based on the Dialogue Truth and Reconciliation Commission (CDVR) program, brought an end to the two civil wars of 2002-2007 and made the 2010 presidential election possible. However, several other conflicts erupted between 2015 and 2016, the worst being in 2017 when several targeted attacks on the national security forces lasted for several months in Abidjan, the nation’s capital. Although dialogue played a critical role in the fragile peace currently enjoyed in the country, divisions along religious, social, and ideological lines have remained perverse since the end of the two civil wars, and this has polarised the

political structure and hindered democratic practices in several aspects. This is because most of the peace pacts were not integrative but rather distributive and contributory for the most part (Benedikter et al., 2019).

6.7.2 Dialogues in Africa: a retrospect

There are several cases in Africa where dialogue ushered in relative peace. For instance, in Burundi, the Organization for African Unity (OAU), now African Union (AU), was involved in several peace interventions since 1994 that were crucial in de-escalating the conflict in the country through the instrumentality of the late Nelson Mandela and Julius Nyerere, and other peacebuilding measures (Muyangwa and Voigt 2000:10). Central to the AU success in Burundi was the multi-disciplinary strategy fixated on establishing the environment for enduring peace and development instead of just disarmament. About 3000 soldiers were deployed under the African Union Mission in Burundi (AMIB) to secure the returning exiled political advocates and refugees to help with the disbandment of rebel sects and extensive peacebuilding efforts. The mission in Burundi was inclusive as it involved ex-ambassadors as political envoys to oversee the transition from one government to the next through negotiations with major political groups and through a commitment to confidence-building to sustain peace in the country (Zondi, 2017).

After over a decade of the Boko Haram conflict in Nigeria, the Nigerian military is yet to win the fight against the terrorist group in northeastern Nigeria. This, according to Khalid of BBC News Nigeria, is due to over-dependence on military strategy (Khalid, 2021). The military resources of the Multi-national Joint Task Force have been overstretched in battles that have no signs of ending soon. The major counterterrorism strategy in the region that relies on the military might have failed in bringing enduring peace to the affected communities. These military failures and the uncertainty of when the conflict will end have provoked agitations for dialogue and negotiations in recent times (Sheriff et al., 2013; Bukola, 2014; Akinola, 2019; Fowowe, 2019; Iweze, 2021).

The participants I interviewed during my fieldwork have contrasting opinions on dialogue and negotiation with Boko Haram. Some female and male IDP peer groups recommended the dialogue approach, but the majority were not confident that it would be successful. I was

fascinated by their responses because I thought that since most participants see the military approach as ineffective and unproductive, a dialogue would be a preferred option. However, they argue to differ. One of the National Human Rights Commission's staff even explained that:

“I don't think dialogue with terrorists is the best. I am saying this because it won't be possible. I think from the beginning that is what they used in the first place, i.e., having a dialogue with the leaders of Boko Haram before the conflict escalated” (NHRC Staff 1).

The NHRC staff referenced the arrest and execution of the first Boko Haram commander, Mohammed Yusuf, in 2009 by the Nigerian military at the start of the conflict as a clear example of the near impossibility of achieving any successful dialogue due to the distrust that incident has created between the government and the group.

Aside from the scepticism on dialogue expressed by the respondents (a view widely shared by some members of the public) and as Olojo (2019) rightly observes, the chances of Boko Haram accepting any government's invitation to negotiate are very narrow, and there is division on the issue among the populace, especially the affected communities. Another major obstacle that may limit the scope of negotiation with Boko Haram is their agenda to establish an Islamic state and impose Sharia law in a multi-religious country like Nigeria. Despite the obstacles, potential openings for engaging in talks should be more deeply explored, and this requires real imagination and will on the government's part (Olojo, 2019).

Furthermore, the responses from the DSS personnel and the retired military officer were not in favour of dialogue. On the one hand, the DSS personnel expressed a lack of confidence in negotiation, but he noted that it could help reduce the conflict to some extent. While the retired officer, on the other hand, worries that it is unlikely that Boko Haram will succumb to sitting at the negotiating table with the government.

6.7.3 Dialogues with Boko Haram: A historical review

It is interesting to note that there were several attempts by the Nigerian government to negotiate with Boko Haram in the past. Nigeria's ex-President Olusegun Obasanjo and Babakura Fugu, the brother-in-law of the late Boko Haram's leader, Mohammed Yusuf, facilitated the first major

effort in 2011. The sudden murder of Fugu, who was the intermediary between the government and Boko Haram, ended the negotiation efforts. Another attempt was made in 2012 when Boko Haram agreed to the appointment of the former president of the Supreme Council for Sharia in Nigeria, Sheikh Ahmed Datti. However, Datti opted out of the negotiation process due to the government's reckless handling of intelligence and sensitive information on ongoing negotiations (Fowowe, 2019).

Notwithstanding the failures of previous attempts at negotiations, there are still signs of hope for a possible future dialogue following the successful negotiations between the Nigerian government and Boko Haram leaders that led to the release of some of the 2014 abducted girls in Chibok town of Borno state in the northeast. According to Bukarti (2017), the successful release of some of the 2014 abducted Chibok girls was made possible through intense negotiations between the Nigerian government and Boko Haram. The first negotiation secured the release of 21 out of the 276 abducted girls in 2016, and the second negotiation rescued 82 more girls. According to reports, the Swiss government and the Red Cross played critical roles in both negotiations that allegedly involved the payment of a ransom in foreign currencies and the release of top Boko Haram commanders in a prisoner exchange (Bukarti, 2017).

Furthermore, there were negotiations led by Hajia Wakil and Hajia Allamin that helped release some hostages, including some of the Chibok girls in Boko Haram's captivity, with no ransom paid by the government. It was gathered that the successful negotiations by Wakil were based on her acts of charity to some of the Boko Haram members before they were radicalised. Allamin, in her part, advocated for dialogue and negotiations between the Nigerian government and Boko Haram at the UN, EU, and the USA. She also rephrased Boko Haram (Western education is forbidden) to Boko Halal, i.e., (Western education is acceptable) and has campaigned against harassment of civilians by security forces as well as secured the free release of hostages in the past (Punch, 2020). After several efforts to return displaced citizens to their homes by the governor have failed due to a lack of trust in the government's ability to secure and protect them, the former ambassador Akinkuolie advised the governor of Borno state, the epicentre of the conflict, to seek the assistance of these two women to initiate fresh negotiations with Boko Haram as continuous reliance on Federal government assistance won't change the situation (Punch, 2020).

6.8 Community policing

Community Policing is the second major alternative to the use of military force identified in the analysis. The DSS personnel disclosed during our interview that:

“Well, I think community policing can assist in curbing the insurgency in the Northeast. But I don’t think dialogue itself is capable of ending the conflict” (Agent X).

Even though the concept of community policing has attracted academic debate in the past 20 years, there is no clear-cut understanding of what it means. Both experts and academics appear more comfortable viewing it as a fluid, impalpable, and vague concept, and as such, they are unable to provide a general definition (Seagrave, 1996). Though the term “community” appeared indistinct and was labelled unfashionable in the 1960s (Trojanowicz and Bucqueroux, 1990), it gained popularity during the 1970s as a slogan for new and transformational policies. As a result, there has been a surge in the number of community-labelled policies such as community care, community education, community radio, community architecture, and community policing (Friedmann, 1992; Willmott, 1987).

The US Department of Justice defined community-based policing as a concept that fosters organisational strategy that advocates for the systematic facilitation of collaborations and problem-solving methods to effectively tackle the immediate situations that lead to public safety problems such as crime and fear of crime under the authority of the police (US Department of Justice, 2014).

Community policing is also referred to as efforts to create collaboration with members of a community and civic organisations that mutually represent them. This entails the engagement of the police with the public in setting their priorities and developing their tactics. To be effective, community policing requires responsiveness to the contributions of the citizens concerning the needs of the community and how best the police can help to achieve them. Central to community policing is the public’s definition of its problems; as such, it is an organisational strategy rather than a set of specific programs. Hence, in practice, this concept significantly varies in different places and is dependent on unique local settings and circumstances (Braga, 2019).

There is, however, a distinction between community policing and community-oriented policing in that the former is not under police authority. Community policing is the collective effort of the people within the community to protect themselves from harm and deal with issues of crime long before the institutionalisation of the police force (Emmanuel et al., 2021). Community policing, for the most part, is a response to bureaucratic policing and aims to organise the public to deal with issues of crime and lawlessness (Seagrave, 1996). It is also a citizen-centred strategy in which the members of the community participate in the design, execution, and assessment of public security (Ikuteyijo, 2009). Generally, the major objective the concept of community policing seeks to achieve is the creation of quality collaborations between the police and the citizenry and an extensive problem-solving framework among law enforcement personnel and the members of the community that is targeted at the identification and eradication of causative factors of crime (Community Policing Consortium, 1994).

6.8.1 The concept of community policing in the US and Africa: A comparison

In the US, community policing also exists in the form of “neighbourhood watch,” a top-bottom style of community policing normally established and regulated by the state (Schärf, 2000). This style is similar to the Western/European community police and involves intensive training, investment in and the application of problem-solving techniques, attention to vulnerable groups, all-encompassing collaborations, and engagement with communities leading to an agreed policing program. At the core of this program is addressing the issue of incivilities and improving the quality of life (Dominique and Ihekwoaba, 2008).

This system of community-based policing also exists in the African context. A prominent example of this is the Irondo ry’Umwuga, also known as Professional Night Patrol (PNP) in Rwanda, which emerged as an alternate community-based security institution to the one provided by the government. Irondo predates the 1994 genocide against the Tutsi in Rwanda and is said to have risen to prominence in the early 1990s following an increase in violence and banditry occasioned by the civil war (Kartas, 2011). Community-based policing in the Rwandan context adopts a multi-agency approach through which the police, the citizens, and political officials at different levels partner with the government and other agencies to prevent crime and guarantee community safety (Newtimes, 20014).

The districts and their lower administrative units are the levels at which community policing-related activities are implemented under the community policing and security committees (CPCs) as provided in the October 2007 Ministerial Order No. 02. The Internal Security Policy (RoR, 2008) regulates the activities of night patrols of this security mechanism. Also, there is a strong link between patrol initiatives under the community policing mechanism and the local government in that the local government serves as the medium through which crimes from village to cell, sector, and districts are reported by the night patrollers (Barihuta, 2017).

At the core of this community-based policing system is community mobilisation, which plays a critical role in the decentralised units and is utilised by local leaders to attract citizens to participate in the security mechanism through financial and physical support for the night patrols. The city of Kigali in Rwanda is the place where the collaboration between security agencies and community-driven initiatives is widely adhered to. This is due to the active role state security forces in collaboration with the militias and night patrollers played under previous regimes in harassing the citizens just before the 1994 Tutsi genocide. As such, the government closely monitors other security apparatus such as this to ensure good practices to secure poor neighbourhoods and provide resources for capacity building as well as prevent abuse of powers by *Irondo ry'umwuga* (Barihuta, 2017).

Furthermore, there are other forms of bottom-up community-style policing in Africa that are different from those of the US and Rwanda. This is a vigilante style of community policing and is usually associated with violence and 'jungle justice' as the primary strategy. A typical example of vigilante-style community policing is the former Bakassi Boys in Nigeria and the People Against Gangsterism and Drugs (PAGAD) in South Africa. Furthermore, these vigilante groups can sometimes change to militias and be institutionalised in the state and incorporated into the security apparatus (Kroef, 1988). Militias are enlisted and trained as backup police with the powers to arrest and are paid by the state they serve. Such militias can be found in Sudan and Nigeria. An example of such militias is the *Shurta Shabia* found in Sudan, who are paid through an informal Islamic tax system called the *Zakhat* (Baillard and Haenni, 1998). Militias' work may include mainly public order and territorial security (Commonwealth Human Rights Initiative, 2006) or, as in the case of the *Shurta Shabia* in Sudan, partly moral police (Dominique and Ihekwoaba, 2008).

Additionally, the Civilian Joint Task Force is another popular vigilante group in northern Nigeria. Their origin can be traced back to a town in Maiduguri called Hausari in June 2013. It started as a political thug group with predominantly jobless youths funded by desperate politicians who lure them with fake promises of lucrative government jobs and all sorts of political affiliations and patronage. However, soon, the group turned into a local vigilante following the rampant and incessant killings by Boko Haram coupled with the Nigerian military's embarrassing performance at the start of the conflict. Armed with local traditional armaments such as bows and arrows, machetes, and, in rare instances, hunter's guns, the youths mobilised to protect their families and communities from Boko Haram attacks (Idris et al., 2014). Their fearlessness and bravery quickly gave them public support and followership. Seeing this development and the pockets of successful counterattacks against Boko Haram by the group, the Nigerian government will later endorse and include them in the counterterrorism operations of the Nigerian military as the Civilian (JTF). Recognising their contributions to the counterterrorism operations of the Nigerian military, the Integrated Regional Information Networks (IRIN) called the Civilian (JTF) the "eyes and ears" of the military for providing local intelligence and usually the first to react to Boko Haram's threat (IRIN 2014).

6.9 Conclusion

This chapter analysed the data on the human rights approach to counterterrorism. First, the effectiveness of the coercive and militaristic approach in the GWT, which has gained prominence since the 9/11 attacks, and the challenges of human rights protection in armed conflict were examined. Second, the debate on how national security concerns and compliance with the provisions of human rights protection and civil liberties in conflict situations such as insurgency, especially in a liberal state, were further interrogated. Third, an analysis of the concept of community policing in both the Western and African contexts was carried out. Here, a comparative analysis of community policing as a tool for intelligence gathering, crime prevention, and countering terrorism globally and in Africa were analysed. Fourth, this chapter also discussed the concept of dialogue and community policing as alternative counterterrorism approaches. A historical overview of several dialogue attempts between the Nigerian government

and Boko Haram and a projection of the potential of this approach in resolving the persisting insurgency in northeastern Nigeria were extensively discussed.

CHAPTER SEVEN

DISCUSSION OF FINDINGS

EVIDENCE OF HUMAN RIGHTS VIOLATIONS IN THE BOKO HARAM COUNTERTERRORISM CAMPAIGN

7.0 Introduction

This chapter will discuss findings on the major issues of human rights violations based on the data analysed in the previous analysis chapters. Here, the main findings will be thematically discussed with a focus on the major forms of human rights violations in the conflict and the extent of abuses committed by the Nigerian military, such as the illegal arrest and detention of terrorist suspects, infringement on individuals' privacy, rape, and torture. Also, findings on the effectiveness of an alternative to the use of military force in the conflict shall be discussed.

7.1.1 Indiscriminate and unlawful arrest and detention of suspects

From the analysis of data conducted in the previous chapter, illegal arrests and prolonged detention of suspects have been identified among some of the forms of human rights abuses in the Boko Haram conflict. Most of these arrests are usually based on suspicion of either membership of or affiliation with Boko Haram. When these arrests are made, they are often without arrest warrants from a competent court of law or any form of legal backing. According to the findings, most often, these illegal arrests occur during military raids on communities suspected of harbouring the insurgents, military checkpoints on highways, and even in IDP camps. Also, the findings reveal that even children are not spared from these forms of abuse. Reports by Amnesty International suggest that arrested children escaping Boko Haram strongholds are kept in military detention camps in the northeast and are mixed with adults, which exposes them to abuse and bullying.

Further findings reveal that the majority of the detention centres are dilapidated, and detainees are kept in terrible and inhabitable conditions with no access to good healthcare services, food,

and water supply. Infectious diseases due to overcrowding are also widely reported in most detention centres, and detainees are not allowed access to their families and legal counsel to facilitate trial and decide their fate. This form of violation has been extensively debated in counterterrorism literature (Gross, 2002; Borelli, 2005; Roberts, 2007; Cassel, 2008; Hakimi, 2009; Elliott, 2010; Londras, 2011; and McCann, 2015) and applies to the wider global counterterrorism efforts. For instance, the US Guantanamo Bay prison is one of the iconic terrorist detention centres in the world where terrorist suspects from all over the world are detained under extreme conditions for years without trial or conviction.

Furthermore, counterterrorism legislations of states have, over the years, derogated from the provisions of IHL law that prohibits the arbitrary arrest and detention of persons. Part 4 of the UK government's Anti-Terrorism Crime and Security Act 2001 (ATCSA), Section 142 of the US Patriot Act 2001, and Section 2 Subsection 5a of the 2013 Nigerian Terrorism Prevention Act (TPA) both allow for the arrest and indefinite detention of terrorist suspects. All these counterterrorism legislations are in contradiction with Article 9 of the Universal Declaration of Human Rights (UDHR), Article 5 of the European Convention on Human Rights (ECHR), Section 35 of the Nigerian Constitution as amended, as well as Article 6 of the African Charter on Human and Peoples' Rights.

7.1.2 Violations of privacy and rape

Violations related to the privacy of individuals, rape, and extortion of civilians by security forces are among the findings of this research. From the data analysed, security personnel, particularly the police and the military, are found to intrude on people's privacy during security operations and patrols. They do this during house-to-house searches where they ransack people's homes without search warrants from the court, seize and check people's phones and travel bags, and harass travellers at highway checkpoints.

In addition, some of the literature on counterterrorism reviewed in this research also suggests that data mining and surveillance, both electronic and in-person, by security agencies also violates individuals' right to privacy. This supports the findings in this study, which shows that security operatives secretly tap into people's phone calls, messages, emails, airline passenger

records, and financial records to track, detect, and predict criminal behaviour in terrorist networks to destabilise them. They also plant hidden surveillance cameras in public buildings and around communities suspected of harbouring terrorists. These counterterrorism measures are very common in the US and UK and have remained controversial and triggered serious public outrage throughout the war on terror campaign, especially in the West.

Article 12 of the UDHR, Article 8 of the UK/ECHR, the US Privacy Act of 1974 as amended, and Section 37 of the Nigerian Constitution provide for the protection of individuals' privacy in their homes and all forms of communications and correspondences. However, despite these laws, Sections 213-218 of the US Patriot Act, Section 44 of the UK Terrorism Act 2000, and the Nigerian Cybercrimes Act 2015 all accord powers to security officers that allow them to intrude on the privacy of persons suspected of associating with, members of terrorist groups to stop and prevent terrorism threats and attacks.

Furthermore, the findings also identify rape among the abuses committed by the Nigerian military in the Boko Haram conflict. The abuses are common in IDP camps and towns and villages ravaged by the conflict. According to the findings, lack of access to livelihoods and inadequate living essentials such as food, shelter, clothing, and medicine are some of the factors that render the victims vulnerable and expose them to all forms of sexual abuse by camp officials and security officers. Most of the victims are widows who lost their husbands to the conflict and orphans who are separated from their parents.

However, one surprising element about the findings is that none of the IDPs made mention of rape during my interviews with them. This is largely due to common suggestions in the literature that rape victims are often reluctant to report being abused due to fear, public stigmatisation, shame, and what their abusers would do to them. Research conducted by Amnesty International, Human Rights Watch, and cases handled by Nigeria's National Human Rights Commission all confirm these postulations. Apart from this, further findings show that there is a lack of willingness from the Judiciary to prosecute rape offenders and the government's lack of interest in the growing cases of rape, which is evident in the large volume of sexual abuse-related cases currently awaiting trial in Nigerian courts. This has triggered widespread protests by human rights groups and women rights activists in Nigeria in recent times. The findings also confirm the reports by Amnesty International that, more often, the Nigerian military denies these allegations,

and this has dented their image and damaged public confidence in their ability to protect women and young girls in the Boko Haram conflict. This is one of the factors responsible for the setbacks experienced by the Nigerian military and other security forces in the conflict.

7.1.3 Torture and interrogation of suspects

Torture is not only globally recognised as a monstrous and inhumane act, but it is also condemned by most liberal and democratic states and is the only form of abuse whose prohibition is “absolute” in the UDHR. According to the findings, the Nigerian military has been engaging in this practice to extract information and force confessions from terrorist suspects since the start of the conflict. Some of the common forms of torture identified in the findings include the beating of IDPs suspected of being members of Boko Haram, the random beating of detained terrorist suspects with gun butts/machetes/batons/sticks/electric cable, nail/teeth removals, starvation, shootings, suspension of detainees upside-down, and Tebay, which involves tying detainees’ elbow behind their backs and suspending them on a stick. These are similar to some of the tortures used in Guantanamo Bay and other terrorist detention facilities around the world, e.g., waterboarding, sleep deprivation, solitary confinement, and the prolonged suspension of suspects in upside-down and awkward positions.

In addition, the findings also discover that there are military officers who have special training skills in torture and have become specialists in that technique. Detained suspects who are unwilling to succumb to less coercive interrogation techniques are usually handed over to the specialist, who then subjects them to the most brutal, inhumane and degrading treatment to get a confession from them. This revelation indicates a deliberate effort by the military to not only indulge in but also institutionalise torture as an interrogation technique in their counterterrorism strategies against Boko Haram.

Furthermore, the use of torture has also been found to be widespread and recurrent not only in the Boko Haram conflict but also across other criminal investigations by the rest of the security agencies in the country. Several reports by the media and many human rights organisations over the years support these findings. Further findings also show a lack of commitment by the government to create stringent and enforceable laws that will ensure the prosecution of violators.

There is also an indication from the findings that the Nigerian military has been complacent on this issue in that, on most occasions, they have not been transparent in the trial and prosecution processes of its officers who have been found guilty of torture. They also tend to cover up these allegations, lie to the public, or sweep them under the carpet to protect their image. Generally, the findings reveal that much attention is given to abuses by the terrorists, but whenever the military is accused, they often give justifications, most common of which is the national security interest or the doctrine of necessity, just as is the case in the wider global counterterrorism context. This is one, if not the most highly debated topic in counterterrorism studies and has been well covered and discussed in the literature and the preceding analysis chapter of this research. Therefore, despite the outright condemnations by liberal governments globally and the absolute prohibition of torture as contained in both the Universal Declaration of Human Rights Law (UDHR) and the European Charter on Human Rights (ECHR), these findings are supported by most of the debates dissected in the literature review, that its use in armed and non-armed conflicts especially in liberal states like Nigeria, remained perverse.

7.1.4 Effectiveness of torture

As adequately demonstrated in the literature in this research, the effectiveness of torture is still an ongoing debate in counterterrorism and security studies. While some scholars have argued that it has led to crucial intelligence that helped stop terrorist attacks on several occasions in the past, this view has been countered by other scholars in the field of terrorism studies against the backdrop that, in most cases, torture is neither effective nor reliable. This has been comprehensively explained by Levinson (2014), who noted that it is hard to ascertain the effectiveness or reliability of torture in that there is no existing proof to support this claim. As such, an evidence-based discourse on the topic is required.

Additionally, the findings suggest that, for the most part, torture has been proven to be unproductive and time-consuming. It also produces false information, which usually results in misleading intelligence. This, according to the findings, is because suspects who, in reality, are not terrorists are compelled to confess due to the excruciating pains they undergo. In fact, the findings reveal that in most cases, suspects who are not subjected to torture give credible intelligence when compared to those who are tortured. This revelation offset the common

assumption that terrorists only confess when they are subjected to inhumane and degrading treatment.

Furthermore, torture is not only found to be ineffective and unreliable, but it is also an old-fashioned interrogation technique. This is because new unconventional interrogation techniques such as persuasion, trickery, and evidence-based confrontation, though slow and resource-demanding, are found to be more effective than torture in recent times. Overall, the lack of adequate intelligence to understand and effectively resolve the Boko Haram conflict despite the widespread torture practice for more than a decade, as reported in most of the existing literature, attests to the ineffectiveness of this technique.

7.2 Military force and counterterrorism

A military approach to counterterrorism became the main strategy of the US under its “war on terror” campaign since the 9/11 attack and has since been adopted by states across the globe. This tactic has, however, appeared to be challenging against a delicate concept of terrorism warfare where terrorists use civilian shields to carry out attacks and the absence of an identifiable battlefield to engage them. The recent US withdrawal from Afghanistan after over twenty years of failed military occupation is a typical case of the inefficacy of military force in counterterrorism warfare. This is also the same in the case of ISIS in Iraq and Syria, and it is not any different in Boko Haram in Nigeria. The findings from the analysis support these existing facts. According to the findings, the use of military force in its own right is not entirely ineffective; it is, however, the over-reliance on this approach as the sole solution that makes it ineffective. This is because there is evidence of successes recorded by the Nigerian military against Boko Haram over the last decade. However, the findings show that the military tactic was only able to weaken the insurgency to some extent but unable to defeat the group.

Furthermore, this study also found that the security forces, especially the Nigerian military, have often derogated from human rights laws during their operations in the northeast, especially at the beginning of the conflict. The findings reveal that the military has resorted to the use of excessive force on numerous occasions, which often led to mass civilian casualties. This is often

out of frustration and a desperate attempt by the military to defeat the terrorists without conforming to the rules of engagement in an armed conflict involving civilians.

Overall, the findings show that the use of excessive military force coupled with human rights abuses as well as the non-compliance with the rules of engagement by the security forces during the early stages of the conflict was what provoked popular public support for the sect and instigated the radicalisation of many civilians in the affected communities who felt threatened and oppressed by the security forces. The level of abuse reported in the conflict was what also deterred the US and UK from rendering any form of military or humanitarian assistance to the Nigerian government at the peak of the conflict. Consequently, the findings also reveal that the conflict would not have escalated or persisted this long if the security forces had used a subtle and non-violent approach to the Boko Haram insurgency when it first began. However, the findings also indicate that the level of violations has dwindled in recent times due to several efforts by the government, such as training and workshops for military personnel on human rights issues in armed conflicts, the establishment of disciplinary committees to ensure compliance and prosecute offenders and policies aimed at improving civil-military relation. There is, however, a lack of clarity as to the extent to which these policies are implemented or whether they are making the desired impact they ought to.

7.3 Alternative Counterterrorism Strategies

7.3.1 Dialogue

Making peace is a far less cinematic activity than making war. The pace of achievement can be glacially slow, but the prize is well worth the waiting. Sometimes, just keeping the conversation going is enough (Devane, 2015). Nonetheless, military force has always been at the forefront of the US global “war on terror” campaign since 2001, an approach that has since become a common feature of counterterrorism measures by most states. Even though the approach has recorded some great strides against some of the notorious terrorist organisations in different parts of the world, research and history have shown that over-reliance on this approach has not always been entirely successful, as is the case of the Boko Haram conflict in Nigeria. This, therefore, is a clear indication that new, better, and unconventional approaches are needed to complement the

existing orthodox tactics used by states in their counterterrorism warfare. This is clearly illustrated in the findings of this study, which identified dialogue as one of the better alternatives to the excessive use of military force. According to the findings, with proper and adequate planning and a strong political will on the part of the government, a dialogue would make a great difference in resolving the enduring Boko Haram conflict against a continuous reliance on military might.

Though there were several failed attempted dialogues with Boko Haram in the past, the findings reveal that there were more successful negotiations between the Nigerian government and the insurgents that saw the release of hostages and the exchange of prisoners in recent times. There is also an increasing debate in favour of dialogue in dealing with the Boko Haram conflict both within Nigeria and in the Lake Chad region, which is due to several successful negotiations achieved between the state and the group.

Furthermore, the findings show that there are several policy initiatives akin to dialogue currently set up by the Nigerian government to end the conflict. Some of these initiatives include amnesty for repentant terrorists, deradicalisation strategies, disarmament, reintegration, and reconciliation programs for captured or surrendered Boko Haram members. However, all these initiatives have suffered serious challenges since their inception. This, according to the findings, is not unrelated to the fact that the programs were most often implemented out of “desperation”; they lack proper monitoring and supervision; they exclude victims and the affected communities in the amnesty processes; and a lack of prosecution of surrendered Boko Haram members. As a result of all these factors, there is serious bitterness and anger towards the government by victims and communities who are yet to recover from the nightmares of the conflict and who still demand justice against the crimes committed by Boko Haram, hence opposed to these initiatives and unwilling to welcome repentant terrorists back to their midst due to distrust and grudge.

There is also a surge in the number of repentant Boko Haram members in recent times. The most recent example is the surrender of 5,890 Boko Haram and Islamic State of West Africa Province (ISWAP) terrorists and their families to the Nigerian military between August 12 and September 2022 (Ufuoma, 2022; Reuters, 2022). These recent trends have put serious pressure on the government, which is already struggling to manage the many previous repentant terrorists under the amnesty program.

Terrorism is a Federal offence under the Nigerian constitution. As such, public dismay for the lack of prosecution of the repentant or captured terrorists by the Nigerian government is widespread. The findings, therefore, suggest that the government must address these lingering issues by establishing a community-based reconciliation and integration process and adequately engaging with the local communities in the dialogue processes to help identify suitable mediators in the negotiation efforts. In addition, the trajectories of the repentant terrorists must be well monitored but not in isolation of the local communities, as this will be essential to measure the effectiveness of the reconciliation program to develop a sufficient contingency plan given the isolated nature of the reintegration process.

Therefore, from the US military counterterrorism expeditions against al-Qaeda in Afghanistan, ISIS in Iraq, and Syria down to Nigeria's Boko Haram conflict, the use of military force has arguably been unsuccessful for the most part. And though the US succeeded in killing Osama Bin Laden and the masterminds behind the 9/11 attacks through military raids and aerial bombardments, the US has been unable to completely decimate al-Qaeda and its affiliates as it initially intended. The recent withdrawal of US and coalition troops from Afghanistan and the subsequent take-over of the government by al-Qaeda is a typical example.

What is similar in the case of al-Qaeda in Afghanistan and Nigeria's Boko Haram is that military efforts have only succeeded in re-capturing the territories previously controlled by the sects and forcing them to remote areas but have failed to completely end their activities. Nonetheless, exponents of the withdrawal argued that regardless of the contentious result, the US anti-terrorism campaign has sufficiently achieved its original objectives of degrading al-Qaeda and similar terrorist groups, and any resurgence would be handled from foreign soil. They further argue that the war was never to be won and, in any case, sustained engagement with the Taliban was otiose (Greentree, 2021). Whether or not this proposition is true is open for debate.

Nevertheless, one lesson Nigeria can learn from this is that over-reliance on military tactics alone cannot end the Boko Haram conflict and that it is only when dialogue fails that military aggression should be resorted to. And though it could be argued that the Boko Haram conflict started as a Non-international Armed Conflict (NIAC) and differs both in context and nature, the conflict is now regional, involving three of the four Lake Chad countries. Thus, whether NIAC or International Armed Conflict (IAC), a military approach is never the long-term solution and

should only be applied when all available options for dialogue are exhausted. As rightly put by Greenstock (2015), whether it is a rivalry between great powers or a regional power tension, every possibility for dialogue should be sought after no matter how painful that can be (Greenstock, 2015).

7.3.2 Dialogue and the future of counterterrorism in Nigeria

The dialogue approach to counterterrorism has become increasingly popular in the recent past, with both regional and international players searching for alternative strategies to combat terrorist activities within the Lake Chad region (Mahdi, 2020). There have also been rising calls for negotiations to end the Boko Haram conflict by some sections of the public, politicians, civil society organisations (CSO), and local and international NGOs in recent times. (Ibrahim et al., 2013; Vanguard, 2017; Bukarti, 2017; Olojo, 2019; Punch, 2020; Mahdi, 2020). The prominent Muslim leader in Nigeria even suggested a total and unconditional amnesty for Boko Haram in 2013 and was supported by a Pro-Norther group, the Arewa Consultative Forum (ACF), but the Christian Association of Nigerian (CAN) and the vast majority of the citizens especially, those victimised by Boko Haram condemned the call. The first call for amnesty came at a time when the Committee on Dialogue and Peaceful Resolution of Security Challenges in the North under President Jonathan's administration recommended that an advisory committee should be set up for continuous negotiation with the group after Boko Haram leaders turned down an invitation to dialogue with the committee (Nwankpa, 2014). More recently, the call for dialogue with the sect came from a coalition of 17 northern groups, including the Northern Elders Forum (NEF) and the Arewa Consultative Forum (ACF), during a meeting tagged 'Northern People's Summit' in Kaduna state. The call came amidst deteriorating standards of livelihood, economy, and rising insecurity in the North (Asadu, 2021).

Despite public disapproval of dialogue and amnesty advocacy for Boko Haram in the past, several amnesty programs have been set up by the government over the past few years, given the Nigerian military's failure to decisively defeat the group for over a decade. In 2014, the government initiated an amnesty-like program to pardon imprisoned Boko Haram members awaiting trial as part of a Counter Violence Extremism strategy (CVE). The deradicalisation strategy involved vocational training, anti-extremist religious education, recreational programs,

and mental/psychological therapy for the prisoners (Brechenmacher, 2018). Another amnesty program was set up through the Defence Headquarters in 2016 with the slogan ‘Operation Safe Corridor’ (OSC) and was designed to reform and re-orient low-risk repentant Boko Haram members just like the Niger Delta amnesty program in the eastern region (Irede, 2021). In addition, a similar initiative was also introduced in 2017 by the Buhari-led government called the Action Plan for Demobilization, Disassociation, Reintegration, and Reconciliation in collaboration with the International Organization for Migration (IOM). The initiative aims to reconcile and reintegrate those associated with Boko Haram back into society (Brechenmacher, 2018).

Even though the amnesty initiative of the Nigerian government is a demonstration of strong political will and commitment to restore peace and stability in the northeastern region, the initiative was haphazardly introduced out of desperation and without proper consideration of the implications and consequences. For instance, according to Brechenmacher (2018), Operation Safe Corridor has no clear reintegration element as detainees are being released without proper preparation or supervision, and some of the deradicalised terrorists have remained in detention based on a suspicion that they will be met with violent retaliation when freed (Brechenmacher, 2018). Another flaw in the amnesty program is that the victims and communities affected were not included in the design of the plan. Most of the victims are still grappling with the devastating effect of the war on their livelihoods, while others are trapped in filthy IDP camps even as the killings of civilians by the group persist. Furthermore, there are instances where the government returned ex-Boko Haram members without the consent of the host communities, and this has triggered mixed reactions and opposition that pose a serious hindrance to any realistic long-term reintegration effort (Reliefweb, 2020).

Therefore, despite the plausibility of the debate for national dialogue, it is likewise important to ensure that human rights violators are brought to justice and adequate and proper caution should be taken by the government with its amnesty plan for Boko Haram, given past failures not only in the country but the continent in general (Nwankpa, 2014). Furthermore, many local and international civil society organisations are advocating for a community-based reconciliation and reintegration process. This may help address the several ethnic and religious divisions that

manifested during the conflict, as well as between civilians and security agencies, those trapped in Boko Haram territories, and those who took refuge in IDP camps (Brechenmacher, 2018).

According to Olojo (2019), the government must engage adequately with local communities in the dialogue processes. This may help identify suitable mediators or third parties in the negotiation efforts (Olojo, 2019). This idea is also recognised by USAID, which advocates community-based dialogues for a better understanding of the host communities for the Boko Haram returnees to assess community needs and gauge possible needs for the returnees. Additionally, there is an ongoing collaboration between the IOM and the Nigerian authorities to create a tracking database for repentant Boko Haram going through the reintegration process in the Operation Safe Corridor program. Proper monitoring of the trajectories of the returning repentant terrorists without isolating the local communities will be critical to evaluating the efficacy of the rehabilitation program to provide a sufficient backup plan due to the dispersed nature of the reintegration process (Brechenmacher, 2018).

7.3.2 Community Policing

The pre-eminence of the debate on community policing as a crime-preventing mechanism in the 1980s and 1990s portrays encouraging characteristics with the shared duty logic of civic obligation. The main promoting factors of community policing popularity consist of the interest in police engagement in social work activities, the increased desire of the community to take charge of the solution to its disorder, a connection between a declined community participation in social institutions and disorder, the need for the backing of police legitimacy through positive community perceptions; and the shortcoming of orthodox crime controlling mechanism for preventing crime (Ratcliffe, 2004).

Even though the concept of a community-based security mechanism is originally targeted at securing a small geographical area, its proven effectiveness in intelligence gathering, identification of criminal elements and early dangers, as well as a swift response to security threats within a given community makes this approach suitable for domestic terrorism challenges such as insurgency. This is rightly observed by Frank Straub, US Director of the Centre for Mass Violence Response Studies, National Police Foundation, that many reports over the years suggest

that community policing, which is built on the relationships developed and sustained at the community level, has effectively helped in crime prevention and the identification of individuals and groups that pose a threat to security, and these are the foundations essential to preventing terrorism and targeted violence (NIJ, 2020).

Furthermore, a community-based approach to security that fosters collaboration between the members of the community and security agencies in the planning and execution of strategies to curtail crime and threats to human life within a community has been applied in several countries in the West and the African continent for many years. Drawing from some of the case studies in Africa, such as Rwanda, where this multi-agency approach through which the police, the citizens, and political officials at different levels partner with the government and other agencies to prevent crime and guarantee community safety, especially, in the post-Rwanda genocide, the findings show that when and if integrated into the state security apparatus, community policing would help in countering terrorism more effectively. This is mainly because a community-based approach to security is capable of addressing some of the critical challenges common in counterterrorism, such as intelligence gathering and surveillance. What this implies is that the communities affected by domestic terrorism can provide information about terrorist activities and even identify members of terrorist groups and their whereabouts through a partnership with security agencies hence, aid in dealing with the threat of terrorism much more effectively than a strictly militaristic approach. In supporting this proposition, the former member of the New York City FBI-NYPD Joint Terrorist Task Force and first responder to the attack on the World Trade Centre on 9/11, Frank Straub, postulate that there are many sources from which terrorism threats emanate, such as organised international groups, domestic groups, and individual attacker. Irrespective of the source, community policing is crucial in identifying potential criminals and terrorists who may be planning to perpetrate violent acts, getting communities prepared for threats, assisting government safety officers in responding to the threats, and in situations beyond prevention, helping the communities through recovery and reconciliation (NIJ, 2020).

Similar forms of community policing mechanisms, though in the form of vigilante groups, are also found in different parts of Nigeria that serve as crime-fighting and deterrence instruments in a community setting. However, one of the most prominent and effective forms of vigilante-style community policing identified in the findings is the Civilian Joint Task Force (CJTF) in

northeast Nigeria. The JTF, which was initially a vigilante group formed by the local youths in the Maiduguri metropolis, the Borno state capital, at the peak of the Boko Haram conflict to identify and fish out terrorist collaborators and sympathisers in their midst and protect their communities from terrorist attacks, was later recognised by the government and attached to the security forces to support the counterterrorism operations in the region. This is because, since its emergence, the local security outlet has demonstrated the capacity and ability to secure communities where they exist from attacks by Boko Haram at a time when the Nigerian military was helpless and incapable of tackling the insurgents.

Conversely, community policing is a unique and distinct approach to aggressive and militaristic responses to security. Orthodox, coercive counterterrorism measures isolate, ostracise, and oppress minority groups in society as collective suspects, damaging their trust in the state, which often results in the radicalisation of some members of the community. A community-based approach to security promotes democratic values in that it lessens the negative characteristics of heavy-handed strategies on police legitimacy (Brown, 2007). Therefore, the findings show that ever since the vigilante group, now the Civilian (JTF), was integrated into the security apparatus, it has tremendously contributed to the successes achieved by the Nigerian military in combating the Boko Haram insurgents and other Non-State Armed Groups in north-eastern Nigeria. This is mainly due to the critical role the group played and is still playing in the areas of intelligence gathering, surveillance, and assisting the military in navigating the difficult terrains of the terrorist strongholds in the towns, villages, and, later, the Sambisa Forest area which has now become their new home as it shields them against aerial attacks by government forces.

7.3.3 Deterrence as the solution

Abrahms (2014) asserts that terrorists derive inspiration from a vast range of personal and strategic objectives, and for this reason, they are poor candidates for deterrence. The multiplicity of these objectives ensures that the actions of many terrorists will be effective no matter how the government responds. He also claims that even opposite responses from the government tend to generate utility for terrorists because of the multifaceted nature of their incentive structure. Despite all these complications, Abrahms argues that, to a certain level, terrorism could still be deterred by discouraging its supporters since they are crucial for creating extensive terrorist

campaigns. This is because terrorist supporters are more deterrable in comparison to terrorists largely due to the simple nature of their 'incentive structure'. Contrary to popular belief that terrorism cannot be deterred on the premise that terrorists are basically undeterrable, he contends that this pessimistic view is baseless and that, indeed, terrorism can be deterred even though a lot of terrorists are undeterrable. This can be achieved through deterrence by de-legitimation, which, unlike deterrence by punishment and denial, is aimed at discrediting the culprits before their supporters. According to Abrahms, this strategy has large, unexploited strategic benefits. First; the ability of terrorists to perpetrate violence depends mainly on their level of support, according to him, because when there is growing support from the local population, terrorism threats also grow; second, supporters of terrorism are potential candidates for deterrence because of the simplicity of their incentive structure which enables the manipulation of costs and benefits strengthening the deterrence mechanism; and third, terrorist supporters are "deterrable" because they methodically overrate political worth of terrorism (Abrahms, 2014).

Another proponent of deterrence is Kirchofer. He postulates that cumulative deterrence can serve as a means for conflict prevention and management and help bring about more lasting political solutions to long-term hostilities. He claims that Israel has used cumulative deterrence by denial for a very long time to prevent aggression from both state and non-state actors. They achieve this by combining deterrence-by-punishment and coercion as well as indirect deterrence, Kirchofer noted. According to him, Israel's relative success in this regard suggests the importance of a persistent, long-term approach to managing non-state threats. Also, cumulative deterrence can serve as an alternative instrument for managing conflict in a situation where conflict resolution proves unattainable (Kirchofer, 2017).

Furthermore, Omand (2013) asserts that there are many enhanced means at the government's disposal today that can help build a strategy for countering terrorist threats, such as advanced defence technology and new digitised sources of intelligence. Nonetheless, these very promising strengths can result in the pursuit of short-term success only to discover that they have a negative consequence on future successes. He also asserts that other factors that have a negative impact on counter-terrorism efforts include local security crackdowns on minority groups, disproportionate encroachments on individual privacy in search of pre-emptive intelligence, and abuse of the rule of law in the process of prosecuting terrorists. Therefore, the problem lies not only in the choices

of ways and means but also in the ends of counter-terrorism measures. Thus, the major question remains: how can governments protect their people from an imminent terrorist threat and still defend civil liberty and democratic values? Although Omand claims that good governments will always prioritise national security however, he also, like other libertarians, cautions that governments must ensure that it does not encroach on fundamental human rights in the process (Omand, 2013).

Conclusion

This chapter has discussed the findings from the data analysed in the preceding chapters. The first sections highlighted human rights abuses such as indiscriminate, unlawful, and prolonged arrest and detention of suspects. Here, the circumstances within which suspects are arrested and the settings and conditions of the detention centres were presented. The second section highlighted the findings related to privacy violations, sexual abuses such as rape, extortion of civilians, lack of prosecution by the judiciary and the government's responses to these problems. The third section of this chapter presented the findings on the various forms of torture and inhumane and degrading treatment of suspects and other interrogation techniques used by the Nigerian military. Also, the effectiveness or ineffectiveness and the reliability of torture and its prevalence in counterterrorism operations in the northeast were discussed. Furthermore, the findings on the use of military force and its successes or lack of it in both domestic and international terrorism contexts, its implication for radicalisation and escalation of conflict, and consequences for international intervention have also been elaborated. The last two sections of this chapter discussed the findings on alternative strategies and approaches to counterterrorism, including their historical contexts, their applications elsewhere, their effectiveness in the past and present, and prospects for Nigeria's counterterrorism efforts.

CHAPTER EIGHT (8)

The Securitisation of Human Rights in Counterterrorism Operations

8.0 Introduction

To understand the concept of securitisation, it is important to first define security and the different contexts within which it is understood in international relations. Unlike social security, which is more focused on issues of entitlement and social justice, international security has strong roots in orthodox power politics and can be traced back to the traditional military conception of security. Understood as such, security, in the real sense, entails survival and is often linked to an impending threat to either the state or society. The unique nature of security threats validates the application of unprecedented measures to tackle them (Buzan et al. 1998). The importance attached to security is central to not just the use of force but also grounds for the state to mobilise exceptional powers to deal with impending threats (Wæver 1988, 1995b). When applied more broadly, an existential threat can mean different things depending on a given feature of the referent object.

However, securitisation transcends the normative rules of the game and depicts issues as special or above politics. As such, securitisation can be viewed as a more radical type of politicisation. In theory, any public issue can fall in the realm of politicised, non-politicised or securitised (Buzan, 1998). Nevertheless, this interconnectedness between politicisation and securitisation does not necessarily mean that securitisation is always the product of the state; it can also be found in other settings. According to Buzan et al. (1998), finding the best philosophical and analytical definitions of a concept is difficult as it largely depends on its usage and how people implicitly conceive and uniquely use it. Therefore, security is a self-referential practice, and in such practice, it thus becomes a security issue not because there is a real existential threat but because it is portrayed in that light.

Yet, in some states, even those that uphold liberal democratic values, security actors often resort to existential threat rhetoric to justify actions that would otherwise be considered a violation of human rights or secrecy. Securitisation is, thus, achieved when states successfully elevate this rhetoric to a level where existing laws no longer constrain them. This is the essence of successful

securitisation- the conjuring of existential threats, the implementation of emergency measures, and the consequences of breaking free from established rules. Within this context, states justify using extraordinary measures and sometimes even legitimise them in international relations and politics (Buzan et al., 1998). Since 9/11, this rhetoric has gained credibility in states' approach to and academic discourse on terrorism and counterterrorism, in which national security takes precedence over all other considerations, including human rights and civil liberties. Ample evidence of this claim in both international and domestic counterterrorism campaigns, including the Boko Haram conflict, has been judiciously presented throughout this thesis.

8.1 The rationalisation of securitisation in counterterrorism

Securitisation in terrorism manifests when state actors present terrorist threats in a survivalist form, requiring urgent and expedient action to save lives and protect the state against its enemies. Most often, states even dramatise or exaggerate terrorist threats to elevate them to a level of supreme priority to justify the extreme measures they intend to use (Wæver, 1988; Austin, 1975). Worst still, when military actors are involved, securitisation is easily institutionalised if a particular threat persists or when states confront an implacable and barbaric enemy (Wæver 1995b). From the point of view of this research, it is on this basis that state actors like the Nigerian military rationalised heavy-handed means to respond to Boko Haram's insurgency in northeastern Nigeria for national security interests regardless of their human rights implications. Buzan et al. (1998) argue that national security should not be idealised, and, like politicisation, securitisation should be viewed intersubjectively, and when states correctly or incorrectly securitised issues, it has consequences.

8.1.2 National security

In the Boko Haram context and from the research findings, one of the bases on which the Nigerian military frames its counterterrorism measures are, unsurprisingly, national security and state sovereignty. According to Oyewole (2020), Boko Haram's ideological mission to establish an Islamic Caliphate under Sharia law threatens not only Nigeria's stability but also challenges the legitimacy of the state and its authority. Viewed as such, the Nigerian military justifies

aggressive measures to counter Boko Haram in defence of its territorial integrity and salvage the country from falling apart (Oyewole, 2020). In the quest to preserve Nigeria's sovereignty and integrity, national security concerns often result in extreme measures such as the declaration of martial law, indiscriminate attacks on civilian targets and extrajudicial killings.

8.1.3 Global counterterrorism efforts

The Nigerian military's counterinsurgency tactics are also framed under the purview of the GWOT as Boko Haram is considered an aspect of a transnational terrorism phenomenon and consolidates global counterterrorism efforts championed by the US, UN and AU. The framing of securitisation in this form often expands military powers in such a way that they violate normative human rights principles such as unlawful detention and privacy violations. A good example of this form of overreaching military powers is contained in the Terrorism Prevention Act 2011 and 2013 as amended, which confers powers of indefinite detention of terrorist suspects and other acts contrary to international human rights standards (Iyekekpolo, 2016).

8.1.4 Collateral damage

Collateral damage and the cost of war also underpin an aspect of the securitisation construct in the Boko Haram counterterrorism operations. From this point of view, military actions are rationalised as a necessity, and any unforeseeable repercussions find legitimacy in the greater good of all and in the urgency of eliminating terrorist threats. This type of securitisation rhetoric is responsible for mass civilian murders, sporadic and coercive military raids and violent acts that are tantamount to war crimes and derogation of the rules of engagement in armed conflict (Amnesty International, 2015).

8.1.5 National unity

Furthermore, securitisation is sometimes legitimised through military posture as the protector of national unity and peace, and under this guise, the imposition of heavy-handed measures such as

curfews, checkpoints and stop and search are projected as paramount for Nigeria's survival. Based on this narrative, the Nigerian military often seeks to earn public support, and whenever there is a backlash or criticism of its aggressive tactics, dissidents are criminalised and ostracised as terrorist collaborators and harshly dealt with (Campbell and Harwood, 2018).

8.1.6 Complexity of guerrilla warfare

Due to the unconventional nature of terrorism that is characterised by suicide bombings, ambushes, hit and run, and the use of civilians as shields, the Nigerian military often insists that civilian casualties are inevitable in this type of warfare. Indiscriminate aerial and ground attacks and raids that put civilian lives in grave danger are justified within this security rhetoric. This was a common military narrative in the early stages of the conflict when the Nigerian military was clueless and helpless on how to tackle Boko Haram's guerrilla tactics. Iheduru (2017) backs this claim when he contends that the military's reputation became highly questionable eight years after the Boko Haram insurgency began due to embarrassing defeats it suffered in its counterterrorism and counterinsurgency operations against the sect in northeastern Nigeria. Their lack of professionalism was further exacerbated by allegations of human rights abuses and violations of the rules of engagement in armed conflicts. Despite their recent combat successes against the insurgents, public perception regarding their professionalism has continued to decline (Iheduru, 2017).

8.1.7 Ignorance of the Law

One of the most surprising revelations on why the Nigerian military justifies the use of extreme measures and human rights abuses is the lack of knowledge of human rights and rules of engagement in armed conflict. Many of the officers indicted for alleged violations of the laws of war and crimes against civilians insist that they were not knowledgeable of the concept of human rights law and how it applies in armed conflict. In fact, the research findings reveal that even officers who served in several peacekeeping missions in Africa under ECOMOG are no

exceptions. Human rights violations such as torture, inhumane and degrading treatment of suspects, including IDPs, extortion and sexual abuses are commonly downplayed or whitewashed to protect the military's reputation.

The rationalisation of security in this way to counter terrorism and terrorist threats both within broader international and domestic contexts, as this research findings show, military actions, despite their noble intentions and purposes, when conducted in disregard of the laws of armed conflict and international human rights and humanitarian law can be counterproductive and exacerbate the same security threats it seeks to counter.

Thus, by examining the Boko Haram conflict from a securitisation standpoint, these research findings contribute to the ongoing debate in terrorism and security studies on why and how states rationalised the use of extraordinary measures that are antithetical to established international norms and laws of armed conflict and facilitate a better understanding of how to balance security concerns and the demands for human rights. Also, academics, security experts, CSOs, NGOs and state actors, especially the Nigerian military, will benefit from the insights the research provides to develop new or improve existing legislations, policies and strategies to deal with security threats posed by terrorism and other NSAGs.

CHAPTER NINE (9)

CONCLUSION

This research has examined the nature and extent of allegations of human rights violations by the Nigerian military in the Boko Haram conflict in northeastern Nigeria. The interplay between human rights and security and how the need for security and the demand for individual rights in armed conflict could be balanced was also analysed. Additionally, this study further examined the issue of compliance with international standards and how that can be secured in armed conflicts, such as domestic insurgency like the Boko Haram conflict. Also, to gain a broader perspective and better understanding of most of the contentious issues on counterterrorism, this study made several references to the US and UK due to their leadership role in the GWOT and in some instances, comparative analyses were made implicitly or explicitly to draw lessons from history, support or argue against a particular issue, or provide historical evidence.

Theoretically, the study adopted the realist and liberalist theories of international relations to examine the intersection between human rights and security. These two theories guided the literature review's operationalisation and the development of the interview questions. While on the one hand, national interest and sovereignty are accorded ample consideration above human rights in the realist school of thought, the liberalist school espouses rules and procedures, interdependence and regimes, and convergence on national preferences.

Methodologically, the study was undertaken qualitatively using a single case study research design to aid in the holistic investigation of the problem of upholding, respecting, and preserving human rights in armed conflict with more clarity and focus. Due to the qualitative nature of the study, an interpretive rather than a positivist method was used to unravel how the counterterrorism efforts of the Nigerian military affect or impact civil liberty and human rights in the Boko Haram conflict. The study is also embedded in the constructivist philosophical outlook, which helped the researcher to understand individuals' viewpoints and, in this case, the experiences of victims of human rights violations and the context in which these views are derived.

Furthermore, the study utilised secondary and primary data sources, with the former consisting mainly of textbooks, journal articles and NGO reports, notably Amnesty International and Human Rights Watch, while the latter consisted of open-ended interviews with IDPs, security officials, legislatures and other relevant stakeholders. Interviews were conducted face-to-face in two phases involving a visit to 2 IDP camps in the conflict-stricken northeast, the National Assembly, Amnesty International and the National Human Rights Commission's headquarters in Abuja, the Federal Capital of Nigeria.

The study established that several human rights violations were committed by the Nigerian military, especially in the early stages of the conflict. Common among these violations are torture, inhumane and degrading treatment of suspects, extrajudicial killings, unlawful arrest and prolonged detention of suspects, forced disappearances, privacy violations, rape and sexual abuses, especially in IDP and detention camps. These abuses were rampant and persistent for the most part of the conflict and have provoked anti-government protests, resulted in the radicalisation of civilians in the affected communities and escalated and exacerbated the problem in the early stages of the insurgency.

In addition, though military tactics have produced some great results in terms of territorial control in the northeast, they have been largely ineffective in the overall aspect of the conflict. Some factors attributed to this include a lack of adequate and advanced weapons and ammunition and a shortage of trained and experienced military personnel in warfare such as insurgency. In contrast, evidence from the study indicates that a non-coercive counterterrorism approach has yielded better results than military force. These results are evidenced in the successful release of several kidnapped and abducted civilians, famous among them being the Chibok girls, which have attracted significant attention globally. Accordingly, the amnesty strategy for repentant insurgents has led to the surrendering of thousands of Boko Haram fighters and their families since the start of the initiative by the Nigerian government.

Furthermore, the study found that a more subtle and diplomatic approach would be more effective in ending the prolonged conflict. Specifically, dialogue and community policing have been revealed to be the best alternatives to a militaristic approach. The successes of these approaches in similar conflicts in Africa have been cross-analysed to support this finding further. At the heart of community policing is intelligence gathering and surveillance, which has proven

to be the most critical factor in counterterrorism globally, which is also seriously lacking in the context of Nigeria's counter-insurgency efforts. It is, however, worth noting that there have been several failed efforts at dialoguing with Boko Haram by the Nigerian government in the past, which has been attributed to poor planning and lack of sincerity on the side of the government that created distrust and hinders any realistic future negotiations. Notwithstanding these shortcomings, this study suggests that negotiations and dialogue are still possible with proper and adequate planning and strong political will from the Nigerian government. Although, at the time of writing this conclusion, the operations of Boko Haram in the northeast have been significantly reduced due to increased government spending on military warheads, improved aerial bombardments, and the joint effort of the Multinational Joint Taskforce (MJTF) the group remains an ever-present threat in the region as attacks on both civilian and military targets still occur daily, and their activities have now spread across Cameroon, Chad and Niger.

Finally, unlike most research on the Boko Haram conflict in Nigeria that focuses on already well-known topical issues, this research is among the few, if not the first, to examine the conflict and its impact on human rights within the context of international relations and law. It is equally novel in that it goes beyond a mere examination of the literature and laws to examine instead the complex relationship between human rights and violent conflicts and how human rights treaty obligations should apply in practice in armed conflicts such as domestic terrorism and insurgency. This is even more critical given the conundrum in the discourse on states' moral limits in responding to and their tendencies to trump all other considerations in dealing with domestic terrorism for national security. Within this context, this research hopes to contribute to the literature by first expanding the discussion to domestic terrorism and the state's obligations to human rights integral to liberal democracy. Most importantly, the insights from the Boko Haram case study will contribute to the ongoing securitisation debate in international relations and provide a better understanding of how and why state actors rationalised the securitisation of human rights in armed conflicts, both international and domestic.

Recommendations and suggestions for further study

Intelligence gathering and synergy among security agencies

Since the 9/11 attacks, counterterrorism, or the GWOT, as popularly coined by the US government, has become synonymous with military tactics across the globe. From the US counterterrorism campaign against al-Qaeda in Afghanistan and Iraq to the War against ISIS in Syria and Iran, the use of military force has been at the forefront of its counterterrorism strategy and widely replicated in other countries grappling with similar threats of terrorism and insurgency. Though it could be argued that, to a certain extent, military tactics have decimated al-Qaeda and killed its founder and subsequent successors, as in the case of ISIS and even Boko Haram in Nigeria, the end results in all these cases have been largely disappointing. The US withdrawal from Afghanistan and the immediate takeover of power by al-Qaeda are typical proof of this. In Africa as a whole, and in Nigeria's case, to be specific, terrorism is a new phenomenon that is yet to be fully understood, and the changing conflict dynamics make it even more challenging for the government. While on the one hand, Boko Haram-controlled territories in northeastern Nigeria were recaptured and liberated by the military Multinational Joint Task Force (MJTF), on the other hand, there is now a splinter Boko Haram group called the Islamic State of West African Province (ISWAP) and the group's activities are wreaking havoc in the towns and villages in the northeast and the border communities across four countries in the Lake Chad region with devastating impact on farming, trading, fishing, education and livelihoods. Given this evidence, it is a glaring fact that the effectiveness and success of a military approach to counterterrorism is limited, temporal, and short-term.

Therefore, countries faced with domestic terrorism, like Nigeria, must learn from history and refocus their counterterrorism efforts towards a non-violent and aggressive approach such as counterintelligence and surveillance, which are now some of the most sought-after counterterrorism and counterinsurgency strategies. A departure from the reactive to an intelligence and diplomatic approach to both international and domestic terrorism is required, and Nigeria and the rest of the world must tap into the benefits of the emerging and advanced intelligence-gathering techniques to decisively deal with terrorism threats. Moreover, the lack of synergy, cooperation, and collective national commitment to counterinsurgency due to

unnecessary competition and senseless rivalry among Nigeria's security agencies must be immediately addressed. Despite several claims of renewed cooperation among the security institutions at different fora, it is still difficult to ascertain the level of cooperation or its effectiveness as there is yet to be any significant visible improvement.

Institutionalising and strengthening community policing

For the Nigerian government's counterterrorism efforts and programs to produce the much-needed and desired result to decisively and effectively end the Boko Haram insurgency in the northeast, community policing must be integrated into its security architecture. Unlike the traditional policing practice that is reactive, the concept of community policing is mainly preventive. Community policing has been incorporated into the policing system in different parts of the world to prevent crime through collaboration, partnership, and collective effort between the police and the community they serve. By promoting and strengthening police-community relations, crime prevention and reduction is made easy as trust between the police and community members, often lacking in traditional policing, is built and strengthened, and community members become active agents and participants in dealing with issues directly affecting them. As revealed in this study's findings, one of the major benefits of this concept is intelligence gathering and surveillance, which are crucial elements of counterterrorism. Thus, when blended with the ongoing counterterrorism strategies in the fight against Boko Haram in Nigeria's northeast, community policing will be a catalysing agent in the prevention of violent extremism, radicalisation, and other terrorist-related crimes such as kidnapping and abductions for ransom, which is now a common strategy use by insurgents and other NSAGs in northeastern Nigeria.

Moreover, much research shows that police legitimacy and effectiveness increase when they work collaboratively with the locals with a common goal than otherwise. The Civilian JTF in the northeast is a very good example of this and is another reason why the Nigerian government must continue to improve and solidify the task force through combat training and orientation on the rules of engagement to ensure the safety of civilians. In addition, there is no better time to re-commit to the rising popular advocacy among state governors, legislators, local government, and religious and traditional leaders for the establishment of state policing to create a localised security mechanism to address the endemic and deplorable state of security in the country

resulting from the incapacitated and almost completely failed federal police system. More essentially, state policing will benefit from the traditional security system with the support of traditional and community leaders who, aside from being highly respected authorities, are also closer to the people than the government. Hence, their contribution and instrumentality to crime prevention, law enforcement, and order at the local level, as well as their wider implications for the counterterrorism efforts of the Nigerian government, cannot be overemphasised.

Dialogue, amnesty, and counter-violence extremism programmes

Considering the level of the ineffectiveness of military force, as evidenced by the prolonged and polarised nature of the Boko Haram conflict, it begs for a diplomatic and non-violent approach to provide a lasting and enduring solution to the insurgency in northeastern Nigeria. However, this does not imply a total abandonment of military tactics but rather a diversified and multi-dimensional approach whereby a combination of military and non-military efforts are employed towards dealing with the conflict. The government must, therefore, develop genuine and realistic programs to engage with Boko Haram leadership through dialogue and negotiation. Historical evidence of the successes of this approach in different conflict contexts across the globe, especially in Africa and even in Nigeria, gives more credence to this recommendation. And despite a few past setbacks in the negotiations with Boko Haram, largely due to a lack of proper and comprehensive planning, the process led to the successful release of hundreds of abducted civilians and prisoner exchange, popular among them the Chibok girls.

Consequently, a more holistic, inclusive, and multi-level approach is needed to correct past and avoid future failure. The government must develop an achievable long-term peace agreement framework involving traditional and religious leaders, civil society, and non-governmental organisations. This is in addition to the existing Counter Violence Extremism (CVE) programmes, such as Operation Safe Corridor and the Demobilisation, Disassociation, Reintegration, and Reconciliation (DDR) program for Boko Haram suspects and civilian collaborators. More importantly, the government must address some of the criticism associated with these programmes. For instance, the DDR lacks clearly stated selection and eligibility criteria for the release or prosecution of surrendered terrorists in that it proposes an unconditional amnesty for all repentant Boko Haram fighters, which is met with outright rejection by most communities in the northeast and opposed by civil society organisations. Similarly, Operation

Safe Corridor is narrow in scope, lacking a transparent vetting process for determining low and high-risk suspects and a clear reintegration strategy, which creates public scepticism on the genuineness and motives of the repentant terrorists. Thus, the Nigerian government must reform the existing Counter Violence Extremism programmes to address these challenges, which should involve developing a well spelt-out vetting process for determining low and high-risk suspects, and a legal pathway for the prosecution of captured and high-level terrorists, systematic and long-term reintegration programme, and the involvement of host communities in the planning and implementation of the reintegration processes, to build trust and gain the confidence of the members of the host communities.

Accountability for human rights violations

Since the Boko Haram insurgency began, there has been widespread public outcry and dismay at the Nigerian government's reluctance to prosecute war crime criminals and human rights violators. Moreover, in most instances, allegations of violations against military personnel are either downplayed or denied by the military authorities and other security agencies. Just like any democratic state, the Nigerian government has a constitutional obligation to ensure the protection of individual rights and civil liberties, compliance with the provisions of domestic and international human rights law and the prosecution of offenders. Unfortunately, cases of human rights abuses in the Boko Haram conflict have been poorly handled, and there is yet to be any significant effort to demonstrate any strong political will or commitment to ensure justice for the victims and measures to deter the future and continuous occurrence of these violations. Most previous efforts to investigate and prosecute indicted military officers on human rights violations were neither convincing nor transparent. For instance, the outcome of the investigations of several disciplinary boards, Federal and State judicial panels of inquiry, and other investigative committees set up by the presidency was secretive, and the number of prosecutions from the outcome of such investigations is few and usually disproportionate to the petitions.

In 2022, the Nigerian government passed a law establishing a special court to handle cases of human rights violations by members of the Nigerian security forces in the Boko Haram conflict. However, since the law was passed, the number of prosecutions remains very few, and there is no indication of any meaningful improvement in the near future. The only recent prosecution of military personnel for cases of human rights violations was a ten-year sentencing of a former

commander and a death sentence of a group of soldiers for the murder of 12 civilians in March and May 2023, respectively. Hundreds of similar cases and petitions are still awaiting trials. The Nigerian government must, therefore, show a strong commitment and political will to prosecuting war crimes against and crimes against civilians by ensuring that the judicial proceedings and the outcome of investigations of the various panels of inquiry are not only independent and apolitical but also public. The lack of political will and the government's reluctance to prosecute military and other security personnel for crimes against civilians in the Boko Haram conflict has negatively impacted the counterinsurgency efforts in northeastern Nigeria and made civil-military relations almost impossible. A case in point is the failure to publish names of Boko Haram collaborators, consisting of former and serving government officials, including ministers, governors, security chiefs, and top military commanders, let alone prosecute them.

Suggestion for further study

Dealing with elite sabotage

Even in the pre-Boko Haram conflict, corruption, lack of accountability and poor performance have already created a serious distrust between the public and the established security forces. The lack of synergy between security agencies has also been responsible for the late and often aggressive responses to domestic security challenges that are synonymous with the northeast and across the length and breadth of Nigeria (NSRP, 2017). Although there is improvement in civil-military relations in some of the affected communities due to the Nigerian military's recent counterinsurgency successes, fear and scepticism in most of the populace remained pervasive.

Intelligence leaks from top military officers are the most worrisome factor in the sabotage. Oriole (2021) documents evidence that supports these allegations from interviews with senior and non-commissioned officers in charge of strategy and troop mobility in the Nigerian armed forces. A General in the Nigerian army also disclosed that the military hierarchy was deliberately reluctant to provide tactical or expert support for counterinsurgency missions under the past government. The study further suggests that the sabotage also had serious religious, ethnic and political undertone as some of the military hierarchy from Northern Nigeria were complacency in the counterinsurgency to favour the immediate past Muslim President Muhammadu Buhari

from the north against the then sitting Christian President Goodluck Jonathan from the south in the 2015 general elections.

In addition, there were also allegations of syndicates consisting of politicians, General Officer Commanding (GOCs) and civilians that exist as part of an organised war scheme involved in the secret release of detained terrorist suspects. A list of Four hundred (400) names of Boko Haram sponsors and collaborators and an additional 800 was promised by the Attorney General of the Federation to be published and prosecuted in 2021. Still, to date, not a single name has been published, nor was anyone prosecuted for that matter, which further supports allegations of Jonathan's administration on top public officials, security personnel, and politicians sympathetic to Boko Haram than Nigeria's stability and security. This problem seriously undermines all counterinsurgency efforts in northern Nigeria, and the newly elected government must make every effort and take realistic steps to investigate and fish out all parties in this despicable and treasonable offence. Therefore, this study suggests further research on this issue as there is little to no original research on this despite the several allegations from both public and government authorities throughout the Boko Haram conflict. The study will help provide evidence of the elite complacency in counterterrorism efforts, possibly identify perpetrators to face prosecution and help cut terrorism funding and support, and address existing obstacles caused by the sabotage. Otherwise, the so-called counterterrorism efforts will only be self-destructive and self-defeating.

Appendix

Research Ethics Approval

Approval Letter

26/11/2020

Dear David Dan-Azumi, your **application 13294: Violent Conflict and Human Rights Violations in Nigeria: A Study of the War Against Boko Haram**, submission 11992, has been approved by the Education and Social Sciences SEC. You may now proceed with your study. If you wish to make any significant changes to the study, you must seek the committee's approval before actioning them.

Good luck with your research.

Dr Iain McPhee

Informed Consent Form

Title of Project: Violent conflicts and human rights violations in Nigeria: a study of the war against Boko Haram

Ethics Approval Number: **13294**

Personal details withheld.

Student's name: David Dan-Azumi

Researcher's [REDACTED]

You will read the following statements, and the researcher will ask for your verbal agreement. The researcher will record verbal agreement by initialling the boxes below and recording signatures.

I confirm that I have read/been read and understand the information sheet for the above study. I have had the opportunity to consider the information, ask questions and have these answered satisfactorily.

Initials

I understand that my participation is voluntary and that I am free to withdraw at any time without giving any reason.

Initials

I consent to the processing of my personal information (name, gender, age) for the purposes explained to me. I understand that such information will be handled in accordance with all applicable data protection legislation.

Initials

I understand that my data will be treated confidentially, and any publication resulting from this work will report only data that does not identify me.

Initials

I agree to have my voice/likeness digitally recorded.

Initials

I freely agree to participate in this study.

Initials

Signatures:

Name of participant:

Name of researcher:

Date:

Date:

Participant Information Sheet

Violent Conflicts and Human Rights Violations in Nigeria: A Study of the War against Boko Haram.

You are invited to take part in a research study. Before you decide, it is important for you to understand why the research is being done and what it will involve. Please take time to read the following information carefully and discuss it with others if you wish. I will also read the key parts of this information to you prior to any participation. Please ask me if anything is unclear or if you want more information. Take time to decide whether or not you wish to take part.

What is the purpose of this study?

I am a PhD research student at the University of the West of Scotland, and I am researching the Boko Haram conflict. The study seeks to understand if and how the counter-terrorism measures of government security agencies violate the civil liberty and human rights of civilians in conflict areas. The findings from this study are expected to shed light on 'alleged' cases of human rights violations and proffer policy recommendations on how best to address the problems.

Why have I been chosen?

You are chosen to participate in this research because of your direct (or indirect) experience with the Boko Haram conflict. In general, participants in this study are selected on the basis of their experience and knowledge of the research topic and not based on educational qualifications or political, religious, or ethnic affiliations.

Do I have to take part?

There will be no consequences of any kind if you choose not to participate, answer any question, or even discontinue the interview at any given time, as participation in this research is not mandatory for any participant.

What will happen to me if I take part?

If you agree to participate in this research, you will be asked to engage in an interview with the researcher (Mr David Villah Dan-Azumi). The interview will last for a minimum of 40 and a maximum of 60 minutes. The interview will be audiotaped. However, if you are uncomfortable with audio recording, notes will be taken instead. The main themes to be discussed are the Boko Haram insurgency in the northeastern part of the country, the responses of and measures used by Nigerian security agencies and how these measures violate human rights or not.

What are the possible disadvantages and risks of taking part?

Due to the topic's sensitive nature, there may be psychological implications as you recollect and narrate your past ordeal or experiences in the conflict, especially if you or someone you know is directly affected by the conflict. If this occurs at any stage of the interview, you can decide to discontinue the interview and seek professional help. In the event this occurs, I will endeavour to refer you to the necessary expert. For participants who are currently serving personnel in any of the security agencies, be assured that this interview is highly confidential, and as such, your identity will be kept unanimous. This is to guarantee that the information you share remains confidential, with no possible backlash from the authority on account of the information provided.

What are the possible benefits of taking part?

Your participation in this interview will immensely contribute towards understanding the nature of the Boko Haram insurgency in Nigeria and assist in determining how government responses have impacted human rights and civil liberties. This research also affords you the privilege to share any direct act of human rights violations you experienced in your encounter with the security agencies in the Boko conflict.

Data Protection Privacy Notice

The University of the West of Scotland (UWS) is the institution in charge of handling the data for this research. All activities that involve handling personal data are under the supervision of the UWS Data Protection office and can be reached via this email address: dataprotection@uws.ac.uk.

The provision of your consent will serve as the legal basis on which your personal data will be handled. You can give verbal consent for your personal data to be used in this research before the research begins and after the researcher has fully briefed you verbally and provided you with an information sheet.

Participation in this study will be kept confidential, and to ensure this, your personal data and the use of all information given shall be restricted only for the purpose of this research. Also, each participant will be given a code name, and should any of them request anonymity of either themselves or the individuals they talk about, their identity will be kept as such. Participants who wish to withdraw from participating have the right to do so within 28 days after the data is collected. If you wish, you can do so through my contact details at the end of this form.

If you have any concerns regarding the handling of your personal data, you should please inform UWS through dataprotection@uws.ac.uk. If you still have any reservations, you may further contact the Information Commissioner's Office (ICO) at [www.https://ico.org.uk/for-organisations/data-protection-reform/overview-of-the-gdpr/individuals-rights](https://ico.org.uk/for-organisations/data-protection-reform/overview-of-the-gdpr/individuals-rights).

What will happen to the results of the research study?

The study is strictly for academic purposes. As such, it is non-profit or commercial. The findings of this study will mainly form part of my final thesis for the award of a doctorate in International Relations. The findings may also be published as journal articles, conference papers, and book chapters during and after my studies.

Who has reviewed the study?

The body that will review this study shall be the Ethics Committee of the School of Education and Social Sciences (ESS) at UWS.

Who has reviewed the study?

The body that will review this study shall be the Ethics Committee of the School of Education and Social Sciences (ESS) at UWS.

Contact me for further information.

If you require any further information, please contact:

David Villah Dan-Azumi

University of the West of Scotland,
Paisley, Scotland,
PA1 2BE P

Personal details withheld.

Telephone: [REDACTED]

E-mail address: [REDACTED]

Dr Colin Atkinson

The University of the West of Scotland,
Paisley, Scotland,
PA1 2BE

Telephone: [REDACTED]

E-mail address: [REDACTED]

Thank you for taking part in this study.

Codebook screenshot

Name	Files	References	Created On	Created By	Modified On	Modified By
Alternative Strategy to Combat Boko Haram	3	3	26/08/2021 13:2	DAVID VILLAH	27/08/2021 12:18	DAVID VILLAH
Alternatives to Torture	2	6	27/08/2021 12:2	DAVID VILLAH	27/08/2021 13:24	DAVID VILLAH
Balancing HR & Security	2	2	26/08/2021 13:2	DAVID VILLAH	27/08/2021 12:20	DAVID VILLAH
Checks on HR Violations	1	1	26/08/2021 15:0	DAVID VILLAH	26/08/2021 15:05	DAVID VILLAH
Compatability of HR & Security	3	4	26/08/2021 13:2	DAVID VILLAH	27/08/2021 12:17	DAVID VILLAH
Dialogue, Comm. Policing & Intelligence Gathering	3	4	26/08/2021 13:1	DAVID VILLAH	27/08/2021 12:05	DAVID VILLAH
Effectiveness & Realiability of Torture	4	7	26/08/2021 13:3	DAVID VILLAH	27/08/2021 13:19	DAVID VILLAH
Evidence of HR Violations	3	7	26/08/2021 13:3	DAVID VILLAH	27/08/2021 12:26	DAVID VILLAH
Evidence of Torture	3	4	26/08/2021 13:3	DAVID VILLAH	27/08/2021 12:25	DAVID VILLAH
General Views on HR Violations in Nigeria	1	1	27/08/2021 12:3	DAVID VILLAH	27/08/2021 12:31	DAVID VILLAH
HR in Emergency Situations	3	4	26/08/2021 13:2	DAVID VILLAH	27/08/2021 12:16	DAVID VILLAH
HR Violations & Radicalisation of Civilians	4	7	26/08/2021 13:1	DAVID VILLAH	27/08/2021 13:01	DAVID VILLAH
International HR Laws in Nigeria	3	3	26/08/2021 13:0	DAVID VILLAH	27/08/2021 11:59	DAVID VILLAH
Justification for Torture	4	6	26/08/2021 13:2	DAVID VILLAH	27/08/2021 13:18	DAVID VILLAH
Liberalist Perspective of HR	2	4	26/08/2021 13:1	DAVID VILLAH	26/08/2021 14:45	DAVID VILLAH
Prevalence of HR Violations	2	7	26/08/2021 15:0	DAVID VILLAH	27/08/2021 12:26	DAVID VILLAH
Prevalence of Torture	2	2	26/08/2021 13:3	DAVID VILLAH	26/08/2021 15:10	DAVID VILLAH
Prioritising HR To Successfully Combat Boko Haram	3	3	26/08/2021 13:2	DAVID VILLAH	27/08/2021 12:18	DAVID VILLAH
Protection of HR During Mil. Operations	3	4	26/08/2021 13:0	DAVID VILLAH	27/08/2021 11:59	DAVID VILLAH
Protection of HR Under Democracy	4	4	26/08/2021 13:1	DAVID VILLAH	27/08/2021 13:04	DAVID VILLAH
Realist Perspective of HR	2	2	26/08/2021 13:2	DAVID VILLAH	26/08/2021 14:23	DAVID VILLAH
Respect for HR by Govt & Security Agencies	4	7	26/08/2021 13:1	DAVID VILLAH	27/08/2021 12:50	DAVID VILLAH
Safeguarding Lives & Prop. Without Violating HR	4	5	26/08/2021 13:2	DAVID VILLAH	27/08/2021 12:40	DAVID VILLAH
Security Refere HR	4	5	26/08/2021 13:1	DAVID VILLAH	27/08/2021 13:11	DAVID VILLAH

Codebook with references

Selected Node: Dialogue, Comm. Policing & Intel

References:

- <Files\Agent X Interview> - 1 reference coded [1.86% Coverage]
 - Reference 1 - 1.86% Coverage

Well, I think community policing can assist in curbing the insurgency in the North-East. But I don't think dialogue itself is capable of ending the conflict.
- <Files\NHRC Staff.docx 2> - 2 references coded [5.74% Coverage]
 - Reference 1 - 2.86% Coverage

I don't think dialogue with terrorist is the best. Why I am saying this is because it won't be possible. I think from the beginning that is what they used in the first place i.e. having dialogue with the leaders of the Boko Haram before the conflict escalated.
 - Reference 2 - 2.88% Coverage

I know there was a time they took the then Boko Haram leader called Mohammed Yusuf to the police station where they tortured and interviewed him on the agenda of the group and what they are doing. At the end, the conflict escalated and then lead to his death.

Nodes screenshot

Violent Conflicts and HR Violations in Nig.

Nodes

Name	Description	Files	References
Alternative Strategy to Combat Boko Haram		3	3
Alternatives to Torture		2	6
Balancing HR & Security		2	2
Checks on HR Violations		1	1
Compatability of HR & Security		3	4
Dialogue, Comm. Policing & Intelligence Gathering		3	4
Effectiveness & Reliability of Torture		4	7
Evidence of HR Violations		3	7
Evidence of Torture		3	4
General Views on HR Violations in		1	1

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